

Master Thesis
Governing AI With Trias Politica

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Table of Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
CHAPTER 1 - INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 Background and context for this research	8
1.1.1 Small overview of AI adoption across different industries.....	8
1.1.2 The Increasing risk of AI bias and unfair-decision-making.....	8
1.1.3 The need of a centralised coordination of the global development on AI initiatives	9
1.1.4 The role of Trias Politica principles in an AI governance framework.	10
1.2 Problem statement	10
1.2.1 Assumptions/Hypothesis	11
1.2.2 Validation of Assumption by gathering Expert's insights	11
1.3 Research Question	12
1.3.1 Problem decomposition	12
CHAPTER 2 – LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.1 Introduction to the Literature Review	14
2.1.1 Purpose and scope of literature review	14
2.1.2 Alignment with the Research Question and Research Sub-Questions	14
2.1.3 AI Definition and Lifecycle of AI in context of this Research	14
2.2 Understanding Bias in AI Systems Implications and Risks	15
2.2.1 Definitions, Classification, and Sources of Bias in AI	16
2.2.2 Critical Implications: Trust, Fairness, and Organisational Risk.....	17
2.3 Mechanisms for AI Bias Mitigation and the Central Role of Governance ..	19
2.3.1 Strategies for Mitigating AI Bias Through Governance	19
2.3.2 Foundations and Structures of AI Governance: Building Responsible AI Systems.....	20
2.3.3 Ethical Principles as Pillars of Bias-Resilient AI.....	22
2.3.4 Governance as a Core Function in AI Risk and Bias Management.....	22
2.4 Regulatory Approaches to Bias: The EU AI Act in Focus.....	23
2.4.1 Scope of the EU AI Act	24
2.4.2 Provisions directly related to diversity, non-discrimination and fairness.	25
2.4.3 Key Findings	26
2.5 Synthesis of reviewed Literature	27
2.5.1 Understanding AI Bias Across the Lifecycle	27
2.5.2 Key Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation	28
2.5.3 Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles as Governance Foundations.....	28
2.5.4 Alignment with EU AI Act Requirements	28
2.5.5 Integration into Broader Corporate Governance Structures.....	29
2.5.6 Challenges in Bias Mitigation and AI Governance	29
CHAPTER 3 – METHODOLOGY	31
3.1 Research approach.....	31
3.2 Applied Methodology and Methods	33
3.2.1 Finding answers for RSQ1	33
3.2.2 Finding answers for RSQ2	33
3.2.3 Finding answers for RSQ3	33
3.3 Literature Review	34

3.3.1 Data Sources and Search Strategy	34
3.3.2 Critical Literature review for RSQ1.....	34
3.3.3 Critical Literature review for RSQ3.....	36
3.4 Case Study	37
3.5 Focused Group Workshop	37
3.6 Qualitative Analysis	38
3.7 Expert Validation Workshop	38
3.8 Use of GSS as a foundational methodology	38
3.9 Summary.....	39
CHAPTER 4 – ANALYSIS.....	40
4.1 Qualitative Analysis	40
4.1.1 Theme 1: Understanding Bias Types, Sources, and Lifecycle Phases.....	41
4.1.2 Theme 2: Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation	41
4.1.3 Theme 3: Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles.....	42
4.1.4 Theme 4: Integration into Corporate Governance Structures	42
4.1.5 Theme 5: Trias Politica–Based Governance Structure.....	42
4.1.6 Theme 6: Compliance with Eu AI Act.	44
4.1.7 Overview of Thematic Analysis	44
CHAPTER 5 - RESULTS.....	46
5.1 Results RSQ1: Bias in AI and Governance-Based Mitigation Strategies	46
5.2 Results RSQ2: Trias Politica–Based Governance Structure	48
5.2.1 Governance Structure – Separation of Powers	48
5.2.2 Governance Processes.....	48
5.2.3 Role of AI Principles	48
5.2.4 Relational Mechanisms and Informal Structures.....	48
5.2.5 Integration into Corporate Governance Structures	49
5.3 Results RSQ3: Compliance with EU AI Act.....	49
5.3.1 Risk-Based Classification	49
5.3.2 High-Risk AI Compliance Requirements	49
5.3.3 Governance Structure Requirements	50
5.4 Answering the Research Question (RQ)	50
5.5 Results Expert Validation Session.....	57
5.5.1 Confidence Ratings and Validation.....	57
5.5.2 Confirming Completeness	58
5.5.3 Qualitative Feedback and Key Insights.....	58
5.5.4 Identified Research Gaps and Future Directions	59
CHAPTER 6 - CONCLUSION.....	60
6.1 Implications	60
6.2 Key Challenges/Gaps Identified.....	60
6.3 Looking Ahead	61
6.4 Final Reflection	61
APPENDIX – A	62
APPENDIX – B	63
APPENDIX - C	63
Literature review Methods and Selection of Relevant Research Papers	63
Web of Science.....	63

Google Scholar	65
Global Standards/Frameworks and Related references	66
Selection of most relevant documents	67
APPENDIX – D	72
Additional Details for Section 2.2	72
Categories of Bias as defined by NIST Special Publication 1270	72
Synthesis of Bias Categories, types, source and root cause	73
Additional Details for Section 2.3	76
AI governance as part of corporate governance	76
AI RMF depicting Governance to be a cross-cutting function	76
Additional Details for Section 2.4	77
APPENDIX - E	79
APPENDIX – F	80
Preliminary Case Study	80
Information Supported Decision/Short Stay VISA process of Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs	80
APPENDIX – G	87
Case Study, AI Implementation at Achmea	87
Acknowledgement	87
Introduction: Background purpose and Context of the Case Study	87
2.1 Objective	87
2.2 Research Approach	88
AI System Under Study - MASHA	89
MASHA (Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm)– AI Governance in Medical Acceptance for Insurance	89
3.1 Overview of MASHA	89
3.2 Key Features & Ethical Safeguards	90
AI Governance Implementation at Achmea	91
4.1 Key AI Principles Adapted by Achmea	92
4.2 Accountability & Oversight Measures	92
4.3 AI Governance Structures	93
4.4 Policy-Driven AI Governance Processes	94
4.5 Current Governance challenges and further need of improvement:	97
Data Governance practice at Achmea ensures AI ready data	97
5.1 Understanding “Daily Close Principles”	98
5.2 Key Aspects of Growing in Data Maturity	99
Aligning literature review results with governance practices at Achmea	100
6.1 Role of Governance from Literature review	100
6.2 Mapping insights from literature review with Operational practices at Achmea	101
6.3 AI Bias related Risks in MASHA and related mitigation mechanisms	103
Mapping Achmea’s AI governance practices to Trias Politica Conceptual model	104
Alignment with EU AI Act	106
Conclusion	107
9.1 Summary of Findings	107
9.2 Final Reflection	109
Reference Documents:	109
APPENDIX – H	110

APPENDIX – I	112
Trias AI Politica Conceptual Model for Bias-Resilient AI Governance	112
APPENDIX – J	118
Abbreviations.....	118
APPENDIX – K	120
First Expert Validation Session Report	120
APPENDIX – L	127
Focus Group Report.....	127
APPENDIX – M	141
Final Expert Validation Report.....	141
Works Cited.....	154

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Executive Summary

This study is based on a research proposal to use the idea behind the Trias Politica to govern AI systems in a business context (van Gils & Mulder, 2023). Inspired by this concept, the research investigates how a separation-of-powers model can provide checks and balances in AI implementations to mitigate bias-related risks and enhance accountability.

The study is based on three primary data sources: (1) a structured literature review, (2) a case study of Achmea's MASHA AI system, and (3) insights from expert workshops and focus groups. Through a deductive thematic analysis, the research identifies six key factors and their subcomponents essential for a Trias Politica-inspired governance model for overseeing AI. These include ethical AI principles, a separation-of-powers structure, lifecycle management through policy, procedural and technical measures, stakeholder inclusion, and alignment with regulatory frameworks such as the EU AI Act.

An expert validation panel confirmed the relevance and overall completeness of the proposed factors, while offering suggestions for refinement. The findings suggest that while AI bias cannot be fully eliminated, it can be effectively managed through structured, transparent, and accountable governance practices.

This research offers a practical foundation for developing AI governance artefacts grounded in democratic principles. A Trias Politica-inspired model presents a viable pathway for organizations to build fair, trustworthy and regulation-ready AI systems.

Keywords: AI Governance, Bias, EU AI Act, Trias Politica, Accountability, Ethical AI

Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT FOR THIS RESEARCH

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity and autonomy (Strycker & Kavlakoglu, 2024). It can work on its own or collaborate with other technologies (e.g., robotics) to perform tasks you would otherwise require human interaction.

Therefore, it is one of the most powerful technologies of our time (Young, 2024, p. 1). AI is often mentioned at the same time as Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL). ML is a subset of AI that involves training machines to learn from historical data. DL is a subfield of ML that uses multilayered neural networks to simulate the complex decision-making power of the human brain function. These two disciplines are closely related to the development of AI algorithms. The modelling of these algorithms includes a decision-making process with human interaction. With this it can learn from available data and make increasingly more accurate predictions over time (Mayank, 2025).

Lastly, Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) relies on DL models that can create original content such as text, images, video, audio or software code in response of a user's prompt or request. (Stryker & Scapicchio, 2024) AI is currently employed across a diverse and expanding array of applications. These potential applications of AI are almost limitless. AI is seen as an important aspect of the digital transformation of society, and it is a priority for the European Union (European Parliament, 2023). As a result, there has been a significant increase in investment and research in this field.

1.1.1 Small overview of AI adoption across different industries

The evolution of AI usages has seen a significant transformation, expanding from theoretical research to practical applications across various domains. AI's history dates to the 1940s with the creation of the electronic digital computer (Iowa State University, 2024).

In a short span of time, computer technology has become an integral part of our everyday lives, making it easy to forget that its development commenced merely eight decades ago. And since the early days, computer scientists have strived to make machines as intelligent as humans (Roser, 2022). The Dartmouth Conference, held in 1956, determined the beginning of AI with the announcement of John McCarthy's concept of using computers to replicate human intelligence (Dartmouth, 2024). The focus of AI research shifted towards ML in the 1980s, leading to more robust and flexible applications. The advent of DL in the 1990s-2010s revolutionised AI applications (Schmidhuber, 2019).

Today, AI powered tools are an integral part of various daily activities in our personal lives. The introduction of the chatbot "ChatGPT" by OpenAI on November 30, 2022 was a major milestone in the advancement of generative AI technology (Chen, Y. et al, 2023).

While the overall adaptation of AI systems has brought enormous potential, it has also brought us major concerns (e.g. Deep Fakes). The following sections make light on various challenges associated with AI adaptation.

1.1.2 The Increasing risk of AI bias and unfair-decision-making

As AI technology advances and brings about remarkable achievements and efficiencies it also brings significant social, economic, and ethical impacts. A global survey on responsible AI highlights that companies' top AI-related concerns include privacy and data governance,

security, reliability, transparency, and fairness. “Extensive analysis of language models suggests that while there is a clear correlation between performance and fairness, fairness and bias can be at odds: Language models which perform better on certain fairness benchmarks tend to have worse gender bias” (Stanford University, 2023, p. 13). The survey shows that “organisations are beginning to take steps to mitigate these risks. However, globally, most companies have so far only mitigated a portion of these risks” (Stanford University, 2024, p. 17). Table 5 at Appendix – A captures major AI related incidents attributed to bias across the globe. “The AI Incident Database, which monitors incidents involving the misuse of AI, reported 123 incidents in 2023. This represents a 32.3% increase compared to 2022” (Stanford University, 2024, p. 18). “According to the “AI, Algorithmic and Automation Incidents and Controversies” (AIAAIC) database, which tracks incidents related to the ethical misuse of AI, the number of AI incidents and controversies has increased twenty-six times since 2012” (Stanford University, 2023, p. 13). An important example includes AI-generated, sexually explicit deepfakes of Taylor Swift widely distributed online (Contreras, 2024). Issues related to bias in AI have been already evident in political context. Researchers found a significant bias in ChatGPT toward Democrats in the United States (US) and the Labour Party in the United Kingdom (UK). (Woollacott, 2023). “This finding raises concerns about the tool’s potential to influence users’ political views, particularly in a year marked by major global elections” (Stanford University, 2024, p. 18).

Growing number of AI related incidents in the past years has drawn significant attention towards responsible development, deployment and operationalise AI systems. The AI community has increasingly focused on evaluating the effects of AI systems and reducing risks for those impacted.

“Over the past year, a substantial debate has emerged among AI scholars and practitioners regarding the focus on immediate model risks, like algorithmic discrimination, versus potential long-term existential threats. It has become challenging to distinguish which claims are scientifically substantiated and which can serve as a basis for policy making. This difficulty is compounded by the tangible nature of short-term risks already present, is in contrast with the theoretical nature of existential threats” (Stanford University, 2024, p. 18).

According to the global state of responsible AI report, 2024 a staggering 45% agreed and 41% strongly agreed (staggering 86% positive) to the fact that “generative AI presents enough of a threat that globally agreed generative AI governance is required” (Stanford University, 2024, p. 190).

1.1.3 The need of a centralised coordination of the global development on AI initiatives

The growing adaptation of AI, its increasing capabilities and associated potential risks have already captured the attention of policy makers throughout the world. There are a substantial amount of AI related policies and governance frameworks are already available (EC/OECD, 2021). Table 6 at Appendix – B, captures few of those available policies and governance frameworks.

Various policymakers, regulators and other governance bodies use guidelines, policies, and frameworks to effectively govern AI systems. The EU constructed in 2018 an AI strategy which evolved into a coordinated plan on AI in 2021 (European Commission, 2021). However, at that time it was still unclear how these governance frameworks and principles should be implemented. Therefore, a centralised coordination is relevant, not only to stay on track of any further AI development in the future, but also to properly balance the impact on the global economy. (Aswani, 2020) Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD)

plays the role of global authority at this stage with their recommendation, the first intergovernmental standard on AI (OECD.AI, 2025).

“The OECD AI Principles promote use of AI that is innovative and trustworthy and that respects human rights and democratic values. Adopted in May 2019, they set standards for AI that are practical and flexible enough to stand the test of time” (OECD.AI, 2025).

With the Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence (GPAI) initiative OECD, the member countries are working together since July 2024 for the advancement of human-centric, safe, secure, and trustworthy AI (OECD.AI, 2025).

1.1.4 The role of Trias Politica principles in an AI governance framework.

Currently, AI tools are widely used in various jurisdictions. They have immense potential but also come with serious risks (Parnas, 2017); (Schneider & Steimers, 2022). Furthermore, the notion of AI Governance (Birkstedt, T. et al, 2023) needs to be understood and leads us straight to other governance disciplines such as IT Governance (De Haes, S. et al, 2020); (Hoogervorst, 2017) and Data Governance (van Gils B. , 2023).

Since the adaptation of OECD AI Principles, OECD launched a framework for the classification of AI systems and created the Working Party on AI Governance (AIGO) to oversee and give direction to the activities of the programme on AI policy and governance. In line with this, the EU published their EU AI Act, which objectively determines what is common when using AI in the EU. In addition, Baron de Montesquieu has coined, the Trias Politica model, also known as separation of powers. Separation of powers is dividing legislative, executive, and judicial functions among separate and independent branches. With this each branch must power to check and balance the others. Available evidence suggests it has recognised as an influential, essential, and adaptive governance framework successfully adopted by various democracies throughout history and still today. It is a system of checks and balances in which each branch has the power to check the others. Therefore, it requires a certain level of expertise to fulfil responsibilities in their specific roles and facilitate cooperation by negotiation and compromise (CIRIS, 2024). Hence, we aim to frame our research question around incorporating the doctrine of the separation of powers, as delineated in the Trias Politica model, into AI governance frameworks, where both human and machine entities collaborate to mitigate bias in AI systems. The adaptability of this principle is important to manage and maintain good governance, and to ensure AI systems are fair, accountable, and reliable.

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

A lack of standardised approach currently posing limitations in adequately addressing the evolving landscape of AI technology and governance needs. Therefore, Governments and International Forums have a duty to develop guidelines, principles, and frameworks to govern AI systems effectively. Hence the problem statement for the research is:

- *Organisations are struggling to address incidents of AI misuse, including issues of bias and fairness, which are obstructing broader adoption efforts.*
- *The lack of a standardised approach in existing AI governance frameworks hinders their effectiveness in addressing the evolving landscape of AI technology, particularly in addressing bias.*

1.2.1 Assumptions/Hypothesis

As illustrated in the table 5 at Appendix – A are associated with bias related issues. According to OECD AI Incident Monitor (AIM), there are a total of 333 bias related incidents reported since 2018 and out of that 94 incidents are reported in 2024 itself (OECD, 2025). Think of the incident in the Netherlands, where Dutch families were wrongly accused of tax fraud by discriminatory algorithm. This scandal is an example of how devastating an automated AI system can be without the proper safeguards. In particular, it was emphasised that decisions should always be processed by a human afterwards. This event has shown exactly what every government should be afraid of (Heikkila, 2022). In line with this, the frequency of AI project failures is increasing due to biases resulting from:

- *Absence of established governance mechanisms (such as structural, technical, or procedural mechanisms)*
- *Absence of standardised governance guidelines (lack of established AI frameworks)*
- *Inadequate governance practices (e.g., insufficient separation of duties or powers between humans and machines)*

There could be many other aspects to the AI failures, but our focuses and subsequent research is based on the above assumptions. Nevertheless, at this moment the pathway for this research topic was still in development.

1.2.2 Validation of Assumption by gathering Expert’s insights

To validate our initial assumptions and refine our research question, we conducted an expert session inspired by the AI-based New Visa Information System (NVIS) used by the Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs. This system, developed to support short-stay visa applications, had come under review due to concerns about potential bias. The expert session took place on 12 September 2024 and included a structured discussion based on insights from our initial literature review and the NVIS case. The session followed a list of key propositions described in Appendix – K and designed to test the validity of our assumptions at Section 1.2.1.

Key outcomes from the session include:

- **Proposition 3:** “Current AI governance practices are insufficient” received an average score of **3.1/4**, confirming that most organizations lack effective governance frameworks.
- **Proposition 10:** “Existing governance frameworks are inadequate for addressing AI bias” scored **3.7/4**, highlighting the need for more comprehensive, multi-disciplinary approaches across legal, IT, operational, and risk domains.
- **Proposition 11:** “Lack of a standardised AI governance approach contributes to AI bias” scored **3.9/4**, strongly reinforcing our hypothesis.

Several other propositions (4, 5, and 8) showed a positive response toward the feasibility of using a *Trias Politica-based governance model*. Experts agreed that the model has potential, but there are still challenges especially in setting clear limits for acceptable bias and deciding how it should be enforced.

The discussion also highlighted a key governance dilemma: while legal and judicial perspectives are essential, direct enforcement by a judicial branch within or outside the organization may not be ideal. Instead, judicial input should inform AI design and decision-making processes, much like it does in cybersecurity. Further support came from positive responses to propositions 6, 7, and 9, which helped us narrow the research scope to focus on “*High-Risk AI Systems*”, especially in alignment with the *EU AI Act*.

The expert session confirmed our assumptions about gaps in current AI governance and provided strong support for exploring a Trias Politica-inspired framework. It also helped us refine and finalize our research question by confirming the practical relevance and urgency of bias mitigation especially in high-risk AI systems.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTION

Given the fragmented state of AI governance and growing incidents of bias-related failures, there is a clear need for a structured and principled framework to guide organisations in addressing these risks. This study explores how the separation of powers *principles of Trias Politica* and institutional checks and balances can support the design of such a governance model, especially within the evolving regulatory landscape shaped by the *EU AI Act*.

The initial assumptions behind this study were tested and validated through an expert session involving AI professionals, governance experts, and practitioners familiar with high-risk AI systems. The findings as specified in section 1.2.1 provided critical input for shaping the final research direction and narrowing the scope. Based on this validation, the Research Question (RQ) is formulated as:

“Which factors are relevant for designing a governance framework such that we apply the principles of the Trias Politica in order to mitigate bias-related risks when adopting AI in organisations within the context of the EU AI Act?”

This question reflects both the theoretical focus on governance principles and the practical urgency highlighted by expert feedback, particularly in relation to high-risk AI applications.

The goal of this research is to explore and identify the key components of an effective AI governance framework grounded in the *Trias Politica* model, in response to the current lack of a standardised approach in existing AI governance practices. By investigating how a system of checks and balances can be embedded within organisational structures, the study aims to find out key relevant factors for developing a resilient governance framework capable of mitigating bias-related risks across the entire AI lifecycle from development to operation guided by the compliance requirements from the *EU AI Act*.

1.3.1 Problem decomposition

Following our research methodology, which is based on a hybrid approach combining aggregative and interrogative approach we have broken down the main Research Question (RQ) into more specific and manageable parts. This helped us structure the study around key themes and focus areas.

We identified three core dimensions of the RQ:

1. *Mitigation of AI bias-related risks* and the identification of relevant factors for designing a governance framework.
2. *Application of Trias Politica principles* specifically the separation of powers in the governance of AI systems.
3. *Regulatory context of the EU AI Act*, focusing on its governance-related provisions for managing bias.

Based on the identified core dimensions, we decomposed our RQ as following Research Sub Questions (RSQ).

1. **RSQ1:** How do diverse types of biases arise in AI systems, and what relevant factors should be incorporated into an AI governance framework to effectively mitigate them?
2. **RSQ2:** How can the principle of separation of powers in Trias Politica be integrated into such a governance framework for organisational AI implementation?
3. **RSQ3:** What are the key provisions of the EU AI Act aimed at addressing bias in AI systems?

These sub-questions support a deeper understanding of the RQ by addressing theoretical, practical, and regulatory aspects of AI governance. The results aim to identify essential factors for mitigating AI bias and to inform the design of governance artefacts that can be reused or adapted across different industries. These insights contribute to both academic discussions and real-world applications, supporting the development of fair and accountable AI systems.

Chapter 2 – Literature Review

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review serves as a foundational component of our research aiming to explore the academic, regulatory and empirical insights around AI bias and governance, particularly in relation to the recently published EU AI Act. The review is designed to offer conceptual clarity, synthesise best practices, and critically evaluate how democratic governance principles like the *Trias Politica* can be operationalised to mitigate bias related risks in organisational implementation of AI systems.

2.1.1 Purpose and scope of literature review

The primary purpose of this literature review is to establish a rigorous, conceptual understanding of the relationship between bias in AI systems and the governance mechanisms needed to manage such risks. Specifically, it offers:

1. A structured investigation into various bias types, sources, and implications.
2. A synthesis of legal and ethical frameworks, including the EU AI Act.
3. Guidance on principles, and mechanisms that can ensure bias-resilient governance.

These insights will help identify the relevant factors in designing a governance framework that operates effectively across both the build and use phases of AI, ensuring the mitigation of bias.

2.1.2 Alignment with the Research Question and Research Sub-Questions

In aligning with the research approach, two key sub questions RSQ1 and RSQ3 guide this literature review. While RSQ1 serves as the analytical foundation, focusing on understanding the sources of bias in AI and identifies key factors that a governance framework must integrate to effectively mitigate these risks, RSQ3 complements this by critically examining how evolving legal framework of the EU AI Act seeks to regulate and mitigate such risks. Together, these questions guide the selection and interrogation of relevant literature.

2.1.3 AI Definition and Lifecycle of AI in context of this Research

Given the focus on AI, it is crucial to define the term within the context of this research to ensure clarity and consistency throughout the study. Since the problem statement revolves around bias-related issues, examining the lifecycle of an AI system is essential for understanding the manifestation, implications, and mitigation of bias. Following the guidance of one of our promoters, Prof. Yuri Bobbert from AMS, we explored the OECD definition of AI and explored its associated lifecycle to provide a comprehensive framework for analysis.

According to OECD “An AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment (Perset, K. et al, 2024, p. 4) .

The OECD definition further simplifies the concept of AI by categorizing the AI lifecycle into two broad phases: the build phase and the use phase. This classification provides a streamlined

framework to understand the development and deployment of AI systems, which is particularly relevant for analysing bias-related issues across these stages.

Figure 1: Simplified overview of an AI system as defined by OECD (Perset, K. et al, 2024, p. 7).

Figure 1 presents only one possible relationship between the development and deployment phases. In many cases, the design and training of the system may continue in downstream uses. For example, deployers of AI systems may fine-tune or continuously train models during operation, which can significantly impact the system's performance and behaviour (Perset, K. et al, 2024, p. 7). We compared this with the EU AI Act definition of AI systems to validate if there any noticeable deviation. As per the EU AI Act, *'AI system' means a machine-based system that is designed to operate with varying levels of autonomy and that may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment, and that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments* (EU, 2024).

We observed that in both the cases the definition of AI is identical, with minimal noticeable differences. Given that this research is conducted within the context of the EU AI Act, we have adopted its definition of AI. However, because the OECD offers a more structured approach for distinguishing the different phases of AI implementation, we have decided to use the OECD lifecycle definition for the continuation of our research and literature review.

Building on this framework, our literature review is structured to explicitly address the lifecycle aspects of AI systems, focusing on the build phase and use phase. This approach ensures a comprehensive analysis of bias-related issues, examining their manifestation, implications, and potential mitigation strategies within each phase of the AI lifecycle. Hence, the subsequent sections explore into the roots and typologies of bias and then link them to governance solutions.

2.2 UNDERSTANDING BIAS IN AI SYSTEMS IMPLICATIONS AND RISKS

This section focuses on understanding AI bias by examining its different types, how it emerges across various stages of the AI lifecycle, and how it can be classified. It also discusses the potential risks bias presents to individuals and organisations. This analysis directly supports Research RSQ1, which investigates the nature of AI bias and the risks it creates. These insights provide a foundation for the next section, which explores mechanisms for mitigating bias and the role of governance in that process.

2.2.1 Definitions, Classification, and Sources of Bias in AI

Bias in AI refers to systematic errors that result in unfair or inaccurate outcomes, especially when such outcomes affect certain individuals or groups disproportionately (Schwartz, R. et al , 2022). The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), drawing from the OECD glossary, describes bias as a distortion that undermines the representativeness of data and model outputs (NIST, 2023). In AI, this can lead to decisions that are discriminatory or socially unacceptable, eroding trust in automated systems.

NIST identifies three primary categories of bias:

1. **Systemic Bias** – Stemming from broader societal and institutional inequalities.
2. **Statistical/Computational Bias** – Resulting from flawed data or model design.
3. **Human Bias** – Introduced through subjective decisions made by developers, users, or annotators (Schwartz, R. et al , 2022, p. 8).

Appendix – D: Categories of Bias as defined by NIST Special Publication 1270 shows a visual taxonomy of AI bias.

Ferrara, E., recommends in his article (Ferrara, 2024) to expand this taxonomy and to include data, algorithmic, user, generative, and measurement biases. These emerge during both the build phase (e.g., data collection, model training) and the use phase (e.g., deployment and user feedback). For example, sampling bias happens when some groups are left out of the data. This can lead to stereotypes in AI-generated content or mistakes in facial recognition.

In the context of GenAI, the publication NIST AI 600-1 (NIST, 2024) highlights new bias-related challenges such as:

- **Harmful Bias:** Reflecting societal inequities in training data.
- **Algorithmic Monoculture:** Where reliance on a few dominant models spreads bias across systems.
- **Confabulation:** The generation of outputs that appear accurate but are factually incorrect posing significant risks in areas like healthcare.

It describes the fact that label, sampling, and societal biases often arise from systemic inequalities, particularly in sensitive areas such as hiring or health. In the article, “How to be fair?” (Favier, M. et al, 2023), the focus is on label and selection bias, showing how flawed labels (e.g., using healthcare cost as a proxy for health) and non-diverse samples can reinforce discrimination. The Dutch childcare benefits scandal is a recent example, where algorithms disproportionately flagged non-native residents as fraudulent.

Chiappetta, A., (Chiappetta, 2023) notes that many AI biases especially data and algorithmic originate in the design stage but continue into deployment. UNESCO’s Global Toolkit on AI and the Rule of Law underscores how these biases, as seen in cases like COMPAS in the U.S. criminal justice system, can lead to systemic discrimination (Stankovich, M. et al , 2023) .

By synthesizing these findings, this research adopts the following working definition:

“Bias in AI systems refers to any systematic difference, error, deviation, or inconsistency in decision-making that leads to unfair or inaccurate outcomes disproportionately impacting particular individuals, groups, or contexts.”

Bias typically arises during two core stages:

- **Build Phase:** Data collection, labelling, and model training.
- **Use Phase:** Real-world deployment, user interaction, and feedback loops.

Root causes include skewed data, flawed design decisions, and over-reliance on automated outputs. Addressing these requires a mix of technical solutions (e.g., fairness metrics, data balancing), procedural checks (e.g., audits, impact assessments), and ethical governance (Ferrara, 2024); (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023).Appendix – D

Additional Details for Section 2.2Appendix D: Table 8: Bias Classification that provides a comprehensive list of bias categories, descriptions, life cycle stage of occurrence, source and root cause.

2.2.2 Critical Implications: Trust, Fairness, and Organisational Risk

Bias in AI not only affects system performance but also undermines public trust, fairness in decision-making, and organisational credibility.

Trust: Transparency, Accountability, and Public Confidence

Trust in AI systems depends on how open, clear, and responsible they are. The *AI Governance White Paper* says that people must be able to question decisions made by AI, especially in important areas like law or healthcare. It also says that companies need clear rules on who is responsible for those decisions (Australian Government, 2024).

The *NIST AI Risk Management Framework (NIST AI RMF)* adds that AI should be easy to understand and explain. These features help people trust the results and spot mistakes (NIST, 2023).

Trust can be harmed by feedback loops. This happens when AI predictions affect future data, which then makes the same bias worse. The *EU Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA)* warns this can lead to “runaway” effects (EU FRA, 2022). A real-life example is the Dutch childcare scandal, already discussed in section 1.2.2.

Fairness: Structural Bias and Data Imbalance

AI is unfair when its training data reflects past discrimination or bias. For example, label bias happens when the labels used in training do not match real-world outcomes. In U.S. healthcare, Black patients were given lower risk scores than white patients, even though they were sicker (Favier, M. et al, 2023). Selection bias happens when some groups are left out of the training data. This was also seen in the Dutch scandal, where non-Dutch residents were unfairly targeted.

Although tools exist to improve fairness, they don't always work as expected. (Favier, M. et al, 2023) explain that it's not always clear which tool to use, or whether these tools improve fairness in practice. Bias can also affect language models. The FRA found that some hate speech detectors wrongly flag harmless phrases like "I am Jewish," while missing actual harmful content (EU FRA, 2022).

UNESCO 's Recommendation on the Ethics of AI (UNESCO, 2023) warns that bias can lead to serious problems like discrimination, exclusion, and threats to cultural diversity. These risks show that AI rules must be based on human rights, not just technical fixes.

Another important factor is drift risk that can affect how AI systems behave over time and can lead to new or increased bias. The NIST AI RMF explains three types of drift. *Data drift* happens when the input data changes, which can cause the model to become less accurate and make unfair decisions. *Concept drift* occurs when the relationship between input and output changes, so the model may no longer reflect real-world conditions. *Model drift* is when the AI system's performance gets worse over time, even if the data stays the same (NIST, 2023) . These types of drift can cause AI systems to treat certain groups unfairly, especially if the changes affect some people more than others.

To reduce these risks and avoid biased outcomes, NIST recommends regularly monitoring AI systems. It also suggests setting up risk controls that focus on data quality, privacy, and trust. These steps help organisations make sure their AI systems stay fair and reliable over time (NIST, 2023).

Organisational Risk: Legal, Strategic, and Reputational Exposure

Organisations using AI must follow legal and ethical rules. According to the *AI Governance White Paper*, company leaders can be held responsible for the results of AI even if a machine made the decision (Australian Government, 2024). This is especially important in areas like hiring, finance, and public services, where unfair outcomes can break the law.

Generative AI brings extra risks. Companies must make sure their data use follows privacy, copyright, and consent rules. Breaking these laws can lead to penalties and damage public trust.

The *Hiroshima AI Policy Recommendations* point out other risks like lack of transparency, biased results, and wrong answers caused by poor training (The University of Tokyo, 2023). It also highlights that with international systems, it's often unclear who is responsible when things go wrong. The *NIST AI RMF* agrees that AI is complex, and without strong rules, mistakes are hard to detect and fix (NIST, 2023).

In Europe, the new *EU AI Act* lists certain systems as "high-risk." These must meet strict rules, including clear documentation, human checks, and bias prevention (EU, 2024). If organisations don't follow the rules, they may face fines, loss of reputation, or even be banned from operating in the EU.

Reviewed literature consistently shows that bias in AI not only jeopardises fairness but also degrades public trust and exposes organisations to serious legal, strategic, and reputational vulnerabilities. To safeguard trust, AI systems must be transparent, explainable, and accountable, allowing those affected to challenge potentially harmful outcomes. Robust governance drawing on technical standards like those from NIST and on emerging regulatory

frameworks such as the forthcoming EU AI Act becomes indispensable for preventing discriminatory practices, blocking self-reinforcing bias loops, and sustaining public confidence. Building on these concerns, the following chapter looks into *AI governance* as a core mechanism for bias mitigation (RSQ1), demonstrating how structured oversight and regulatory alignment can systematically address the risks posed by biased AI.

2.3 MECHANISMS FOR AI BIAS MITIGATION AND THE CENTRAL ROLE OF GOVERNANCE

In this section, we first explore the main concepts and mechanisms related to bias mitigation and how governance plays a role in the entire process. Each subsection provides a brief conclusion to the findings in the literature aligning to RSQ1.

2.3.1 Strategies for Mitigating AI Bias Through Governance

Reducing bias in AI is critical to achieving fairness, accuracy, and public trust. Multiple studies emphasise that no single method can solve the problem of bias. Effective mitigation requires a combination of technical tools, process improvements, and policy measures. These strategies must be integrated into a strong governance framework that supports ethical and inclusive AI throughout its entire lifecycle (UNESCO, 2023); (NIST, 2023).

AI bias stems from a range of interrelated sources. Data-related biases are among the most common, often caused by sampling imbalances or the underrepresentation of minority groups, which can result in skewed outputs and unfair decisions. Algorithmic bias arises from biased training objectives or loss functions that unintentionally favour certain populations during model optimisation. Societal and cultural influences can also be encoded in training data, especially in generative AI models trained on large datasets scraped from the web. As Ferrara, mentions, these datasets often reflect social stereotypes, which become embedded in AI outputs (Ferrara, 2024). Additionally, feedback bias is a growing concern. This occurs when AI systems learn from user interactions over time, reinforcing existing patterns and creating self-perpetuating cycles of bias, particularly in generative or recommendation-based AI applications.

To effectively mitigate these layered issues, a lifecycle-based approach is necessary. An approach that addresses bias at every stage, from data collection and model development to deployment and monitoring. This approach advocates for continuous fairness-aware design, regular auditing, and transparency in AI decisions to avoid reinforcing structural inequalities.

Global frameworks have responded to these challenges. The UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI (UNESCO, 2023) outlines key policy tools including ethical impact assessments, fairness and non-discrimination principles, stakeholder engagement, and strong data governance. These actions aim to ensure high-quality, inclusive datasets and create transparency and accountability in algorithmic systems.

The Missing Links in AI Governance report by UNESCO and Mila (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023) expands this by recommending third-party audits, public disclosures, fairness measurement standards, and incident reporting to detect and address hidden or systemic biases. These tools promote accountability and empower communities to scrutinise AI deployments.

In the legal domain, the Global Toolkit on AI and the Rule of Law for the Judiciary (Stankovich, M. et al, 2023) focuses on fairness, transparency, and human rights. It encourages clear rules for data accuracy and algorithmic accountability while building capacity among judges and legal professionals to detect and challenge AI bias.

The NIST AI RMF (NIST, 2023) adds a detailed structure for managing bias through policy, technical, and process-based interventions. It includes explainability tools, risk mapping, privacy safeguards, and mechanisms for ongoing feedback and documentation (NIST, 2023) . A more recent update, the NIST Generative AI Profile (NIST, 2024), addresses unique risks in generative AI. It recommends transparency in training data sources, ethical use guidelines to prevent harmful content, and advanced tools like counterfactual analysis to detect hidden biases (Autio & Stanley, 2024).

NIST Special Publication 1270 further emphasises a socio-technical governance model, targeting bias across datasets, algorithms, and human decision-making. It promotes formal governance standards, inclusive stakeholder participation, and human-centred system design (NIST, 2022).

On the technical side, the OECD has developed an unsupervised bias detection tool that identifies subtle or intersectional biases through clustering techniques. This method helps detect discrimination even among groups not traditionally defined by protected attributes. Importantly, this process is followed by expert review to evaluate the social and legal relevance of the findings, enhancing transparency and stakeholder engagement (OECD, 2023).

Finally, the European Parliament’s Artificial Intelligence in a Digital Age Committee and the EU AI Act echo these principles, focusing on transparency, risk assessments, and regulatory oversight. These efforts are particularly aimed at public sector applications of AI, where biased outcomes can significantly harm marginalised populations (Chiappetta, 2023).

Despite the growing ecosystem of bias mitigation techniques, there is no consensus on which metrics are most appropriate for evaluating fairness across different contexts. As (Favier, M. et al, 2023) argue, “it is still poorly understood what the exact effects of different fairness interventions are and in which situations they should be applied.” Similarly, NIST AI RMF mentions that organisations often struggle to select and apply technical tools consistently, leading to fragmented or ineffective bias mitigation (NIST, 2023).

The review consistently indicates that AI bias stems from a complex mix of data limitations, algorithmic design choices, embedded cultural norms, and self-reinforcing feedback loops. Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive strategy that combines technical solutions, inclusive policy design, and continuous oversight. As observed, mitigating bias is not solely a technical task but it also depends on effective governance. Structured oversight, ethical principles, and participatory decision-making are essential to ensuring that AI systems are fair, transparent, and accountable. This leads us to an examination of AI governance, its foundations, values, and the rationale behind regulatory efforts shaping the responsible use of AI technologies.

2.3.2 Foundations and Structures of AI Governance: Building Responsible AI Systems

Effective governance of AI is essential for developing, deploying, and using AI technologies responsibly adhering to safety and ethical norms while complying with regulatory standards

(Australian Government, 2024). The Governance Institute of Australia stresses that operationalising accountability within AI systems requires three core pillars:

- **Responsibility:** Who is accountable and to whom?
- **Auditability:** What is one accountable for?
- **Redressability:** How do entities remain accountable, and how do they rectify issues?

These pillars highlight the multifaceted nature of oversight, spanning organisational culture, technical documentation, and legal responsibilities (Australian Government, 2024).

According to the paper “Defining organisational AI governance,” AI governance is “a system of rules, practices, processes, and technological tools that are employed to ensure an organisation’s use of AI technologies aligns with the organisation’s strategies, objectives, and values; fulfils legal requirements; and meets principles of ethical AI followed by the organisation.” (Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022).

This definition situates AI governance within overarching corporate governance, reflecting the idea that AI-centric policies must align with established organisational strategies and frameworks. Notably, “AI governance” is the appropriate term for describing these responsibilities (Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022) AI governance is viewed as a subset of corporate governance and IT governance, with a partial overlap in data governance as depicted in Figure 11 at Appendix – D.

- **Corporate Governance** provides the broader governance structure.
- **IT Governance** offers specific mechanisms relevant to AI as an IT-based system.
- **Data Governance** intersects with AI governance when managing data inputs and outputs, even if algorithms themselves may not strictly fall under data governance (Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022).

AI governance does not function in isolation. It is interwoven into the organisation’s overall governance ecosystem, thereby fostering consistency in policy enforcement and accountability structures (Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022). The study “Toward AI Governance: Identifying Best Practices and Potential Barriers and Outcomes” emphasise the critical role of embedding AI governance within the broader corporate framework. For example, they note that “Firms need to introduce robust AI systems and mitigate AI risks, which emphasises the importance of creating suitable AI governance practices” (Papagiannidis, E. et al, 2022). The authors also referenced prior work stating that AI involves sophisticated forms of analytics and automated decision-making, it requires new roles and responsibilities but also leading to new risks. Governance should therefore not be limited to the content, but should also include its analysis, as AI should be considering a dynamic frontier of computing (Berente, 2021). This insight underscores the view that AI impacts various aspects of the business hence governance should not be an isolated function but rather integrated into existing corporate strategies.

In contrast, the paper “AI governance: a systematic literature review” identifies a major gap in their research as they discovered that only three studies comprehensively address the who, what, when, and how of governance (Batoool, A. et al , 2025). While many frameworks emphasise risk management within organisations, insufficient stakeholder engagement persists across AI development stages, and ethical principles lack thorough implementation guidelines. This underscores the need for holistic, ethically grounded approaches that move beyond mere risk

mitigation to encompass broader social and organisational responsibilities (Batool, A. et al , 2025).

Policy recommendations from the Hiroshima AI Process indicate that in practical organisational contexts, integrating AI governance practices into current corporate governance frameworks may be more efficient than crafting separate, stand-alone rules (The University of Tokyo, 2023).

Various literature suggests AI governance is essential for mitigating bias, and it should be embedded into company policies, risk systems, and values. It should not be a separate process but a key part of how organisations manage AI safely and ethically.

2.3.3 Ethical Principles as Pillars of Bias-Resilient AI

To build fair and trustworthy AI, global organisations like UNESCO and the OECD have created guidelines that highlight the importance of values such as fairness, transparency, and accountability (UNESCO, 2023); (OECD, 2022).

UNESCO's *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence* outlines ten core principles for ethical AI. A closer look at these shows that seven directly help reduce bias by focusing on fairness, human oversight, and making AI decisions understandable and accountable. The other three principles are also helpful in indirectly addressing bias by encouraging public awareness or supporting sustainability (UNESCO, 2023) and visible in Appendix H - Table 15: UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI. AI principles (UNESCO, 2023).

The OECD's *Principles on AI* also support reducing bias. Out of five main principles, four are highly relevant to fairness and inclusion. These focus on human rights, transparency, and responsible use of AI throughout its development and use. The fifth principle, on safety and reliability, is still useful but only partly related to bias issues (OECD, 2022) and visible in Appendix H - Table 16: OECD principles of trustworthy AI and their relevance to bias related to issues (OECD, 2022).

Overall, the study shows that ethical principles play a big role in making AI systems fairer and more responsible. Importantly, no principle from either organisation was found to be irrelevant to bias concerns. These findings highlight the role of AI principles in AI governance to reduce risks and build fairer systems.

2.3.4 Governance as a Core Function in AI Risk and Bias Management

As highlighted in the preceding sections, bias in AI has become a significant organisational risk manifesting in numerous forms. Accordingly, it is crucial for organisations to recognise and mitigate AI-related risks including bias by integrating these practices into their overarching corporate risk management frameworks. The NIST AI RMF offers a structured methodology for handling AI-related risks, emphasizing that AI should be integrated within broader corporate risk strategies rather than treated in isolation (NIST, 2023). Central to this framework are four core functions Govern, Map, Measure, and Manage, which collectively address the unique challenges AI systems pose, including bias, privacy, and security. Figure 12 depicts this at Appendix – D.

Within this model, “Govern” is explicitly characterised as a “cross-cutting function,” meaning it underpins every phase of AI risk management. Achieving effective governance requires

“organisational commitment at senior levels,” ensuring that AI-related decisions conform to enterprise-wide policies and values (NIST, 2023).

This holistic stance becomes crucial in addressing systemic issues like bias, which can originate in data or model design and carry over into deployment.

Both NIST.AI.100-1 (AI RMF) and the companion NIST AI 600-1: GenAI Profile underscore the need to tackle bias throughout the AI lifecycle, noting that AI “can increase the speed and scale at which harmful biases manifest,” potentially affecting “individuals, groups, communities, organisations, and society” (NIST, 2024) . Governance mechanisms help organisations identify, measure, and address these bias-related concerns by “establishing and maintaining the appropriate accountability mechanisms, roles and responsibilities, culture, and incentive structures for risk management to be effective” (NIST, 2023).

In practical terms, this involves integrating bias detection and remediation measures into existing corporate governance. For instance, the AI RMF advises diverse teams and transparent processes, enabling early identification of discriminatory decision-making or the “amplification of existing societal biases,” which can then be mitigated through corporate policies, technical audits, and structured reporting (NIST, 2023); (NIST, 2024). Embedding these measures under the Govern function supported by Map, Measure, and Manage ensures that organisations bolster ethical standards and accountability while continuously tackling bias throughout development and deployment.

Ultimately, the AI RMF underscores *governance* as the backbone for responsible AI, cautioning that risk management “should not be considered in isolation.” Instead, governance must be woven into enterprise-wide strategies so that bias mitigation remains a central priority across the entire AI lifecycle (NIST, 2023).

Literature from various studies pointed that by embedding governance into every part of the AI lifecycle, companies can reduce the chance of bias and build ethical, fair, and trustworthy AI. Building on the role of governance in managing AI bias and broader risks, the next chapter explores how these principles are being translated into formal regulations particularly focusing on the EU AI Act as a key example of a structured legal approach to bias mitigation.

Appendix - E provides a synthesis of applicable governance controls to mitigate bias related risks in AI systems.

2.4 REGULATORY APPROACHES TO BIAS: THE EU AI ACT IN FOCUS

This section explores how the EU AI Act addresses bias in AI systems, focusing on the legal provisions, compliance obligations, and governance structures introduced to mitigate discrimination and promote fairness. In doing so, it provides answers to RSQ3 by identifying the key regulatory mechanisms aimed at ensuring bias-resilient AI across the system lifecycle.

High-Level Expert Group on AI (AI HLEG) was established in June 2018 to provide guidance on AI policy and ethics. Their role was to make recommendations by advising on mid-term and long-term challenges of AI implementation, contributing to policy development process and preparing ethic guidelines (Shaping Europe's digital future, 2018).

According to AI HLEG's published "Ethics guidelines to achieve trustworthy AI", trustworthy AI should be *lawful* - respecting all applicable laws and regulations, *ethical* - respecting ethical principles and values and lastly *robust* - both from a technical perspective while considering its social environment. In extension of this a set of "seven" key requirements was defined which should be met to be a trustworthy AI system. (Shaping Europe's digital future, 2019)

Eventually the EU AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence) and at the same time the first-ever comprehensive legal framework on AI worldwide was published and entered into force on 1st August 2024. (Shaping Europe's digital future, 2025)

2.4.1 Scope of the EU AI Act

The EU AI Act provides a comprehensive regulatory direction through the different opportunities and challenges of AI systems. The goals are to improve the European market and to promote a *human-centric* and *trustworthy AI*.

The focus lies on the protection of *health, safety, and fundamental rights*. This includes the protection of democracy and the environment against harmful effects, and the support of innovation. (EU, 2024).

Therefore, the regulation will enforce certain harmonised rules, which will have an impact the AI life cycle and foresees prohibitions of certain AI systems, specific requirements and/or obligations. (EU, 2024) As to our acknowledgement the EU AI Act goes out of a risk-based enforcement and mainly applies to systems classified as high-risk AI system. Before we dive deeper into the risk-based classification and compliancy requirements, we shortly enlist the seven key requirements of AI HLEG which will contribute to the design of a trustworthy AI system because of their alignment with this regulation.

- *Human agency and oversight*: AI systems should enable equitable societies by supporting human agency and fundamental rights, and not decrease, limit or misguide human autonomy.
- *Technical robustness and safety*: Trustworthy AI requires algorithms to be secure, reliable and robust enough to deal with errors or inconsistencies during all life cycle phases of AI systems.
- *Privacy and data governance*: People should have full control over their own data, while data concerning them will not be used to harm or discriminate against them.
- *Transparency*: Traceability of AI systems should be ensured at all times.
- *Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness*: AI systems should consider the whole range of human abilities, skills and requirements, and ensure accessibility.
- *Societal and environmental well-being*: AI systems should be used to enhance positive social change and enhance sustainability and ecological responsibility.
- *Accountability*: Control mechanisms should be put in place to ensure responsibility and accountability for AI systems and their outcomes.

(Shaping Europe's digital future, 2019)

As already mentioned above, the EU AI Act categorises risks associated with AI systems into unacceptable risk, high-risk, limited risk (AI with specific transparency obligation), and minimal-risk categories, with a particular focus on managing biases that impact societal equality and fairness. As a result of the assessment of the level of risk of an AI system, providers and users have to fulfil established obligations. (European Commission Press corner, 2024)

The EU AI Act has not foreseen obligations to *minimal-risk* AI systems (e.g. spam filters). Companies are free to provide a code of conduct to systems that fall under this unregulated category.

Limited risk AI systems (e.g. chatbots) have a transparency obligation and therefore must clearly inform the users when they are interacting with an AI system and mark their outputs if they create content (e.g. deepfakes).

AI systems fall under *high-risk* when they potentially cause risk to health, safety, and fundamental rights. Before they can be put on the market, strict obligations need to be fulfilled.

Unacceptable risk AI systems are the ones with a clear threat to the safety, health and rights of people. They are described as such in the EU AI Act.

More details on these four levels of risk-based classification and compliancy requirements can be found in Table 9: EU AI Act Bias mitigation and Compliance Requirements.

2.4.2 Provisions directly related to diversity, non-discrimination and fairness.

During the development and use phase an AI system should include diverse actors and promote equal access, gender equality and cultural diversity. The best way to do this is to avoid discriminatory impacts and unfair bias.

High-quality datasets is a foundation to ensure high-risk AI systems perform as intended and in a safely way while it avoids becoming a source of discrimination. High-quality data sets for training, validation and testing should be relevant, sufficiently representative, include labels, being free of errors and in line with the purpose of the system. This should not prevent the implementation of privacy-preserving techniques during development and testing. They should also reflect the features, characteristics of elements particularly reflected in the specific geographical, contextual, behavioural or functional environments in which the AI system is intended to be used.

Biases in AI systems often emerge at various stages of their lifecycle. In the development stage, bias can be introduced during the data collection and model training phase. If the data used to train the AI systems is not representative or contains inherent biases, the AI systems may learn and perpetuate these biases. When an AI system is placed on the market, biases can manifest if the AI system has not undergone thorough testing and validation to ensure it performs fairly across different demographic groups. If an AI system is put into service or deployed, biases can become apparent if the system's performance varies significantly in different real-world environments or among different user groups. Biases can continue to manifest during the use of the AI system if it is not regularly monitored and updated to address any emerging issues. This includes biases that may arise from changes in the environment or user behaviour.

To mitigate bias, data sets must have the right statistical properties relative to the target persons or groups of persons of the AI system. Especially to the mitigation of possible biases to the data sets (e.g. feedback loops: data outputs influencing inputs for future operations) that can potentially affect the health and safety of persons, negatively impact fundamental rights or lead to discrimination against vulnerable groups such as racial or ethnic communities.

Therefore, a provider of a high-risk system must establish a robust post-market monitoring system to detect and mitigate biases that may not have been apparent during earlier stages. This involves risk management, regular audits, user feedback, and updates to the AI system to ensure it remains fair and unbiased. Inadequate inclusion of diverse stakeholder perspectives or insufficient ethical considerations can lead to systemic oversights.

Data governance and management practices should be put in place to achieve and maintain high quality data sets for training, validation and testing. To facilitate compliance with the GDPR, it should include transparency about the purpose of the data collection especially when PII is involved. One practical approach is to engage third-party certified compliance services to verify data governance practices, the integrity of data sets, and the overall robustness of the training, validation, and testing process.

Mitigation strategies outlined in the EU AI Act include rigorous data governance standards to ensure datasets are representative and accurate, thereby reducing the prevalence of data bias. Bias detection tools, such as counterfactual analysis and fairness testing, are recommended to identify and address algorithmic bias during system development and validation. Human oversight is required in high-stakes AI applications to minimise the risk of erroneous or discriminatory decisions. Continuous monitoring and adaptive feedback loops are emphasised as critical post-deployment practices. Governance structures are central to implementing these strategies, ensuring that bias mitigation measures are systematically applied and enforced.

Technical robustness to withstand errors, faults, inconsistencies and unexpected situations, is a key requirement for high-risk AI systems. This means that features such as mechanisms enabling the system to safely interrupt or remedy its operation when anomalous behaviour is detected. These measures ensure the AI system does not continue to operate in a potential harmful or biased manner.

Training datasets, which are often incomplete or unrepresentative, contribute to data bias that propagates through model training. Testing and deployment stages may fail to detect or mitigate these biases due to insufficient validation. Post-deployment monitoring is essential to identify and rectify bias-related risks as they evolve over time. The EU AI Act emphasises the need for lifecycle-wide vigilance to address these risks comprehensively. It identifies multiple sources and causes of bias. Data bias stems from unbalanced or skewed datasets that reflect historical inequities or inadequacies in data collection processes. Algorithmic bias arises from design choices or objectives that inadvertently prioritise efficiency over fairness. Societal bias, reflecting systemic inequities, is embedded in societal norms, institutional practices, and regulations. The EU AI Act addresses these root causes through risk assessments, diverse stakeholder inclusion, and robust governance frameworks.

The EU AI Act suggests a governance framework to mitigate bias in AI systems. Key controls include transparency and accountability requirements, where providers must disclose **technical documentation and risk management practices**. Regulatory oversight by national authorities and the European Artificial Intelligence Board ensures compliance with fairness and anti-bias standards. Ethical standards, such as fairness and non-discrimination, are mandated as foundational principles for AI systems. Incident reporting mechanisms further enhance the Act's governance structure, facilitating proactive identification and resolution of bias-related risks (EU, 2024).

2.4.3 Key Findings

While the EU AI Act represents a significant milestone in establishing a comprehensive Act for implementing AI systems, certain gaps limit its effectiveness in fully mitigating bias-related risks. One significant gap is the Act's reliance on predefined high-risk categories, which may overlook emerging AI applications with potential for discriminatory outcomes. This rigid classification might fail to adapt quickly to evolving technologies and contexts. Additionally,

while the Act emphasises transparency and accountability, it provides limited guidance on the practical implementation of fairness metrics or on standardising bias detection and mitigation techniques across diverse AI systems.

The EU AI Act's approach to lifecycle governance, though robust, could be enhanced by incorporating stronger post-deployment monitoring mechanisms and adaptive governance models that respond to real-world outcomes. Another area for improvement lies in the inclusion of marginalised voices; while stakeholder engagement is emphasised, the lack of specific mandates for involving underrepresented groups during the design and testing phases leaves a critical gap in addressing societal bias.

To strengthen its provisions, the EU AI Act could integrate dynamic risk assessment methodologies to identify and classify emerging risks proactively. Additionally, the development of standardised fairness and bias mitigation tools, combined with clear implementation guidelines, would provide stakeholders with actionable measures to address bias effectively. Enhanced post-deployment monitoring frameworks, with mechanisms for real-time feedback and accountability, would further ensure that AI systems adapt to mitigate evolving biases.

Finally, fostering international collaboration to harmonise bias-related standards and best practices would enhance the Act's global relevance and impact.

By addressing these gaps and adopting these improvements, the EU AI Act can evolve into a more adaptive and equitable framework for governing AI systems, ensuring that they align with societal values while safeguarding against discriminatory outcomes (EU, 2024).

2.5 SYNTHESIS OF REVIEWED LITERATURE

This section synthesizes the critical insights from the literature review, encompassing the nature of AI bias, effective governance mechanisms, ethical principles, regulatory frameworks, and the challenges encountered in implementing bias mitigation strategies. The synthesis is structured to address the RSQ1 and RSQ3 and the RQ.

2.5.1 Understanding AI Bias Across the Lifecycle

AI bias is a multifaceted issue that emerges throughout the AI lifecycle, from data collection and model development to deployment and user interaction. Key categories of biases identified include:

- **Data-Related Biases:** Such as sampling bias, where datasets do not adequately represent the target population, and historical bias, reflecting entrenched inequalities in legacy data.
- **Model-Design and Algorithmic Biases:** Including feature selection bias, where certain features inadvertently act as proxies for protected attributes, and optimization bias, where models prioritize accuracy over equity considerations.
- **Societal and Cultural Biases:** Embedded in training data due to ingrained stereotypes or systemic inequities, which can be perpetuated by AI systems.
- **External Dependency Bias:** Biases introduced through reliance on third-party data, pre-trained models, or other external components.

- **Deployment and Interaction Bias:** Biases that emerge through user interaction post-deployment, including feedback loops and adaptive user interactions.
- **Generative Model Bias:** Biases specific to generative AI models, especially those related to content generation, such as confabulation or harmful stereotypes.

These biases are not confined to the development phase but can persist or even be amplified during the deployment and use phases, emphasizing the need for continuous, lifecycle-wide governance.

2.5.2 Key Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation

Effective governance frameworks for AI bias mitigation incorporate a combination of policy, process, and technical mechanisms:

- **Policy Mechanisms:** Establishing clear data governance policies, conducting ethical impact assessments, and integrating fairness-by-design principles into AI development processes.
- **Process Mechanisms:** Implementing regular bias audits and reviews, defining human oversight protocols, and establishing continuous monitoring and incident reporting systems.
- **Technical Mechanisms:** Utilizing algorithmic fairness techniques, deploying explainability and transparency tools, and managing adaptive feedback controls to prevent self-reinforcing biases post-deployment.

These mechanisms are critical in ensuring that AI systems are developed and operated in a manner that is transparent, accountable, and aligned with ethical standards. Appendix - E has a detailed list of these mechanisms and their respective sources from the literature.

2.5.3 Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles as Governance Foundations

Ethical principles serve as the foundation for trustworthy AI governance. Frameworks such as the OECD Principles on AI and UNESCO's Recommendation on the Ethics of AI emphasize values like inclusiveness, transparency, fairness, and accountability. These principles guide the development and implementation of AI systems that respect human rights and promote societal well-being. Incorporating these ethical principles into governance frameworks ensures that AI systems are not only legally compliant but also socially responsible, fostering public trust and acceptance.

2.5.4 Alignment with EU AI Act Requirements

The EU AI Act provides a regulatory framework that categorizes AI systems based on risk levels and imposes corresponding obligations. For high-risk AI systems, the Act mandates:

- **Risk Management and Documentation:** Implementing comprehensive risk management systems and maintaining detailed documentation of AI systems.
- **Dataset Quality and Bias Controls:** Ensuring the quality of datasets and implementing measures to detect and mitigate biases.
- **Human Oversight Mechanisms:** Establishing protocols for human oversight to intervene in AI decision-making processes.

- **Technical Robustness and Post-Deployment Monitoring:** Ensuring AI systems are technically robust and subject to continuous monitoring after deployment.

These requirements align with the ethical principles discussed earlier and provide a legal basis for enforcing responsible AI practices.

2.5.5 Integration into Broader Corporate Governance Structures

Integrating AI governance into existing corporate governance structures is essential for effective oversight and accountability. This integration involves:

- **Strategic Alignment:** Ensuring AI initiatives align with the organization's overall strategy and values.
- **Risk Management:** Incorporating AI risks into the organization's broader risk management framework.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Engaging diverse stakeholders, including marginalized communities, in AI governance processes to ensure inclusivity and fairness.

Embedding AI governance within corporate governance structures facilitates a holistic approach to managing AI-related risks and promotes organizational accountability.

2.5.6 Challenges in Bias Mitigation and AI Governance

Despite the advancements in AI governance frameworks, several challenges persist:

- **Lack of Clarity in AI Governance Roles and Processes:** There is a clear gap in the literature regarding the definition and clarity of governance responsibilities in AI. Few studies comprehensively address the essential dimensions of governance specifically, who is accountable, what actions are required, when governance measures should be applied, and how they should be executed.
- **Ethical Implementation and Stakeholder Inclusion:** Another key gap relates to the operationalisation of ethical AI. Although many governance frameworks emphasise risk management, they often lack practical guidance for implementing ethical principles and fail to ensure active stakeholder participation across different stages of the AI lifecycle.
- **Lack of Standardised Bias Metrics and Tools:** There is no consensus on which metrics to use for evaluating fairness, leading to inconsistencies in bias mitigation efforts.
- **Inadequate Post-Deployment Monitoring:** Many organizations lack mechanisms for real-time bias detection and adaptive retraining, allowing biases to persist or evolve unnoticed.
- **Fragmented Governance Approaches:** AI governance responsibilities are often siloed across different departments, hindering a cohesive approach to bias mitigation.
- **Limited Stakeholder Inclusion:** Marginalized or vulnerable communities are frequently excluded from AI design and governance discussions, resulting in systems that may not address their needs or concerns.
- **Ambiguity in Legal and Ethical Obligations:** Organizations often struggle to translate abstract ethical principles into practical compliance steps, leading to uncertainty in implementing responsible AI practices.

These identified challenges offer important insights for shaping a Trias Politica inspired AI governance model. They help define key factors that enable checks and balances within organisations to effectively mitigate bias-related risks in AI systems.

Chapter 3 – Methodology

3.1 RESEARCH APPROACH

This chapter goes deeper into the chosen methodology and why we have selected this research approach. The primary base of this thesis was to use the ideas behind the Trias Politica to govern AI-systems in a business context (van Gils & Mulder, 2023). Initially we envisaged developing an artifact and conducting relevant validation processes to prove its effectiveness in a business context. Hence, we started our initial research with design science methodology. However, during follow-up meetings with our promotors and reflections from the first expert session, it became clear that the original approach was overly ambitious given the complexity of the research question, the constraints of time, and available resources. Consequently, we revised our course of action and adjusted our RQ accordingly.

Therefore, we have adopted our research approach to a combination of the Interrogative Research Method and Aggregative Research Method, which allowed a structured approach designed to explore and systematically answer complex research questions by breaking them into sub-questions (Ritchie, J. et al, 2013). Following the adopted research approach, a plan was made by considering the standard research methods from both Aggregative and Interrogative methods. We have considered literature study, query-based Web search, and documents analysis methods from the aggregative research method and combined them with focus group sessions with questionnaires from the Interrogative research method (Vroom & Horvath, 2014). Combination of these two research methods provide us with a robust and comprehensive research approach to seek answers to our RQ. Figure illustrates the blueprint of a high-level research approach.

The plan was to validate the assumptions as formulated in section 1.2.1, obtain practical information from AI experts about bias related issues from existing AI implementations, and gather essential data. As the RQ is complex and touching upon various aspects of AI governance, democratic principles of Trias Politica Conceptual Model, policy formulation subjected to EU AI act and bias mitigation, we needed to ensure a comprehensive exploration of our RQ. Hence, the plan was to decompose the RQ into several RSQs.

The interrogation of RSQ1 and RSQ3 are to be conducted in parallel through critical literature review. The result of the literature review will contribute to a conceptual model answering RSQ2. This will be followed by data collection through case studies, focused group discussions and validations, culminating in a qualitative analysis. The results of the qualitative analysis were to be further validated with expert panel discussion to produce the results and subsequent conclusion of this research.

Figure 2: Research Approach based on Interrogative and Aggregative Research Methods

3.2 APPLIED METHODOLOGY AND METHODS

Following the guidelines adopted in the research plan we decomposed the RQ in a structured and comprehensive way. Through this process, the RQ was systematically divided into smaller, more manageable components, referred to as RSQs. Each RSQ targets a specific aspect of the RQ, enabling focused and detailed investigation. The decomposition involved identifying the key elements and dimensions of the problem, followed by formulating sub-questions to examine these elements individually. This ensures that the RSQs collectively contribute to answering the overarching research objective. We have fragmented the main research question to identify the core elements of the RQ as defined in section 1.3.

3.2.1 Finding answers for RSQ1

To explore RSQ1, we began with a comprehensive literature review focused on defining, identifying, categorising, and understanding bias in AI systems. We examined how bias manifests, its root causes, and the stages of the AI lifecycle at which it emerges. Subsequently, we reviewed various bias mitigation strategies and analysed the role of AI governance as a potential key factor in addressing these biases. In line with our research blueprint, the findings from the literature review were further enriched by insights gathered through a case study, focus group sessions, and expert interviews.

3.2.2 Finding answers for RSQ2

We tried to address RSQ2 using the literature review insights from RSQ1 that identifies bias mitigation strategies and related governance mechanism. We combined the theoretical insights from the literature study with concepts from COBIT 19 Governance Systems (ISACA, 2018) and structures, processes and relational mechanism concept from EGIT (De Haes, S. et al, 2020) to work on a conceptual governance model inspired by the separation of powers principle (Trias Politica). Details of the conceptual model is available in Figure 18: Trias AI Politica Conceptual Governance Model with reference to the EGIT model. A practical case study was conducted, examining AI implementations within organisations to enrich the conceptual model with real-world insights. This deliverable highlights the practical implications of governance in mitigating AI bias. The case study approach aligned well with our research methodology, allowing us to validate theoretical findings through real-life industry examples of AI implementations and governance practices. Since the Trias Politica-based governance mechanism is a new concept in this context, we validated the conceptual model using a focused group workshop. The insights gained were then integrated into the qualitative analysis used to address the RQ.

3.2.3 Finding answers for RSQ3

Given that many provisions of the EU AI Act are not yet widely implemented, we conducted a critical literature analysis of the Act to understand its approach to addressing AI bias and its associated compliance requirements. We examined the specific controls and measures proposed by the Act for bias mitigation. The findings from this analysis offer valuable insights into the regulatory framework and its provisions for AI governance and compliance.

3.3 LITERATURE REVIEW

The methodology for this critical literature review is designed to ensure an assessment of existing research to the topic concerning bias in AI systems, AI governance and EU AI Act. This section outlines the process undertaken to identify, evaluate and synthesise academic literature and globally recognised standards to develop key themes, theories, and gaps within the field of AI Bias related issues and related governance frameworks. The review follows a structured approach incorporating systematic search strategies, predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria, and rigorous analytical framework to critically assess and synthesise the findings of selected studies.

3.3.1 Data Sources and Search Strategy

We started our literature review with the initial documents and article links provided to us by our promoters. These resources helped us acquire valuable knowledge on the subject. Later in the quest of academic literature, the search was extended to established academic databases including Web of Science, Google Scholar. Keywords and Boolean operators were used to refine the search process, incorporating a combination of key concepts, synonyms, and relevant terminologies related to our research topic.

Considering the rapidly evolving landscape of AI and the abundance of available relatively recent literature we have extended our search to widely acclaimed and standardised sources. Our objective was to identify standardised and authoritative sources of information and collect relevant literature from those sources. During our initial investigation of our problem statement, we came across various standards, best practices and ethical AI principles towards AI governance from NIST and UNESCO. This endeavour led us to explore additional resources provided by the documentation portal from NIST and UNESCO where we discovered relevant literature offering foundational insights on the subject. Following initial inputs from our promoters, we further extended our research to the OECD portal to identify relevant policy and technical documents relevant to our topic for further analysis. NIST documents are important in this context because they provide standardised guidelines, frameworks, and best practices for AI systems, ensuring reliability, security, risk management, and ethical compliance. As a reputable institution, NIST's resources are widely recognised for their rigor and authority, making them crucial for grounding AI-related research and implementation in robust, evidence-based methodologies.

Hence the following list of sources were used.

- Web of Science
- Google Scholar
- Global Standards/Frameworks and Related references
 - NIST document portal
 - UNESCO document portal
 - OECD portal
 - Additional articles, reference sites and documents as referred by our promoters, and experts.

3.3.2 Critical Literature review for RSQ1

The following inclusion and exclusion criteria were followed during refining the searches and later during the preliminary review to select the relevant documents for the literature review.

Inclusion criteria:

- Research that directly addresses the core themes and objectives of this review (e.g. AI Bias, AI governance directly attributing to RSQ1).
- Studies published within past 3 years. Considering the recent emergence of AI adaptation and fast-moving technological landscape, we kept this to past 3 years to obtain relatively fresher research on this topic.
- Articles proposing or evaluating governance frameworks, ethical principles, or bias mitigation techniques.
- Peer-reviewed journal articles, standards from reputed world bodies and reputable academic books.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Non-English publications
- Studies outside the core scope of the research focus (e.g. other than AI bias, AI governance related topics)
- Any article without open access

Web of Science

To address RSQ1, a structured literature search was conducted using *Web of Science*. The search query included terms such as “*AI Bias*,” “*Bias Mitigation*,” “*Algorithmic Bias*,” “*AI Governance*,” and “*AI*,” and was limited to English-language publications. The initial search returned *160 results*, which were then refined based on several criteria: publication years (2022, 2023, or early access for 2024), document types (articles, early access papers, awarded grants, abstracts, or theses), and databases (Web of Science Core Collection, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Citation Index, or Grants Index). The search was further narrowed to the research areas of Computer Science, Engineering, and Social Issues.

From the refined list, *34 relevant articles* were selected for closer examination. Titles and abstracts were then reviewed against predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to determine their relevance to specific attributes of RSQ1. The most relevant articles were included in the final Web of Science Selection List for detailed analysis, ensuring that the literature review incorporated diverse and rigorously filtered academic sources.

The selection of papers did not provide enough satisfactory coverage of all relevant aspects of the RQ and most of them were predominantly covering the healthcare and life science sectors. This enticed us to search for additional literature covering a wider spectrum of industries and relevancy to our research question using Google Scholar. Appendix C: Figure 6 illustrates the method in detail.

Google Scholar

To further support the investigation of RSQ1 a structured literature search was conducted using Google Scholar, following a systematic two-query approach. The first query focused on “AI Bias” OR “AI” AND “Bias,” while the second targeted “AI Governance.” Both searches were limited to sources from 2023 onwards and included patents and citations. From the initial 16,800 and 10,600 results respectively, titles and short descriptions from the first five pages were reviewed to shortlist relevant documents. Abstracts of these shortlisted articles were then

screened using predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure alignment with the specific attributes of RSQ1. Open-access articles meeting these criteria were added to a final selection list for detailed review. This rigorous filtering process ensured that only high-relevance, up-to-date literature contributed to the foundational analysis of AI bias and governance. Appendix C Figure 7 further illustrates the search approach.

NIST

The NIST portal provides search functions for its publications. The NIST search interface performs keywords search for the titles, Abstract, Citations, Keyword or Authors. An advanced search on the NIST portal using the search term “AI bias risk mitigation and governance “within the topic area “AI” produced 106 results. A further careful review of the titles and followed by a review of the abstracts, we have identified three relevant papers addressing bias in AI systems and AI risk management. Appendix C - Figure 8 further illustrates the search approach.

UNESCO

Based on insights from the expert session with Achmea, we went to the UNESCO portal looking for “*UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*” within the document repository of the website UNESCO.org. After finding the required document, we wanted to extend our search for additional standards. A targeted search for “AI bias” and “AI Governance” in the document repository of UNESCO portal was conducted. The search criteria were filtered to:

- Language: English,
- Material Type: Books, Content Nature: Guides, manuals, and handbooks
- Publication Year: 2023

This search returned 57 results. After reviewing the document titles followed by abstracts for the latest standards and relevance to the research focus, two key documents were selected for further analysis that made total three documents from the UNESCO repository. Appendix C - Figure 8 further illustrates the search approach.

Selection of most relevant documents

After reviewing the content of each shortlisted document, we have selected a list of the most relevant research papers for further critical review and analysis. The selection is based on their comprehensive treatment of bias types, sources, and lifecycle stages in AI systems, especially in the context of AI governance and risk management. The list of research papers utilised for further literature review along their relevance to this research were provided in Appendix C - Figure 9.

3.3.3 Critical Literature review for RSQ3

The literature review of the EU AI Act involved a close examination of the draft legislation in its current form. The focus was on understanding how AI systems are categorized by risk levels and what compliance obligations apply to each category. Special attention was given to sections that address bias-related risks, including how the Act defines, regulates, and aims to mitigate such risks. Insights were drawn specifically from provisions concerning bias, associated risks, and the required governance and compliance measures.

3.4 CASE STUDY

In accordance with our research approach, we conducted a case study with one of the organisations who has successfully implemented AI systems. The study was conducted through initial exploration and engaging with Achmea's AI and innovation team. After presenting our case, purpose and objective of this engagement we were directed towards the data governance team that is also responsible for AI governance within Achmea. We performed the following actions

1. **Initial Exploration:** Engaging with Achmea's AI & Innovation Team.
2. **Document Analysis:** Reviewing Achmea's AI governance policies and ethical framework.
3. **Literature Review:** Gathering inputs from the broader literature review activity as part of our research and utilizing vital relevant insights to guide this case study and to further validate theoretical findings with practical implementation.
4. **Expert interviews and workshop-based data collection:** Presenting research findings to Achmea's AI governance team. And obtaining key information through interview questions, brainstorming sessions. We have conducted the workshop with Meeting Wizard tool. The tool works as a Group support system and facilitates expert sessions and relevant data capturing in a very efficient and structured way which complements to scientific research methodology.
5. **Qualitative Analysis:** Capturing insights from documents analysis, focused group workshop and expert discussions and performing a qualitative analysis on the findings.
6. **Review:** Details of the findings post qualitative analysis were shared with Achmea to fact check and validate our understand on the AI system, organisational structure, processes, best practices, technical mitigation techniques and tools.
7. **Result Output:** The final output of the case study was produced after integrating the feedback received from Achmea and subsequent confirmation on the fact check.

Research approach is further detailed in section 2.2 Research Approach of the case study document in Appendix – G

3.5 FOCUSED GROUP WORKSHOP

The focus group session was conducted with academic experts and members of the AI implementation and governance team at Achmea where we presented key findings of our literature review, and the conceptual governance model based on the principles of Trias Politica. The objective was to gather insights on identifying key factors of an AI governance framework based on the Trias Politica model, to mitigate bias-related risks during the adoption of AI systems like MASHA in organisations like Achmea. The focus group was attended by total 12 participations where 8 of them were from Achmea.

The structure of the focus group was consisting of 3 type of data capturing mechanisms. (1) Questions following "what degree do you agree" designed to acquire a confidence score, (2) question and answer and (3) brainstorming session with open discussion on the topic.

Participants included AI governance experts, data scientists, organisational leaders, and ethics officers. The discussion centred on bias risks, governance challenges, and the applicability of the separation of powers in a corporate AI context. A detailed report and result summary is available in Appendix – L

3.6 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

This study uses a deductive thematic analysis, with themes structured around the main RQ and its RSQs, guided by COBIT 2019 and EGIT governance models. Qualitative data from the literature review, case study, expert sessions, and focus group workshop were analysed against this structure. The answers to RSQ1, RSQ2, and RSQ3 collectively support the final response to the RQ. Findings were validated through an expert panel, and the resulting feedback was integrated into the results.

3.7 EXPERT VALIDATION WORKSHOP

The consolidated findings from all sources following the qualitative analysis were presented to a panel of AI experts for validation. The structure of the validation session was consisting of 2 type of data capturing mechanisms. (1) Questions following “what extent do you agree” designed to acquire a confidence score, (2) brainstorming session with open discussion on the topic. The goals were to:

- Assess expert confidence in the completeness and relevance of the results
- Gather additional feedback through brainstorming on the implications, limitations, and future opportunities of the study

A detailed report and result summary is available at Appendix – M

3.8 USE OF GSS AS A FOUNDATIONAL METHODOLOGY

During the beginning of our research our promotor had shared an article with us regarding the use the Group Support System (GSS) as a research methodology. A GSS-based assessment method focuses on getting all AI actors’ collective views and opinions. These AI actors vary in the AI lifetime but share a joint responsibility of managing the risks of AI. This group can reflect a diversity of experience, backgrounds, and expertise. Using a GSS-based assessment, you remove the risk of bias by collectively doing the evaluation together (Bobbert & van Dijk, 2023). The article reiterated that academic research shows that GSS-based collective assessments help generate diverse and valid insights through open discussion and consensus-building. This process enhances understanding, raises awareness on key issues like accountability, and supports stronger commitment to goals and actions, leading to more sustainable implementation of AI strategies (Bobbert & van Dijk, 2023).

This vital input in the beginning of our research helped us to conduct focus group sessions and expert panel sessions with a GSS-based assessment method using the Meeting Wizard platform. This platform offers an interactive environment for brainstorming, structured discussions, and voting on critical aspects of the research. The session generates valuable insights, validates findings from the earlier tracks, and incorporates feedback from case studies to refine the final conclusions. This iterative validation ensures the robustness and reliability of the research outcomes.

3.9 SUMMARY

We collected data and insights from multiple sources including an extensive literature review, in-depth case studies, focused group and expert sessions to explore bias and governance in AI. Our approach comprised detailed document analysis of regulatory texts such as the EU AI Act and organisational governance frameworks, along with focused group workshops and expert validation sessions using a structured questionnaire and brainstorming techniques (e.g., Meeting Wizard Group support system). This multi-method strategy provided a comprehensive basis for understanding bias risks, governance challenges, and the practical applicability of the Trias Politica principles in organisational contexts. With this foundation established, the following section presents our key findings and emerging patterns derived from the qualitative analysis.

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Chapter 4 – Analysis

This chapter we have compiled the outputs from multiple data sources and brought together to conduct a qualitative analysis aimed at addressing the research question.

4.1 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

This section presents the qualitative analysis of data gathered from three primary sources: the literature review, a case study on MASHA at Achmea, and a focus group session. The analysis applies a deductive thematic approach, where themes were pre-defined based on the components of the main RQ and its three RSQs. These themes were further supported by the governance structures outlined in COBIT 2019 and EGIT. Through this structured analysis, six key themes were identified, and insights from the different data sources were aggregated accordingly.

The following table 1 outlines how each thematic cluster identified in this study aligns with the respective RSQs, and how they collectively contribute to answering the RQ. This mapping demonstrates how the qualitative findings from the literature review, case study, and focus group are synthesised to form a coherent framework for AI governance based on Trias Politica principles within the context of the EU AI Act.

No.	Theme	Mapped RSQ	Contribution to RQ	COBIT 2019 / EGIT Alignment
1	Bias Types, Sources, and Lifecycle Phases	RSQ1	Identifies the types and stages of bias that governance needs to manage. Helps define ‘ <i>what risks</i> ’ governance must address.	Processes: Identification and management of risks across AI lifecycle (build/use).
2	Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation	RSQ1	Outlines ‘ <i>how</i> ’ to manage the identified risks through structured controls in terms of policy, process, and technical mechanisms.	Processes, Principles, Policies and Procedures, People, Skills and Competencies
3	Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles	RSQ2	Adds foundational values to governance for bias mitigation by supporting fairness, transparency, and accountability.	Principles, Culture, Ethics and Behaviour: Embedding fairness, transparency, and human oversight. - People, Skills and Competencies: AI ethics training and stakeholder inclusion.

4	Integration into Corporate Governance Structures	RSQ2	Demonstrates how AI governance can be embedded into existing structures (boards, risk systems) for operational viability.	Organisational Structures, Processes
5	Trias Politica: Separation of Powers in AI Governance	RSQ2	Offers a structured model for <i>organising governance functions</i> : legislative (policy), executive (implementation), judiciary (oversight).	Organisational Structures: Separation of roles into legislative (policy), executive (implementation), and judiciary (oversight)
6	Compliance with the EU AI Act	RSQ3	Anchors the governance model within current legal and regulatory requirements, particularly for high-risk AI.	Policies and Procedures: Aligned with legal mandates like GDPR and the EU AI Act.

Table 1: Mapping of Identified themes to RSQ and RQ as a whole

4.1.1 Theme 1: Understanding Bias Types, Sources, and Lifecycle Phases

Bias in AI systems appears during both the *build* and *use* phases. From the literature, we learn that biases can originate from historical data, flawed design decisions, or societal norms. Bias can be *data-related*, such as sampling and label bias, or *model-related*, such as feature selection or optimisation bias. During the use phase, bias can be amplified through adaptive learning or user interaction. In MASHA’s case, Achmea identifies and addresses bias through structured oversight and uses techniques like pseudonymisation and fairness metrics to reduce hidden bias. One focus group participant remarked, “*We can’t make an AI system 100% bias free. Hence a good idea to define thresholds.*” This supports the idea that bias must be managed continuously, rather than eliminated outright. This finding aligns with COBIT 2019’s emphasis on lifecycle governance and risk treatment Evaluate, Direct and Monitor (EDM): Ensure Risk Optimisation. A synthesis from the literature review can be obtained here: Synthesis of Bias Categories, types, source and root cause.

4.1.2 Theme 2: Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation

All sources emphasised three types of mechanisms: *policy*, *process*, and *technical*. Literature stresses the importance of fairness-by-design, bias audits, and explainability tools. The case study showed Achmea implementing these through a checklist, model registration, and red-teaming exercises. These were structured around their ethical AI principles and implemented across all AI systems. These findings reflect COBIT’s “Align, Plan and Organise” (APO) domain and EGIT’s guiding principle of ensuring benefits delivery through structured controls. The focus group emphasised the value of these continuous practices, noting that “*continuous monitoring and human-in-the-loop checkpoints*” are needed to detect and manage emerging bias.

Details from literature review: Appendix - E

Details from Case study:

6.2 Mapping insights from literature review with Operational practices at Achmea

6.3 AI Bias related Risks in MASHA and related mitigation mechanisms

4.1.3 Theme 3: Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles

Ethical principles such as fairness, transparency, accountability, and privacy emerged as key factors of AI governance. The literature connects these to OECD and UNESCO guidelines. From the findings of the literature study, we performed a relevance analysis of the principles of OECD and UNESCO to identify their relevancy to AI bias related issues. Relevance criteria were defined to analyse them. The analysis resulted into a strong relevance of these principles to bias related risks. Four out of the five OECD principles and seven out of the ten UNESCO principles are directly relevant to bias. None were found to be not relevant. Table 14 and 15 at Appendix – H has details on this analysis results.

Achmea operationalises these principles through its “*Ethical Wheel*”, used to evaluate AI risks and fairness. In the focus group, one participant highlighted the importance of these values: “*The ethical framework guides how AI decisions are made. It’s not just compliance, it’s culture.*” Details can be obtained here: 4.1 Key AI Principles Adapted by Achmea.

This theme shows that embedding ethical principles helps move from abstract ideals to actionable safeguards in real-world AI deployment. This approach fits the EGIT principle of “value delivery” by ensuring that AI systems align with stakeholder values and public expectations.

4.1.4 Theme 4: Integration into Corporate Governance Structures

Integrating AI governance into existing governance structures is critical. The literature advises embedding AI oversight into board-level processes to ensure strategic alignment and consistent accountability. Achmea demonstrates this approach by involving its Privacy Board, Ethics Committee, and cross-functional Risk Committees. These bodies allow the organisation to align AI governance with broader enterprise goals and regulatory requirements. One focus group participant emphasised, “*We don’t need to reinvent governance; we just need to extend it with the right AI checkpoints.*” This insight reinforces the idea that embedding AI into corporate governance makes oversight practical, efficient, and scalable.

In parallel, Achmea is also in the process of formally integrating AI risk management into its corporate risk management framework, guided by the NIST AI RMF. This includes structured mapping, measuring, and managing of AI-related risks, ensuring that AI-specific controls are harmonised with enterprise-wide risk strategies. This reflects the COBIT governance framework’s view of “*governance system enablers*” such as organisational structures, decision-making protocols, and continuous performance monitoring.

Literature: 2.5.5 Integration into Broader Corporate Governance Structures

Case Study: 4.3 AI Governance Structures

4.1.5 Theme 5: Trias Politica–Based Governance Structure

This theme emerged directly from the research question and was strongly supported in the focus group. Drawing from the Trias Politica model, governance responsibilities are divided into:

- **Legislative:** Policy creation and standards

- **Executive:** Implementation and operations
- **Judiciary:** Independent audits and grievance handling

Achmea uses this structure to map responsibilities clearly, reduce conflicts, and establish balance. Focus group participants appreciated the model but acknowledged challenges: *“In reality, we wear multiple hats. Separation is hard, but having clarity helps”*. In a question related to the positioning of the judiciary branch, one participant mentioned *“If this particular branch is external, it can properly carry out oversight without being biased by day-to-day operations.”*. However, others cautioned about practical challenges, such as cost, legal requirements, and finding third parties with enough expertise to evaluate AI systems thoroughly. This was also explicitly mentioned that internal department is still functional as Achmea is still performing well without any such issues while operating in a highly regulated environment. Participants agreed that the legislative branch create, unify, and maintain policies regarding bias mitigation, data quality, transparency, and risk thresholds. Ensures consistency across internal standards so that, as one participant remarked, *“we don’t end up with inconsistent policies on privacy vs. AP”*. This confirmed our proposal to position the judiciary branch as passive structure that doesn’t participate in daily operational activities of governance.

One participant observed *“As MASHA is identified as a High-Risk AI system, a Trias Politica approach seems appropriate.”*. While many endorsed the structure for high-risk AI like MASHA, some participants admitted true independence is hard to achieve, noting *“On every occasion, the first line is always accountable. The audit and monitoring teams only advise, they don’t make the decisions. the executives decide.”*

The influence of an informal “4th pillar,” often referring to either long-tenured employees or external groups (e.g., media, advocacy bodies) that can quietly shape AI outcomes was highlighted. One attendee remarked, *“The people who have been in the organisation 10, 20, 30 years can act as a ‘shadow power,’ too, shaping AI outcomes beyond policy”* This “4th pillar” can operate alongside legislative, executive, and judiciary functions, sometimes circumventing formal governance rules to affect decisions. These comments show strong conceptual support with an understanding of practical limits. Following links provided additional details on this theme.

During the focus group session, participants were asked to vote around several propositions “To what degree you agree” related to the Trias AI Politica Governance conceptual model using a 4-point Likert scale. The questions were framed to gain their confidence on such a model. While the average confidence score across all questions was **3.36**. The panel gave a high average rating **3.6** for applying Trias Politica principles to govern AI systems like MASHA. This indicates strong agreement to the factors of the conceptual model. Figure 3 on the next page points out the results of the questions asked.

Figure 3: Trias AI Politica Conceptual Model Validation Result

Mode detail information can be obtained from the following links.

Trias politica Conceptual Model: Appendix – I

Case Study: Mapping Achmea’s AI governance practices to Trias Politica Conceptual model

Focus Group Workshop Report: Appendix – L

4.1.6 Theme 6: Compliance with Eu AI Act.

The final theme concerns compliance with the EU AI Act. Literature highlights the need for formal frameworks, lifecycle documentation, and human oversight. Achmea proactively implements most of these, including model risk classification, DPIAs, and transparency protocols. In the focus group, participants agreed with regulatory alignment but expressed uncertainty about implementation details. One said, *“We support the Act, but need more guidance from regulators to implement it correctly.”* This theme reflects the tension between aspiration and application, underscoring the need for external collaboration and internal adaptability.

Details from Literature: 2.4 Regulatory Approaches to Bias: The EU AI Act in Focus

Details from Case Study: Alignment with EU AI Act9.1.7 Alignment with the EU AI Act

4.1.7 Overview of Thematic Analysis

While details on the results from each source provided in the respective Appendix - K, L and M of (Literature, Case Study, Focus Group) The following table 2 outlines overview of the thematic analysis and contribution from various data sources towards the specific theme.

No.	Theme Title	Literature	Case Study	Focus Group	Key Insights
1	Bias Types Sources and Lifecycle Phases	✓		✓	Bias is multifaceted source and root cause depends on the bias types. Emerges in both build and use phases. Thresholds are essential.
2	Governance Mechanisms for Bias Mitigation	✓	✓	✓	Governance is essential for mitigation spanning policy, process, and technical domains.
3	Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles	✓	✓	✓	Ethics like fairness and transparency drive design and review.
4	Integration into Corporate Governance Structures	✓	✓	✓	Extending existing structures avoids duplication and improves efficiency.
5	Trias Politica Governance Structure	✓	✓	✓	Separation of powers enhances oversight; practical overlap acknowledged.
6	Compliance with EU AI Act	✓	✓	✓	Most requirements addressed; regulators need to clarify expectations.

Table 2: Overview of Thematic Analysis

We analysed data from the literature, case study, and focus group, as described in this chapter, to identify key governance elements for managing AI bias. The next chapter presents the results, showing how the proposed governance model addresses each question and is supported by the evidence.

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Chapter 5 - Results

This chapter presents the main results of the research, structured according to the overarching RQ and the three RSQs. A qualitative analysis approach was applied to identify recurring patterns and actionable insights across these data sources with reference to the identified themes. The objective is to identify key relevant factors that are instrumental in developing an AI governance framework based on the principles of Trias Politica and in accordance with the EU AI Act, while considering bias mitigation as a potential risk.

5.1 RESULTS RSQ1: BIAS IN AI AND GOVERNANCE-BASED MITIGATION STRATEGIES

This section outlines the findings for RSQ1. Analysed sources confirmed that AI bias is multi-layered and can emerge during both the build and use phases. Common types include sampling bias, historical bias, feature selection bias, and confabulation in generative models. These findings were echoed in the case study at Achmea, where data quality standards and bias audits were embedded throughout the lifecycle of the MASHA system. A comprehensive list of bias types, its source and lifecycle stage of emergence has been provided in Appendix – D. The following table 3 captures the consolidated list of key factors as bias mitigation governance controls in terms of policy, process and technical mechanisms with its applicable lifecycle stage:

No	Governance Controls	Type (Policy/ Process/ Technical)	Applicable Phase (Build/Use)	Short Description
1	Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making	Policy	Build & Use	Ethical guidelines for fairness, transparency, and customer protection (e.g., HLEG Trustworthy AI, used in MASHA).
2	Model Management & Validation Policy	Policy	Build & Use	Periodic AI model validation to ensure robust performance and fairness (e.g., medical expert validation for MASHA).
3	Fairness-by-Design Principles	Policy	Build	Embedding fairness into the AI design process to prevent systemic inequalities and unfair outcomes.
4	Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs)	Policy	Build & Use	Evaluations of AI systems for privacy and business impact prior to deployment (e.g., conducted on MASHA).
5	Privacy Impact Assessments (PIAs)	Policy	Build	Assess data privacy risks to ensure compliance and data protection standards (e.g., PIAs performed at Achmea).
6	Daily Close Principles	Policy	Build	Ensures automated data quality and compliance, providing high-quality data for AI implementations (e.g., data management at Achmea).
7	Third-party Data Vetting	Policy	Build	Guidelines to vet external data sources for quality, integrity, and relevance to reduce potential biases.

8	Data Governance Policies	Policy	Build	Policies ensuring quality, diversity, and representativeness of datasets to mitigate bias risks.
9	Education and Training Programs, Employee Awareness	Process	Build & Use	Initiatives to train developers, stakeholders, and end-users on AI ethics and bias mitigation strategies. Training staff on responsible AI use and ethical compliance (e.g., Achmea's e-learning programs).
10	Pre-Production AI Quality Gate Checklist	Process	Build	Compliance checklist ensuring AI meets legal, ethical, and fairness standards before deployment (e.g., MASHA's pre-launch checks).
11	Ethical Impact Assessments	Process	Build & Use	Frameworks to assess ethical implications, manage risks, and align AI with societal and organisational values.
12	Stakeholder Engagement	Process	Build	Inclusion of diverse and marginalised communities in governance processes to address biases. Integrating diverse stakeholder inputs to address biases and ensure ethical AI decisions (e.g., multidisciplinary teams at Achmea).
13	Risk Management Frameworks (RMFs)	Process	Build & Use	Continuous evaluation of risks, alignment of optimisation goals with ethical principles, and harm mitigation strategies. (e.g., NIST AI Risk Management Framework)
14	Incentives for Inclusive Practices	Process	Build	Economic or regulatory incentives for adopting inclusive practices in AI development and deployment.
15	Continuous Monitoring and Collaboration	Process	Use	Mechanisms for ongoing evaluation and collaboration to address emerging risks and biases in AI systems. Real-time monitoring for biases or unexpected behaviours (e.g., monitoring tools for MASHA).
16	Human Oversight Mechanisms (Human-in-the-Loop Approach)	Process	Build & Use	Systems allowing human intervention to ensure accountability in decision-making processes. (e.g., MASHA forwards cases for manual review).
17	Bias Audits and Reviews	Technical	Build	Independent and systematic evaluations to identify and address biases in datasets and AI systems.
18	Transparency & Explainability Measures	Technical	Build & Use	Mechanisms for explainability, documentation, and clear communication to ensure accountability.
19	Fairness Audits	Technical	Build & Use	Regular bias evaluations during model training to ensure fairness (e.g., MASHA model assessments).
20	Data Validation & Quality Control	Technical	Build	Use of audited, pseudonymised data to continuously assess fairness (e.g., MASHA's dataset management).
21	Red Teaming	Technical	Build & Use	Adversarial testing to detect vulnerabilities or biases in AI systems (e.g., regularly conducted on MASHA).

Table 3: Consolidated Governance controls for Bias Mitigation

5.2 RESULTS RSQ2: TRIAS POLITICA–BASED GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE

This section presents the findings related to RSQ2, which explores how the separation of powers inspired by the Trias Politica principle can be applied to AI governance in organisational settings. Insights were drawn from the literature review, the case study at Achmea, the focus group session, and are visually supported by the conceptual governance structure illustrated in the Trias AI Politica Governance model at Appendix – I
Trias AI Politica Conceptual Model for Bias-Resilient AI Governance

5.2.1 Governance Structure – Separation of Powers

The integration of Trias Politica is operationalised through the definition of three distinct governance branches; each aligned with specific roles and responsibilities:

- **Legislative Branch:** Responsible for policy creation and standardisation, including defining data governance standards, fairness requirements, and threshold levels for acceptable bias.
- **Executive Branch:** Handles operational implementation. This includes model development, resource allocation, and adherence to defined standards. The case study at Achmea shows this is reflected in operational roles distributed among data scientists, model validators, and risk teams.
- **Judiciary Branch:** Envisions independent oversight through red teaming, audits, and review of decisions or bias-related complaints. However, as noted during the focus group, full independence is difficult to achieve in practice.

5.2.2 Governance Processes

To support the structure, process controls are introduced across all stages of the AI lifecycle. These include audits, risk assessments, and oversight mechanisms. At Achmea, internal processes such as model registration and bias testing are embedded as standard steps before deployment.

5.2.3 Role of AI Principles

The principles of trustworthy and ethical AI (from OECD, UNESCO, and HLEG) are embedded across all branches, especially the legislative one. These guide policy creation, influence operational execution, and underpin review mechanisms. Achmea aligns with these principles using fairness metrics, documentation, and technical control tools such as automated bias detection and threshold calibration.

5.2.4 Relational Mechanisms and Informal Structures

An important finding from the focus group was the recognition of “*shadow powers*” long-tenured employees or external actors (e.g. media, lobbying groups) who influence governance indirectly. This dynamic supports the idea that beyond formal branches, cross-functional collaboration and stakeholder inclusion are essential to hold power in check. These relational mechanisms are essential to maintaining balance and accountability, especially when the ideal separation of powers is not structurally feasible.

5.2.5 Integration into Corporate Governance Structures

One of the most important findings is that successful implementation of a Trias Politica model requires integration into existing corporate governance structures. Achmea avoids standalone governance silos by embedding AI oversight into its existing risk, ethics, and compliance committees. The organisation is also in the process of aligning AI risk management with its enterprise risk management system, following the NIST Risk Management Framework (RMF).

5.3 RESULTS RSQ3: COMPLIANCE WITH EU AI ACT.

This section presents the results for RSQ3, which explores how the EU AI Act addresses bias-related risks in AI systems. The analysis draws on literature, the Achmea case study, and visual synthesis of the EU AI Act's provisions, with particular emphasis on high-risk systems such as MASHA (Alignment with EU AI Act). The provisions are structured under three main categories: risk-based classification, compliance requirements, and governance structure.

5.3.1 Risk-Based Classification

The EU AI Act introduces a risk-based framework for regulating AI systems. AI systems are categorized into unacceptable, high-risk, limited-risk, and minimal-risk levels based on their potential to impact health, safety, and fundamental rights. MASHA, for instance, falls under the high-risk category due to its role in insurance decision-making.

5.3.2 High-Risk AI Compliance Requirements

For high-risk AI systems, the EU AI Act mandates a wide range of safeguards to ensure fairness, transparency, and non-discrimination. These include:

- **Rigorous Data Governance:** High-quality, representative data must be used throughout the AI lifecycle to prevent embedded bias.
- **Mandatory Risk Assessment:** Risk must be evaluated continuously, from design to post-deployment.
- **Human Oversight:** Mechanisms must ensure human involvement in critical decisions to prevent unchecked automated outcomes.
- **Bias Detection & Mitigation:** Technical and procedural methods must be in place to detect, measure, and correct bias.
- **Post-Deployment Monitoring:** Real-world model behaviour must be tracked to detect drift and unintended bias.
- **Continuous Feedback Loop:** User interactions should inform ongoing system improvements and fairness calibration.
- **Conformity Assessment Before Deployment:** Systems must undergo predefined evaluations before they are placed on the market.
- **Testing and Validation for Fairness:** Performance across demographic groups must be tested and documented.
- **Technical Documentation & Record Keeping:** Complete traceability and transparency in how AI systems function.
- **Transparency Protocols:** Information about AI logic and decision-making must be made available to users and regulators.

- **Accuracy, Robustness, and Cybersecurity:** Systems must operate reliably under normal and unforeseen conditions.

Achmea has implemented many of these safeguards in MASHA, demonstrating readiness for future legal compliance. For instance, bias testing and post-market monitoring have already been built into its operational model.

5.3.3 Governance Structure Requirements

The EU AI Act also outlines institutional and organisational governance expectations, particularly for high-risk AI systems:

- **Internal Governance with Accountability:** Organisations must establish clear lines of accountability for AI system decisions and risks.
- **Regulatory Oversight:** National authorities and the newly created EU AI Board oversee implementation, audit processes, and enforcement.
- **Ethical Mandates:** Systems must uphold principles of **fairness** and **non-discrimination**, embedded in both development and operation.
- **Incident Reporting Mechanisms:** Organisations must document and report incidents that may compromise fairness, safety, or legal compliance.

These governance requirements reinforce the need to embed AI governance into broader corporate structures, a practice already underway at Achmea.

The EU AI Act enforces a comprehensive legal framework that aligns strongly with ethical AI governance. Its focus on high-risk systems ensures that AI impacting critical rights or services is subject to strict controls. Achmea's MASHA system, which aligns well with many of these requirements, exemplifies how organisations can prepare for compliance by embedding robust governance structures and processes. These legal obligations complement the conceptual governance model proposed in this study and reinforce the role of law in bias mitigation.

5.4 ANSWERING THE RESEARCH QUESTION (RQ)

This research combined insights from academic literature, a practical case study at Achmea, a focus group session with domain experts and a validation session with experts. The culmination of these sources enabled a detailed response to the research sub-questions:

- **RSQ1:** The analysis identified a range of bias types and governance mechanisms needed to mitigate them.
- **RSQ2:** The Trias Politica model emerged as a promising lens for designing an AI governance structure, offering a balance of power and clearer accountability.
- **RSQ3:** The governance features examined were found to align well with the compliance requirements set by the EU AI Act.

Together, the answers to these sub-questions provide a strong foundation for addressing the overarching Research Question (RQ):

“Which factors are relevant for designing a governance framework such that we apply the principles of the Trias Politica in order to mitigate bias-related risks when adopting AI in organisations within the context of the EU AI Act?”

The study confirms that a Trias Politica inspired governance structure, supported by ethical principles and embedded in corporate frameworks, offers a feasible and effective approach to managing AI bias in compliance with evolving regulations.

The study has identified six top level relevant factors. Below, Figure 4: Relevant factors for Trias AI politica Governance framework, captures these Top-level Relevant factors for a Trias Politica inspired AI governance framework to mitigate bias related risks within organisations. These top-level factors were further elaborated with their respective factors in Table 4: Top level Relevant factors for Trias AI Politica Governance Framework. It offers links for additional detailed information for each identified Top level Relevant factors.

Figure 4: Relevant factors for Trias AI politica Governance framework

Table 4 captures these top-level factors along with their respective subfactors in details.

Trias AI Politica Governance – Relevant Factors	
Top Level Factor 1	What AI Risk to Mitigate
What AI Risk To Mitigate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bias In AI <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear Bias Definition Identify Bias Category/Types <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Related Bias Model Design and Algorithmic Bias Societal and Cultural Bias External Dependency Bias Deployment and Interaction Bias Generative Model Bias Source and Root Cause of Identified Bias Types Phase of Bias Manifestation in AI Lifecycle
Short Description	Identification of bias types relevant for the AI implementation (e.g., data, algorithmic, societal) and understanding their origin across the AI lifecycle.
Sources and Reference	Literature: Synthesis of Bias Categories, types, source and root cause

Short Description	Application of policy controls, process mechanisms, and technical measures to address bias at different stages.
Sources and Reference	Literature: Appendix - E Case Study: Appendix – G and L Focus group session: Table 3: Consolidated Governance controls for Bias Mitigation - M

Top Level Factor 3	Timing: When to Apply Mitigation Mechanism
<p>Timing: When To Apply Mitigation Mechanism</p>	<pre> graph LR Root[Timing: When To Apply Mitigation Mechanism] --- Build[AI Build Phase: Pre Deployment] Root --- Use[AI Use Phase: Post Deployment] Build --- DC[Data Collection] Build --- DPL[Data Processing / Labelling] Build --- MDD[Model Design and Development] Build --- MTE[Model Training and Evaluation] Build --- T[Testing] Use --- FT[Field Trials] Use --- PU[Production Use] Use --- FL[Feedback Loop] Use --- UI[User Interaction] Use --- CG[Content Generation] </pre>
<p>Short Description</p>	<p>Lifecycle-based approach. Mitigation actions must be applied both during the build and use phases of AI systems.</p>
<p>Sources and Reference</p>	<p>Literature: Appendix - C Table 8: Bias Classification Case Study: Appendix - G</p>

Top Level Factor 4	Role of AI Principles
<p>Role Of AI Principles</p>	<pre> graph LR Root[Role Of AI Principles] --- Derived[Derived from Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles] Derived --- OECD[OECD] Derived --- UNESCO[UNESCO] Derived --- EEC[EEC] Derived --- AOS[Any Other standards] </pre>
<p>Short Description</p>	<p>Embedding global trustworthy AI principles (e.g., fairness, accountability, transparency) into governance practices.</p>
<p>Sources and Reference</p>	<p>Literature: Appendix – H Case Study: Appendix - G</p>

Top-Level Factor 5	AI Governance Structure
Short Description	Distribution of governance roles into legislative, executive, and judiciary functions. Includes integration into broader corporate governance structures.
Sources and Reference	<p>Literature: Appendix – I</p> <p>Trias AI Politica Conceptual Model for Bias-Resilient AI Governance</p> <p>Case Study: Mapping Achmea’s AI governance practices to Trias Politica Conceptual model</p>

Top Level Factor 6	EU AI Act Compliance
Short Description	Alignment with regulatory requirements including risk classification, human oversight, documentation, and transparency obligations.
Sources and Reference	Literature: Appendix - D Case Study: Alignment with EU AI Act

Table 4: Top level Relevant factors for Trias AI Politica Governance Framework

5.5 RESULTS EXPERT VALIDATION SESSION

To ensure the reliability and completeness of the research findings, a final expert validation session was conducted with ten experts in the fields of AI governance, risk management, and ethics. The session aimed to assess expert confidence in the relevance and completeness of the identified factors for a Trias Politica–inspired AI governance model intended to mitigate bias-related risks under the EU AI Act.

5.5.1 Confidence Ratings and Validation

Experts were asked to rate their agreement with ten key questions related to the identified governance factors using a 4-point Likert scale. The average confidence score across all factors was **3.4**, indicating strong expert agreement. Some of the highest-rated factors included:

- Timing of Mitigation Measures (Build Phase) – *3.7 average rating*
- Integration into Corporate Governance – *3.6 average rating*
- Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles – *3.4 average rating*
- AI Governance Components (Policy, Process, Technical Controls) – *3.4 average rating*

The factor “*Stakeholder engagement and shadow powers*” showed the highest variability in expert scores, with a deviation of 58%. This variation encouraged further discussion during the validation session. Participants from a specific public sector organisation acknowledged the importance of this factor in general but felt it may be less applicable in their own organisational context reflected their rating. Despite this, the overall scores validated the relevance of the proposed governance model and confirmed its alignment with expert expectations for responsible and bias-resilient AI implementation. The chart below illustrates the distribution of expert scores across the evaluated factors.

The entire report is available in Appendix – M.

Figure 5: Results of Final Expert validation Session

5.5.2 Confirming Completeness

Experts also rated the overall completeness of the governance framework with a score of 3.0 with a relatively lower variability of 35%, agreeing that while the framework is largely comprehensive, some aspects such as the role of emerging norms (e.g., from CEN/CENELEC) should be explored further to strengthen the model. All the identified 6 top-level factors received high scores with acceptable variability. This suggests a strong validation for the identified relevant factors for the Trias AI Politica Governance model.

5.5.3 Qualitative Feedback and Key Insights

The validation session also yielded valuable qualitative feedback, which revealed the following:

- **Support for Trias Politica:** Experts affirmed that distributing governance responsibilities across legislative, executive, and judiciary branches strengthens accountability and reduces bias risk. As one expert noted, *“By distributing responsibilities and enforcing mutual oversight, the Trias Politica model introduces a systemic balance that is well-suited for governing AI.”*
- **Integration into Corporate Structures:** Multiple experts emphasized that embedding AI governance into enterprise governance is essential. One participant commented, *“Embedding AI governance within the enterprise’s existing governance architecture does more than improve compliance—it embeds ethical accountability into the DNA of the organization.”*
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Experts highlighted the importance of informal “shadow powers” (e.g., media, advocacy groups) in exposing hidden risks and shaping ethical oversight. One noted, *“These actors enhance system responsiveness, reveal hidden harms, and push for ethical reflection.”*

- **Ethical Principles:** Ethical frameworks from institutions like OECD and UNESCO were seen as essential, though experts expressed concerns about fragmentation among different standards.
- **EU AI Act Compliance:** Experts termed the EU AI Act as a good start that establishes a strong regulatory foundation for bias mitigation, but its effectiveness depends on how deeply its principles are embedded into real-world AI practices. One expert mentioned, “Just ticking boxed on audit form will not help to actually reduce bias. The auditors should work very closely with data scientists to understand what’s actually going on”.

5.5.4 Identified Research Gaps and Future Directions

Several constructive suggestions emerged for further research:

- **Edge Cases in Separation of Powers:** There is interest in how exceptions to the Trias Politica structure (e.g., overlapping roles) influence real-world governance outcomes.
- **Comparative Models:** Experts suggested comparing Trias Politica with alternative frameworks such as 3LM or hybrid governance models.
- **Cultural Context:** Some questioned how transferable the model is across different regions (e.g., Europe vs. East Asia) or organizational structures (centralized vs. decentralized).
- **Role of Norms and Standards:** Participants noted that alignment with formal standards (e.g., from CEN/CENELEC) could enhance regulatory compliance and legitimacy.

This validation session strengthened the credibility of the research outcomes and offered practical and theoretical inputs to refine the proposed governance framework. The feedback confirmed that the research findings are well-grounded, timely, and relevant for organisations seeking to implement bias-mitigation strategies under emerging AI regulations.

Details of the final expert validation session is available at Appendix – M

Chapter 6 - Conclusion

This research explored how a **Trias Politica–inspired governance model** can help organisations reduce bias-related risks in AI systems, particularly within the compliance context of the EU AI Act. Using a deductive thematic analysis approach, and drawing on evidence from literature, a real-world case study (Achmea), and expert engagement through Group Support System (GSS), the study identified relevant governance factors ranging from ethical principles to lifecycle oversight and organisational integration.

The research identified several gaps in current AI governance practices, including unclear role definitions, weak integration of ethical principles, and limited oversight after deployment. The proposed model addresses these issues by structuring governance into three distinct functions: **legislative (policy-making), executive (implementation), and judiciary (oversight)**. The inclusion of a “**shadow power**” layer (e.g., long-tenured employees or external influencers) emerged as a unique insight into how informal forces shape governance outcomes. This model enhances accountability and aligns with both ethical AI standards and regulatory requirements.

One of the key contributions of this study is its focus on bias not as an isolated technical issue, but as a practical entry point for building more trustworthy and accountable AI systems. Bias was used as the main entry point to reveal deeper governance needs. The model is designed for bias mitigation but can also support other AI risks, such as lack of transparency, ethical conflicts, and system failures.

Expert validation confirmed the model’s relevance and completeness. It was recognised as useful and practical, though experts suggested improvement in areas like technical standard alignment and adaptability across organisations.

6.1 IMPLICATIONS

This research provides a practical model for organisations seeking to strengthen AI governance. The main implications are:

- It offers a **structured framework** to manage AI bias and other risks using checks and balances.
- It supports integration into **existing corporate governance**, reducing duplication and improving coordination.
- It introduces a **set of controls** (policy, process, and technical) to manage bias across the AI lifecycle.
- It encourages **continuous monitoring**, not just one-time audits.
- It maps governance practices to **EU AI Act** requirements, supporting compliance.
- Although tested in a European insurance setting, the model can be adapted to other sectors and regulatory systems.

6.2 KEY CHALLENGES/GAPS IDENTIFIED

The research identified the following recurring challenges:

- **Siloed Governance:** AI responsibilities were often split across departments, leading to duplication and inefficiencies.

- **Complex Bias Thresholds:** It is difficult to set bias thresholds that work across all domains.
- **Limited Public Transparency:** There was little public disclosure of AI behaviour or audits.
- **Resource Limitations:** Bias audits, fairness tests, and red teaming require time, expertise, and budget.
- **Difficulty of Full Independence:** Strictly separating roles into distinctive branches is challenging in existing corporate structures.
- **regulatory uncertainty:** EU AI Act and related regulations continue to evolve, complicating the rollout of stable, long-term governance frameworks
- **Informal Influence “Shadow Power”:** Unofficial yet long-tenured stakeholders can exert *significant internal influence*, sidestepping or diluting formal governance processes

6.3 LOOKING AHEAD

AI governance must keep pace with rapid AI development. This research lays a foundation but should be extended. Suggested next steps include:

- **Testing and operationalising the model** in different sectors and cultural contexts by developing an and using structural artefacts.
- **Expanding the model** to cover AI risks beyond bias such as explainability gaps, adversarial vulnerabilities, or ethical conflicts.
- **Continuously aligning with evolving standards.** Further studies should consider emerging norms and guidelines from bodies like CEN/CENELEC, ISO, the EU AI Board and ISACA. At the beginning of this study, AI governance practices lack standardisation; however, during the research period significant progress was made by organizations liked ISACA. For example, ISACA released resources like “*Leveraging COBIT for Effective AI System Governance*“ (ISACA, 2025), which should be considered in future work to ensure practical relevance and alignment with best practices..

6.4 FINAL REFLECTION

In closing, this research reinforces that governing AI is not just about managing technology, it is about assigning responsibility and ensuring accountability. Bias in AI systems, as defined in this study, involves systematic errors or inconsistencies that lead to unfair or inaccurate outcomes for specific individuals, groups or contexts. This makes structured governance essential. By drawing from democratic theory of Trias Politica, the proposed model offers a principled and practical way to manage such risks. It helps organisations stay compliant with regulations like EU Ai Act, reduce harm from biased outcomes, and remain accountable to those affected by their AI systems.

Table below depicts various AI incidents mainly attributed to bias related risks across the globe.

AI incident	Incident Description	Reason	Source
COMPAS Recidivism Risk Assessment Tool	The tool was found to be biased against Black defendants, assigning higher risk scores compared to white defendants with similar criminal histories.	The training data used to develop the algorithm reflected existing <i>racial biases</i> in the criminal justice system.	(Wheeler, 2023)
Facial Recognition Systems	Facial recognition AI systems used by law enforcement agencies have shown higher error rates when identifying individuals from minority ethnic groups, particularly Black and Asian individuals.	The training data used to develop these systems lacked sufficient diversity, leading to <i>biased</i> and inaccurate results.	(Vickers, 2024)
Child Welfare Risk Assessment	AI systems used to assess the risk of child abuse or neglect have been found to exhibit racial biases, leading to higher risk scores for Black and Native American families.	The training data used reflected existing <i>biases</i> and disparities in the child welfare system.	(Whicher, D. et al, 2022)
Amazon AI-enabled recruitment tool only recommended men	Amazon's experimental AI-based hiring tool was found to be biased against women.	The training data used to develop the system reflected past hiring practices that favoured men, leading the AI to learn and perpetuate <i>gender biases</i> .	(Olavsrud, 2024)
Healthcare algorithm failed to flag Black patients	An AI diagnostic tool showed higher error rates when analysing medical scans of certain racial or ethnic groups.	The training data lacked diversity, leading the AI to learn <i>biases</i> and perform poorly on underrepresented groups	(Olavsrud, 2024)

Table 5: List of AI Incidents contributed from bias related issues

Table 6 depicts a list of standard AI policy and Frameworks

AI policy/regulation/framework Name	Description	Reference
NIST AI RMF:	This framework, developed in collaboration with the private and public sectors, is intended for voluntary use and to improve the ability to incorporate trustworthiness considerations into the design, development, use, and evaluation of AI products, services, and systems.	(NIST, 2023)
Canada publishes AI and Data Act	This AI and Data Act sets the foundation for the responsible design, development and deployment of AI systems that impact the lives of Canadians.	(ISED, 2022)
Towards Responsible AI Deployment: Policy Recommendations for the Hiroshima AI Process	This policy aims to promote safe, secure, and trustworthy AI worldwide and provide voluntary guidance for actions by organisations developing the most advanced the rules for digital technologies, including the most advanced foundation models and generative AI systems, to ensure that these are in line with “our shared democratic values”.	(The University of Tokyo, 2023)
The UK AI Ethical Framework. Guidance Ethics, Transparency and Accountability Framework for automated Decision-Making	This framework is advancing the UK AI ethical governance approach. This 7-point framework will help government departments with the safe, sustainable, and ethical use of automated or algorithmic decision-making systems. Applicable for Govt. organisations only.	(Government UK, 2023)

Table 6: List of standard AI Policy and Frameworks

Appendix - C

LITERATURE REVIEW METHODS AND SELECTION OF RELEVANT RESEARCH PAPERS

Web of Science

Figure 6: Method for selection of literature from Web of Science source

Google Scholar

Figure 7: Method of selection of literature from Google Scholar source

Figure 8: Method of selection of Literature from standard sources

Selection of most relevant documents

Figure 9: Method and criteria used for literature review and synthesis of relevant information

Table 7 captures all the research papers those are selected based on the process as described in figure 9.

Source	Research paper	Relevance	Reference
Web of Science	"A Comprehensive Review of Bias in Deep Learning Models: Methods, Impacts, and Future Directions"	Shah and Sureja's work offer a comprehensive understanding of the types, emergence points, and causes of bias in deep learning models. Their emphasis on a lifecycle approach and intersectional mitigation strategies aligns well with creating equitable and trustworthy AI systems. This analysis informs effective bias management by highlighting the importance of continuous monitoring, adaptive approaches, and ethical considerations.	(Shah & Sureja, 2024)
Web of Science	"How to be fair? A study of label and selection bias"	Favier et al.'s work offers a focused analysis of label and selection biases, revealing the critical stages and societal factors influencing AI fairness. By identifying data practices and proxy reliance as primary sources, the paper provides actionable insights for targeted, pre-emptive mitigation measures. This research supports lifecycle and socially contextualised approaches for effective bias management in AI.	(Favier, M. et al, 2023)
Web of Science	"Bias, Fairness, and Accountability with Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Algorithms"	Zhou et al.'s work offers a comprehensive understanding of bias in AI, emphasizing the need for a lifecycle approach to bias management. By identifying data and algorithmic sources and noting their presence at each stage, the paper provides a foundation for addressing bias through continuous monitoring, fairness-aware model design, and improved transparency. This approach is critical to promoting accountability and fairness in AI-driven decisions.	(Zhou, N. et al, 2022)
Web of Science	"Fairness issues, current approaches, and challenges in machine learning models"	The paper by Jui and Rivas presents a comprehensive view of bias in AI, identifying critical types, lifecycle emergence points, and root causes. It highlights the need for multi-stage interventions, transparency, and balanced fairness definitions to address biases effectively, especially in high-stakes applications.	(Rivas & Das Jui, 2024)
Google Scholar	"Toward AI Governance: Identifying Best Practices and Potential Barriers and Outcomes"	This study is highly relevant as it systematically reviews existing AI governance frameworks, focusing on how governance is implemented and who is accountable—critical for addressing bias-related risks. By categorizing governance across multiple levels, it provides valuable insights into the structural factors needed for effective AI bias mitigation.	(Papagiannidis, E. et al, 2022)
Google Scholar	"AI governance: a systematic literature review"	This study is highly relevant as it systematically reviews existing AI governance frameworks, focusing on how governance is implemented and who is accountable—critical for addressing bias-related risks. By categorizing governance across multiple levels, it provides valuable insights into the structural factors needed for effective AI bias mitigation.	(Batool, A. et al , 2025)

Google Scholar	“Catching up with AI: Pushing toward a cohesive governance framework”	This document is moderately relevant as it reviews AI governance models in the context of public administration, highlighting concerns like inequitable service delivery—closely tied to bias. While focused on the U.S., it identifies governance components that can inform frameworks aimed at mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.	(Mallinson, 2023)
Google Scholar	“Defining organisational AI governance”	This document is relevant as it defines AI governance at the organisational level and connects it to broader governance structures like IT and data governance. It supports the development of governance frameworks by translating ethical principles, such as fairness, into actionable processes—key for mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.	(Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022)
Google Scholar	“AI pitfalls and what not to do: mitigating bias in AI”	The reviewed paper highlights that bias in AI is a pervasive issue across all lifecycle stages, deeply embedded within data, algorithmic, and deployment processes. A comprehensive bias mitigation strategy must address each stage with targeted approaches, from improving data diversity to implementing robust post-deployment monitoring systems.	(Gichoya, J. W. et al, 2023)
Google Scholar	"Navigating the AI frontier: European parliamentary insights on bias and regulation, preceding the AI Act"	Chiappetta’s study reflects European policymakers' deep concerns over bias in AI, advocating for a lifecycle approach to bias detection and regulation. Emphasis is placed on the need for continuous oversight, transparency, and accountability to address technical and systemic sources of bias, ultimately guiding the development of the EU AI Act.	(Chiappetta, 2023)
Google Scholar	“Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Brief Survey of Sources, Impacts, and Mitigation Strategies”	The document is relevant as it provides clear definitions, examples, and stages for bias identification. Offers examples and mitigation strategies but lacks detailed real-world applications. Ferrara advocates for a comprehensive, multi-stage mitigation strategy to address biases in both predictive and generative AI models. This approach is essential for developing equitable AI systems.	(Ferrara, 2024)
NIST Portal	NIST Special Publication 1270: "Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence."	This publication provides a structured framework for understanding and managing bias in AI systems. By classifying biases into systemic, statistical, and human types and identifying their presence across the AI lifecycle, NIST advocates for a socio-technical approach that emphasises continuous stakeholder involvement and rigorous lifecycle-based evaluation. This document’s insights are foundational for establishing standards in AI bias management, aiming to foster trust and accountability in AI technologies.	(NIST, 2022)

NIST Portal	NIST AI 600-1: "Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework: Generative Artificial Intelligence Profile"	This framework is essential for understanding and managing bias in generative AI, offering a multi-dimensional approach to risk and bias management across the lifecycle. This structured framework emphasises the need for transparency, accountability, and continuous monitoring to mitigate harmful biases, underscoring the value of governance in fostering equitable AI systems. Highly relevant for examining AI bias, particularly in the context of generative AI systems.	(NIST, 2024)
NIST Portal	NIST AI RMF	This framework offers structured guidance on identifying and managing AI risks, emphasizing fairness, accountability, and transparency.	(NIST, 2023)
UNESCO Portal	UNESCO: "Global Toolkit on AI and the Rule of Law for the Judiciary"	These insights from the UNESCO toolkit provide a foundation for understanding the origins and types of AI bias, along with key stages in the AI lifecycle where such biases are most likely to appear. The toolkit identifies bias in AI as a crucial issue that can reinforce discrimination and inequality, particularly in sensitive areas like the judiciary. It emphasises the need for awareness and mechanisms to mitigate these biases.	(Stankovich, M. et al , 2023)
UNESCO Portal	UNESCO: "Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence"	This document provides comprehensive ethical guidelines for AI development and governance. It focuses on mitigating biases, emphasizing human rights, and ensuring inclusivity and equality. Key areas include ethical impact assessments, governance frameworks, and data policy	(UNESCO, 2023)
UNESCO Portal	UNESCO: "Missing Links in AI Governance"	The document provides definitions and stages of bias emergence, explicitly mapping them to lifecycle phases and ethical concerns. Offers policy guidelines and recommendations.	(Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023)
OECD Portal	"Explanatory memorandum on the updated OECD definition of an AI system"	Provided the updated definition of AI. Defines the lifecycle phases of AI application.	(OECD 2024)
OECD Portal	"Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence"	This is the first intergovernmental standard for AI. The Recommendation aims to foster innovation and trust in AI by promoting the responsible stewardship of trustworthy AI while ensuring respect for human rights and democratic values. Relevancy for the Trustworthy AI principles.	(OECD 2024)
OECD Portal	"OECD framework for the classification of AI systems"	The OECD framework was very relevant for the research as the AI definition and lifecycle phases were derived from it. The framework also provides vital insights into the Trustworthy AI framework and principles.	(OECD 2022)
OECD Portal	"Unsupervised bias detection tool"	The article explains about an unsupervised bias detection tool aims to discover complex and hidden forms of bias. The tool is specifically geared towards detecting unforeseen forms of bias and higher-dimensional forms of bias. The tool is being used in audit processes. This is high relevance to our research as a proven mechanism of algorithmic bias detection.	(OECD, 2023)

Received from Prof. Mulder	“While Paper on AI Governance”	This document has limited relevance to the research sub-question. While it touches on the importance of governance for ethical AI deployment, it lacks specific analysis of how biases arise in AI systems or what concrete governance factors are needed to mitigate them effectively. It is more of a high-level thought leadership piece than a focused academic or empirical study.	(Australian Government, 2024)
Obtained during Initial research and literature study	“Towards Responsible AI Deployment, Policy Recommendations for the Hiroshima AI Process”	This document is relevant as it emphasises the need for comprehensive AI governance involving all stakeholders, with a focus on transparency and equity, key principles for mitigating bias-related risks. While it doesn’t detail specific bias types, it highlights the structural and societal considerations necessary for designing effective governance frameworks.	(Institute for Future Initiatives 2023)

Table 7: Most relevant Research Papers for Literature review

ADDITIONAL DETAILS FOR SECTION 2.2

Categories of Bias as defined by NIST Special Publication 1270

Figure 10: Categories of Bias as defined by NIST Special Publication (Schwartz, R. et al , 2022, p. 8)

SYNTHESIS OF BISE CATEGORIES, TYPES, SOURCE AND ROOT CAUSE

During the literature review, numerous types of bias in AI systems were identified, highlighting the need for a structured and comprehensive classification. To facilitate clarity and provide a practical reference, a consolidated catalogue was developed to summarise each bias type alongside its associated factors. This classification was guided by an analysis of bias origins, the stages of the AI lifecycle at which they manifest, their underlying mechanisms, and their impact pathways. To ensure logical consistency and avoid overlap, the classification process employed the MECE (Mutually Exclusive, Collectively Exhaustive) framework, enabling a systematic synthesis of the biases into a coherent and accessible scheme.

Mutual Exclusivity: By clearly delineating between data, model, user interaction, societal, external, and generative biases, we create categories with minimal overlap. Each category has a specific, well-defined source and context within the AI lifecycle.

Collective Exhaustiveness: These refined categories cover most of the major sources and lifecycle stages of bias in AI systems, including new considerations for external dependencies and the unique challenges of generative models. This approach comprehensively addresses both internal and external factors, from data collection to deployment and content generation. We identified 6 major bias categories

1. **Data-Related Bias:** Biases arising from issues within the dataset, such as sampling, historical biases, or labelling inaccuracies. Addressing Data-Related Bias typically involves technical interventions, such as adjusting sampling strategies, improving data labelling accuracy, or balancing datasets. These are often well-defined solutions that data scientists can implement directly. Data-Related Bias is primarily about "how" the data is collected or labelled.
2. **Model Design and Algorithmic Bias:** Biases stemming from design and technical choices made during model architecture and optimisation where certain model choices inadvertently favour specific outcomes or groups over others.
3. **Societal and Cultural Bias:** Biases that reflect societal stereotypes, systemic inequalities, and cultural norms, embedded in data or model. Addressing Societal and Cultural Bias requires broader, often ethical considerations and may involve re-evaluating the values embedded in data. For example, simply balancing data may not address societal biases if the underlying data reflects harmful stereotypes. Addressing this bias may require interventions like bias detection algorithms, diverse teams for data annotation, and oversight bodies to review data for social fairness. These biases reflect "what" the data inherently represents in society and are more challenging to correct without a broader social intervention.
4. **External Dependency Bias:** Biases introduced through reliance on third-party data, pre-trained models, or other external components.
5. **Deployment and Interaction Bias:** Biases that emerge through user interaction post-deployment, including feedback loops and adaptive user interactions.
6. **Generative Model Bias:** Biases specific to generative AI models, especially those related to content generation, such as confabulation or harmful stereotypes.

The table 8 presents a detailed classification of six distinct categories of bias, assigning each bias type to its respective category. It includes descriptions for both the categories and individual bias types to enhance understanding. Additionally, the table identifies the lifecycle stage where each bias emerges, along with its source and root cause.

No.	Bias Category	Bias Types	Bias Type Description	Lifecycle Stage	Source	Root Cause
1	Data-Related Bias	Sampling Bias	Occurs when the data sample does not represent the overall population, leading to biased outputs. It's a technical issue.	Data Collection	Non-representative data samples	Imbalanced datasets with under/over-represented groups
		Historical Bias	Reflects past societal inequalities within the dataset, causing certain biases to persist over time.	Data Collection	Training data reflecting historical inequities	Embedded societal biases in historical data
		Measurement Bias	Inaccuracies in data collection or measurement processes, which can lead to biased results.	Data Collection	Data collection inconsistencies	Inaccurate or inconsistent measurement methodologies
		Label Bias	Bias introduced by using proxy labels that do not accurately reflect the target concept.	Data Labelling	Proxies used in labelling that do not match target	Use of inappropriate proxy labels for complex concepts
		Temporal Bias	Arises from outdated data that fails to represent current trends	Data Preparation	Stale data	Lack of timely updates to datasets.
		Spatial Bias	Results from geographic underrepresentation.	Data Collection	Geographic underrepresentation	Unequal sampling from diverse regions.
2	Model Design and Algorithmic Bias	Model Design Bias	Bias that arises from decisions made during model design which favour certain groups or outcomes.	Model Design	Model design choices and optimisation criteria	Model choices that unintentionally favour certain groups
		Optimisation Bias	Occurs when optimisation criteria prioritise certain results over fairness considerations.	Model Training	Prioritisation of certain results during optimisation	Optimisation metrics favouring accuracy over fairness
		Feature Selection Bias	Bias introduced when selected features act as indirect indicators of protected attributes, causing unfair outcomes.	Feature Engineering	Indirect features linked to protected attributes	Feature selection unintentionally acting as proxies
3	Societal and Cultural Bias	Societal/Cultural Bias	Bias from societal stereotypes embedded in data, reflecting broader social prejudices.	Data Collection	Cultural norms and societal stereotypes in data	Societal and cultural prejudices reflected in datasets
		Structural Bias	Bias arising from broader societal or structural inequalities that influence the AI system.	Data Collection	Socio-economic inequalities in data sources	Structural inequalities embedded in socio-economic data
		Association Bias	Reflects and perpetuates existing societal stereotypes, such as associating specific genders with certain professions.	Data Collection	Data associations based on social stereotypes	Data associations reinforcing harmful stereotypes

4	External Dependency Bias	Third-party Data/Component Bias	Bias introduced by external data sources or components that the AI system depends on, transferring bias from external sources.	Data Integration	External data sources and third-party models	Reliance on third-party data without bias controls
5	Deployment and Interaction Bias	Feedback Loop Bias	Emerges when feedback from users reinforces initial biases, leading to a self-reinforcing cycle.	User Interaction	User feedback loops in adaptive systems	Feedback creating self-reinforcing bias cycles
		Adaptive Bias	Occurs in adaptive models that adjust to user input, potentially amplifying existing biases.	User Interaction	User behaviour adaptation	Model adjustments based on biased user inputs
		Interaction Bias	Bias that stems from user interactions which affect system outputs over time.	User Interaction	Repeated user interactions influencing model outputs	Accumulation of biases through continued user interactions
6	Generative Model Bias	Confabulation	Specific to generative AI, where the model produces confidently erroneous outputs that may be biased.	Content Generation	Generative model structures producing incorrect information	Overconfidence in generative outputs leading to errors
		Harmful Bias	Harmful stereotypes or inaccuracies embedded in AI-generated content, often seen in generative AI models.	Content Generation	Harmful stereotypes in data influencing content generation	Training data embedding stereotypes into content generation

Table 8: Bias Classification

Note: In the column “Lifecycle Stage”, the blue colour represents “Build phase” and the green colour represents the “Use Phase” of the AI system as per the OECD definition of phases of AI System.

AI governance as part of corporate governance

Figure 11: AI governance as part of corporate governance (Mäntyrnäki, M. et al, 2022, p. 605)

AI RMF depicting Governance to be a cross-cutting function

Figure 12: AI RMF depicting Governance to be a cross-cutting function to inform and be infused throughout the other three functions (NIST, 2023, p. 20).

ADDITIONAL DETAILS FOR SECTION 2.4

This section contains more details about risk-based classification, EU AI Act Bias mitigation and Compliance Requirements for AI systems of all risk levels (European Commission, 2024).

AI Risk Category	Bias-Related Risks	Mitigations	Compliance Requirements
Unacceptable Risk	AI systems that: Exploit vulnerabilities (age, disability, socio-economic status) Engage in social scoring Infer emotions in workplace/education Scrape facial data from public sources Such systems deepen structural bias, erode autonomy, and reinforce exclusion.	Inferring emotions for medical or safety reasons is allowed. RBI is except when: Searching for missing persons, abduction victims, or people being human trafficked or sexually exploited. Preventing substantial and imminent threat to life, or foreseeable terrorist attack. Identifying suspects in serious crimes. (Art. 5)	The usage of it is only allowed when not using the tool causes considerable harm. Before deploying the following measurements should be done: <ul style="list-style-type: none">– Fundamental rights impact assessment– Registry in the EU database– Obtaining of authorisation from a judicial authority or independent administrative authority. (Art. 5)
High-Risk AI Systems	Bias arises from: Historical discrimination in training data Unbalanced or non-representative datasets Feedback loops reinforcing bias Opaque? decision-making Limited human oversight Impacts key rights (non-discrimination, privacy, fair treatment).	Art. 9 Risk management system Art. 10 Data and data governance Art. 11 Technical documentation Art. 12 Record-keeping Art. 13 Transparency and provision of information to deployers Art. 14 Human oversight Art. 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity	Providers must: Conduct conformity assessments Maintain technical documentation Ensure traceability and logs Address bias explicitly in design Allow human intervention and contestability Deployers (e.g., in healthcare, education, law enforcement) must complete Fundamental Rights Impact Assessments (FRIA).

<p>Limited-Risk AI Systems</p>	<p>May still embed subtle bias via: Chatbots giving misleading responses Emotion recognition misinterpreting users Bias risks are softer but can still lead to discrimination or psychological harm.</p>	<p>Transparency is emphasized (Art. 52): users must be informed they are interacting with AI. Recital 81 underscores that transparency helps mitigate manipulation and bias.</p>	<p>Disclose AI interaction to users Provide opt-outs where feasible Ensure systems do not exploit users deceptively</p>
<p>Minimal/No-Risk AI Systems</p>	<p>Includes general productivity tools (e.g., spam filters, autocomplete) with low immediate bias impact, but cumulative harms may arise.</p>	<p>No mandatory provisions. However, the Act encourages adoption of codes of conduct aligned with ethical AI principles (Recital 27): fairness, inclusiveness, and avoidance of harm.</p>	<p>Voluntary measures: Ethical guidelines adoption Internal audits for fairness Stakeholder engagement</p>

Table 9: EU AI Act Bias mitigation and Compliance Requirements

Appendix - E

Table 10 below captures details of the applicable governance controls which are a combination of policy, process and technical measures relevant to mitigate or prevent bias in AI systems as synthesised during the literature review.

	Governance Mechanism	Mechanism Type	Applicable Phase(s)	Short Description
1	Ethical Impact Assessments	Policy / Process	Build & Use	Frameworks to assess ethical implications, manage risks, and align AI with societal and organisational values (UNESCO, 2023).
2	Data Governance Policies	Policy	Build	Ensures dataset quality, representativeness, and integrity to avert skewed or historic inequalities (Ferrara, 2024).
3	Bias Audits and Reviews	Process	Build	Independent and systematic evaluations to identify and address biases in datasets and models (NIST, 2023).
4	Transparency Protocols	Policy / Process	Build & Use	Mechanisms for documenting and communicating model development, data lineage, and assumptions to ensure accountability (NIST, 2024) .
5	Human Oversight Mechanisms	Process	Build & Use	Systems allowing human intervention to ensure accountability in decision-making processes (Australian Government, 2024).
6	Fairness-by-Design Principles	Policy / Process	Build	Embedding fairness and inclusivity into the AI design process to prevent systemic inequalities (Favier, M. et al, 2023).
7	Stakeholder Engagement	Process	Build	Inclusion of diverse and marginalised communities in governance processes to address biases (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023).
8	Continuous Monitoring & Collaboration	Process / Technical	Use	Mechanisms for ongoing evaluation, user feedback loops, and real-time collaboration to address emergent risks (NIST, 2023).
9	Risk Management Frameworks	Policy / Process	Build & Use	Continuous assessment of risks, alignment of optimisation goals with ethical principles, and mitigation strategies (NIST, 2023) .
10	Third-party Data Vetting	Policy / Technical	Build	Guidelines to vet external data sources for quality, integrity, and relevance to reduce potential biases (Ferrara, 2024).
11	Education and Training Programs	Process / Technical	Build & Use	Initiatives to train developers, stakeholders, and end-users on AI ethics, bias mitigation, and responsible AI practices (UNESCO, 2023).
12	Incentives for Inclusive Practices	Policy	Build	Economic or regulatory incentives to adopt inclusive design, data practices, and processes in AI development (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023).

Table 10: List of governance controls to mitigate bias in AI systems

Appendix – F

PRELIMINARY CASE STUDY

Information Supported Decision/Short Stay VISA process of Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs

Context: Validation assumptions to finalise the research question and focus on applying the Principles Trias Politica to reduce bias in AI systems.

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1 Introduction: Background purpose and Context of the Case Study

During the first stages of our master's thesis at AMS under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Bart van Gils and Prof. Dr. Hans Mulder, we received the opportunity to have introduced us to *Mr. Dion Kotteman, Mr. Michel Mulders* and *Mr. Jeroen Simons* partners of Grey Matter Matters (GMM). GMM is a consultancy firm for administrative and digital issues for the Dutch government. GMM advocates the design of the management and control of AI for every public or private law organisation. Therefore, GMM bundled their knowledge and experience in functional/technical operation of AI, functioning of organisations, process design, human position, scientific developments, auditing, and legal context into a program design, analysis- and implementation approach.

2 OBJECTIVES

In this stage of our research approach, we wanted to validate our assumptions to finalise the construct of our RQ and to gather expertise and to explore the feasibility of an AI governance framework. We will focus on applying the Trias Politica model to reduce bias in AI systems, using the Information Supported Decision/Short Stay Visa (ISD/SSV) process implemented by the Dutch Ministry of Foreign affairs (MFA) as a case study. The discussion will focus on identifying key elements of an AI governance framework inspired by the Trias Politica model. We aim to explore how this model can be adapted to address bias-related risks during the adoption of AI systems, particularly within the context of the EU AI Act.

3 RESEARCH APPROACH

The study involved preliminary exploration and collaboration with GMM's AI governance experts. We performed the following actions.

- **Initial Exploration:** Engaging with GMM's AI governance experts.
- **Document Analysis:** Reviewing ISD/SSV process, report of the Dutch Ministry of Foreign affairs and external research report of SigmaRed Technologies.
- **Web Search:** Gathering inputs from various literature as part of our initial research activity and utilizing vital relevant insights to guide this case study.

- **Framework Validation & Workshop:** Presenting research findings to GMM's AI governance experts. And obtaining key information through interview questions and a brainstorm session. We have conducted the workshop with Meeting Wizard tool. The tool works as a Group support system and facilitates expert sessions and relevant data capturing in a very efficient and structured way which complements to scientific research methodology.
- **Qualitative Analysis:** Capturing insights from documents analysis and additional web search4 AI SYSTEM UNDER STUDY - ISD/SSV

4.1 OVERVIEW OF ISD/SSV PROCESS

The MFA is responsible for handling and assessing SSV applications for entry into the Netherlands. Such a visa allows a short stay within the Schengen countries. In this way, MFA fulfils a task in the field of admission (regular) for the migration chain. Knowledge-intensive and qualitative decision-making in a SSV application is necessary and therefore the principles of effective service delivery by MFA.

Bron: NL Buiza-team

Figure 13; Overview of Information Supported Decision Making Process of MFA.

Information Supported Decision Making Process

1. Application => NVIS (Nieuwe Visum Informatie Systeem) => BAO (Buitenlands Zaken Analyse Omgeving)
2. BAO = Compare ((applicant +/- sponsor +/- employer) +/- profiles) => Track
3. Track (Fast, Regular, Intensive) => NVIS
4. NVIS => Assessment (assessment + VISA application + Local Context)
5. Decision => Ground for refusal (Yes/No)

By handling SSV applications objectively, carefully, and efficiently, tourism, family visits, and economic diplomacy are promoted, and MFA contributes to the exercise of tasks of the

migration chain and thus to safety in the Netherlands. Before a SSV can be issued, MFA must assess whether all EU-prescribed conditions are met. Due to the considerable number of applications, but also to perform this task objectively, carefully, and efficiently, MFA uses a data analysis-supported working method. This is called Information Supported Decision Making (ISD).

The decision on the visa application is always made by the competent officer based on compliance with the conditions as set out in the Visa Code. The BAO has a supporting role in this. With the help of the BAO, part of the information available to the decision-making employees is digitised, and a supporting advice is given about the appropriate intensity of the file investigation: the so-called ‘tracks. This allows decisions to be made more efficiently, and potentially subjective impressions in the decision-making process are avoided as much as possible. It is the decision-making employee who decides the appropriate intensity of the file investigation based on the file.

The final decision to grant or reject a SSV application is made by the authorised decision-making employee based on the entire file and the conditions laid down in the Visa Code. The track in which the application is classified has no influence on this. There is therefore no link between the tracks resulting from the BAO (and thus the BAO process) and the final decision made by the decision-making employee on the SSV application. The tracks from the BAO are therefore never used as a basis for a decision.

So far, MFA has assumed that the use of the BAO, and particularly the tracks resulting from the BAO, does not constitute automated individual decision-making as referred to in Article 22, section 1, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). On December 7, 2023, the Court of Justice of the European Union further clarified the prohibition of automated individual decision-making in the so-called SCHUFA ruling.

4.2 BAO Working Method

The BAO checks in two separate ways to what extent anything is known about the application:

1. **Comparison:** It is checked whether there is a match with the information from the visa application with information present in the BAO. This can be information that MFA itself has collected from (previous) visa applications or information obtained from chain partners.
2. **Profiles:** MFA uses so-called profiles in the BAO. These are profiles drawn up based on information that MFA itself has available and data from the sources of chain partners. The relevance of profiles is periodically evaluated; if there is insufficient or no relevance over time, the profile is removed.

Potential matches in the BAO are weighed by assigning a score. This score determines which track is shared with to the decision-making employee: fast, regular, or intensive.

If data is available that relates to the applicant, employer, and/or sponsor, these always weigh more heavily in the calculation of the score than a profile in which the applicant falls. This final score determines the track and therefore the recommended intensity of a file investigation. The determined track is visible to the decision-making employee in the NVIS. The track is only a recommendation. The decision-making employee independently decides based on the information in the file what intensity of the file investigation is appropriate.

4.3 Tracks Resulting from the BAO

As explained in above section, a track is assigned to a SSV application based on a weighting through scores by the BAO. It must therefore be assessed whether assigning these tracks constitutes automated individual decision-making, based on the cumulative conditions. It is already emphasised that the working method of the BAO, and thus the tracks, is separate from the final decision made by the decision-making employee on a SSV application. This is also further explained at point three below. Moreover, the track is only a recommendation to the decision-making employee regarding the intensity of the file investigation.

- There is a decision. As evidenced by the SCHUFA ruling, the Court gives a broad scope to the concept of a decision. It can involve various actions that affect individuals in a certain way, including a solvency calculation. In this light, a weighting through scores to assess the intensity of a SSV file can also be considered a decision. Just as in the solvency calculation, an assessment is made based on a mathematical evaluation. In the case of the BAO, this is an assessment of the intensity with which the file should be overseen (in which track). The track can thus be considered a decision, and the first condition is met.
- The decision must be ‘based solely on automated processing, including profiling.’ The assignment of these scores, and the final weighting, takes place automatically in the BAO. An algorithm is used for this. This algorithm operates based on a decision tree with simple ‘if-then’ rules.
- The decision must have ‘legal effects’ concerning the data subject or similarly significantly affect him or her. A track, and therefore the decision, only provides an assessment of the intensity with which the file should be managed. The track is, as mentioned, separate from the decision on a SSV application. A track also has no (direct) influence on the final decision on a SSV application. A track is merely a recommendation for the decision-making employee regarding the intensity of the file. It supports the employee in making a better (time) estimate for managing the SSV application.

The decision whether a SSV application is granted or not does not depend on the track resulting from the BAO. On the contrary, it entirely depends on the judgment of the decision-making employee based on the file investigation. A track is only supportive for the decision-making employee to assess the intensity of a file investigation.

Each SSV application is treated in the same way: if the decision-making employee deems it necessary to request more information or to further check documents, this is possible. It is not the case that a fast track means that no investigation of the file takes place by the decision-making employee. Each SSV application file is manually investigated, regardless of the assigned track. The track only indicates a recommended intensity of that investigation.

Moreover, for example, conducting an extra interview or further investigating documents does not aim to refuse the SSV application. The goal is to request missing necessary information from the applicant. This allows for an assessment based on all relevant information whether the applicant meets the conditions for an SSV.

A fast track does not mean that a SSV application is granted, and an intensive track does not mean that an application is refused. MFA closely monitors this. Dashboards are used for this, tracking the percentage of approvals and rejections of SSV applications linked to the three possible tracks. The dashboards show that rejection rates for the fast track remain (reasonably) stable and that the rejection rate for the intensive track has decreased since 2017 - from 56% to about 33% of the total number of SSV applications or within the intensive track. This indicates that an intensive track does not standardly lead to a refusal.

This is also not the goal of the BAO. An application is only honoured when it meets the conditions set by the Visa Code, regardless of the track advised by the BAO. Decision-making employees are also instructed that the tracks only give an estimate of the intensity with which the file should be managed, and that the final intensity is at the decision-making employee's discretion.

5 Presences of BIAS in ISD/SSV process

5.1 Different types of BIAS

Bias can occur in principle in all steps in the ISD/SSV process. Specific to the BAO, bias can enter.

- into the data sources used by the BAO, e.g. in the form of historical bias.
- during the modelling and training of the BAO, e.g. in the form of confirmation bias.
- because of the BAO being put into use, e.g. in the form of feedback bias.
- in the daily use of the BAO by employees, e.g. in the form of automation bias.

5.2 Definitions

- **Bias:** Systematic deviation between model results and the actual values for a specific group. For example, if there is a systematic underestimation or overestimation of the risk profile for a specific group, the model contains a bias in favour of or against this group.
- **Discrimination:** Differences in treatment of certain persons in comparable cases, directly or indirectly based on protected personal characteristics.
- **Fairness:** Desired form and degree of equal treatment of or model results for individuals or groups based on characteristics considered relevant.

5.3 Sources and manifestations of BIAS

In algorithm-supported decision-making processes, various sources of bias can play a role in all process steps. There are many different, but similar typologies of bias. Regarding algorithm-supported decision-making processes such as the ISD/SSV, potential sources of bias can be divided into four categories.

- **Bias in data:** During the training of algorithms or determining decision rules, the used data can be a source of much bias. The risk of bias is particularly high when the data comes from external sources, outdated data, incomplete data, or data collected for another purpose.
- **Bias in modelling:** During the development of an algorithm, different implicit and explicit choices are made that can lead to bias. For example, consider the choice of the methodology to be used, the pre-processing of the data, the chosen values for model parameters, the selection of evaluation criteria, etc.
- **Bias because of the implementation of a system:** Once a system has been put into production, the system itself can unintentionally become a source of bias.
- **Bias in daily use by employees:** Bias can occur when employees use the system, particularly because of incorrect interpretation and/or use of model results.

5.4 Possible BIAS injection during creation and use of profiles?

Based on research results, it can be concluded that there are:

- considered bias discrepancies based on nationality.
- limited bias discrepancies based on gender and.
- no substantial bias discrepancies based on age.

Below figure depicts three separate stages where things may go wrong, and we need to validate the output.

Figure 14: Depiction of ISD/SSV System as per OECD AI Systems - Post deployment stage

5.5 What are the main conclusions regarding observed BIAS?

The BAO was created with the intention to make the decision-making process for SSV applications more objective and efficient. The alternative option of not using a BAO-like model is suitable for capturing, for example, confirmation bias at the individual level of decision-makers. However, the BAO can potentially introduce new forms of bias and even reinforce existing bias. It should be clear that it is impossible to completely prevent every form of bias. It is therefore important to exclude the unfavourable impact of the BAO as completely as possible.

6 Alignments with EU AI Act

Based on the information in chapter 4, we conclude that the BAO falls under the category of AI systems. Hence it is subjected to EU AI act: AI systems are always considered **high-risk** if it **profiles individuals**, i.e. **automated processing of personal data** to assess various aspects of a person's life, such as work performance, economic situation, health, preferences, interests, reliability, behaviour, location or movement.

As per Annex III, point 7c: "AI systems intended to be used by or on behalf of competent public authorities or by Union institutions, bodies, offices or agencies to assist competent public authorities for the examination of applications for asylum, visa or residence permits and for

associated complaints with regard to the eligibility of the natural persons applying for a status, including related assessments of the reliability of evidence;”

Based on the above criteria, we concluded that the BAO system falls under high-risk category as defined by EU AI act.

7. Classification of BAO with Trias Politica-based governance.

As per Trias political model, the separation of power may fall under the following categories.

Legislative Branch: This branch is responsible for making laws. The primary goal of the legislative branch is to represent the will of the people and to create laws that reflect the needs and values of society.

In current context, there must be a governing body that defines the policies, compliance, and rules for the AI system. This governing body process must inherit all the applicable Laws, policies, and rules.

Executive Branch: This branch is tasked with enforcing and administering the laws passed by the legislative branch. The executive branch also includes various government agencies and departments that conduct the day-to-day operations of the government.

In current context, the BAO AI system plays the role of the executive in terms of executing the defined laws, policies, rules and producing output.

Judicial Branch: This branch interprets the laws and ensures they are applied fairly and consistently. The judiciary acts as a safeguard against abuses of power by the other branches.

In current context, to comply to define laws and policies, there must be a governing body that puts guardrails on the output of the system. If we consider the current scenario, we may need guardrails on multiple stages.

1. AI output from the BAO model
2. Possible human/personal bias on interpreting the Output during analysis by the Visa officer.
3. And finally, the overall decision

8. Roundtable discussion: mitigating BIAS related risks in AI adaptation

After a short introduction and presentation of the objectives and scope a preliminary discussion about mitigating bias related risks in AI adaptation was conducted followed by a voting session on several propositions and an evaluation of the outcomes of the answers.

Afterwards, some of them were used during the discussion with the partners of GMM. In Appendix – K, more information can be found about this discussion.

9. Conclusion

See Appendix – K, Validation of Assumption by gathering Expert’s insights.

10. Reference documents

Open source documents (Tweede Kamer, 2024)

- Bias toetsing_Kort Verblijf Visa_aanvragen
- Bias experiment invloed labels op beslissing

Appendix – G

CASE STUDY, AI IMPLEMENTATION AT ACHMEA

Context: AI Governance for Bias Mitigation in Organizations and application of Principles of Trias Politica – The Case of MASHA at Achmea

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INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND PURPOSE AND CONTEXT OF THE CASE STUDY

In accordance with our research approach, we wanted to perform a case study with one of the organizations who has successfully implemented AI systems. The goal was to obtain practical insights and best practices directly from the organizations who are in the forefront of innovation with successful AI implementations. We got an opportunity when our promotor *Prof. Hans Mulder* introduced us to *Mr. Rikkert van Capelleveen*, Sr. Manager Business data and AI at Achmea, S&I group. Achmea Holding N.V. is one of the largest suppliers of financial services in the Netherlands. During his presentation as a guest lecture at AMS, *Mr. Capelleveen* was explaining how Achmea is driving innovation and gaining competitive advantage in the industry with various successful AI implementations. As a research team, we further engaged with *Mr. Capelleveen* to explore options for a case study for our research project. Subsequently, we collaborated with multiple internal teams at Achmea to determine an appropriate AI implementation suitable for inclusion in the case study. With the support from *Mr. Arjan Juurlink*, Head of CDO and his team of S&I group within Achmea, we found a system called MASHA (Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm) to be part of further research. We have obtained several relevant documentations to understand the MASHA system, operational procedures and processes, AI governance framework. Finally, we have conducted a knowledge workshop with experts and staff members of the AI governance team to confirm our findings and obtain vital insights for our research.

2.1 Objective

The objective was to conduct a case study aimed at gathering insights on finding the causes, sources, and mitigation strategies of bias within key AI initiatives. Additionally, to analyse these insights to identify the critical components of an AI governance framework, grounded in

the Trias Politica model and aligned with the EU AI Act, to mitigate bias-related risks during the adoption of AI in organizations.

By examining MASHA, a Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm developed by Achmea for medical acceptance in term life insurance, this case study aims to:

- Understand AI governance mechanisms applied to bias mitigation within Achmea's operational framework.
- Validate AI governance best practices through expert engagement, document analysis, and structured workshops.
- Evaluate how defined governance structures, policy-driven process and technical governance practices align with Trias Politica principles (Legislative, Executive, Judicial governance).
- In the context of EU AI Act., MASHA falls under the high-risk AI system category. It perfectly matches the requirement for our research and the aim is to understand organizational readiness to address the compliance requirements down under.

2.2 Research Approach

The study involved preliminary exploration and collaboration with Achmea's AI and innovation team. After outlining our case, purpose and objective of this engagement, we were referred to the data governance team, which is also responsible for AI governance within Achmea. We performed the following actions

8. **Initial Exploration:** Engaging with Achmea's AI & Innovation Team.
9. **Document Analysis:** Reviewing Achmea's AI governance policies and ethical framework.
10. **Literature Review:** Gathering inputs from the broader literature review activity as part of our research and utilizing vital relevant insights to guide this case study and to further validate theoretical findings with practical implementation.
11. **Expert interviews and workshop-based data collection:** Presenting research findings to Achmea's AI governance team. And obtaining key information through interview questions, brainstorming sessions. We have conducted the workshop with Meeting Wizard tool. The tool works as a Group support system and facilitates expert sessions and relevant data capturing in a very efficient and structured way which complements to scientific research methodology.
12. **Qualitative Analysis:** Capturing insights from documents analysis, focused group workshop and expert discussions and performing a qualitative analysis on the findings.
13. **Review:** Details of the findings post qualitative analysis were shared with Achmea to fact check and validate our understand on the AI system, organizational structure, processes, best practices, technical mitigation techniques and tools.
14. **Result Output:** The final output of the case study was produced after integrating the feedback received from Achmea and subsequent confirmation on the fact check.

Figure 15 on the next page, illustrates the research approach and methods used for the case study conducted at Achmea.

Figure 15: Illustrates research approach and methods for this case study

AI SYSTEM UNDER STUDY - MASHA

MASHA (Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm)– AI Governance in Medical Acceptance for Insurance

3.1 Overview of MASHA

MASHA is an AI-powered decision-support system designed to automate the medical acceptance process for term life insurance at Achmea.

MASHA stands for Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm. It is utilized in the application process for term life insurance. A term life insurance policy at Achmea pays out a predetermined amount, if the insured passes away before the policy end date. Before ensuring a client, Achmea first assess whether the risk of premature death is too high. In cases of high risk, the client may be offered insurance at an increased premium (approximately 5% of applications) or declined (approximately 2%).

Figure 16 on the next page illustrates an overview of MASHA AI system.

Figure 16: Overview of the MASHA AI system with reference to OECD AI Model

3.1.1 The medical acceptance process works as follows:

1. The applicant always first fills out a digital health declaration.
2. These medical details (excluding name, address, or contact information) are sent in real-time to ‘MASHA’.
3. MASHA returns a score between 0 and 1 to the medical system MOS (Medisch Oproep System).
4. MOS uses a ‘threshold value’: the minimum score required for automatic acceptance by the system.
 - If the score is below this threshold value, the case is forwarded to a staff member for manual review.
 - If the score exceeds this threshold value and no ‘business rules’ (e.g., medical examination required for coverage above a specified amount) are triggered, the applicant is immediately informed of medical approval. The customer then receives the policy within minutes.

3.1.2 Key business Advantages of MASHA

- With MASHA, 65% of customers receive instant approval upon completing the health declaration, enabling swift policy issuance and a better customer experience.
- MASHA exclusively supports positive decisions. Customers are not directly charged higher premiums or declined. Cases flagged by MASHA’s inputs further managed by staff, often with additional medical information, ensuring a personal approach with human in loop.

3.2 Key Features & Ethical Safeguards

3.2.1 Ethical Consideration

Ethics has always been a central theme in medical acceptance for term life insurance. For instance, ensuring insurability for chronically ill individuals and keeping a human-centred approach are key values. This was no different during the development of MASHA in 2018. From the start, *ethical impact assessments* were conducted with external (European) guidelines. Achmea actively collaborated with the HLEG Trustworthy AI initiative and contributed to the self-regulation framework, “Ethisch Kader Datagedreven Besluitvorming” (Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making), for the Dutch insurance sector. During development of MASHA, proactive efforts were made to address *discrimination*, including *identifying hidden biases* in training data. Ensuring the *explainability* of the model and its individual results has

always been a strict requirement. To support this, Achmea had included *external evaluation results* based on the “Ethisch Kader Datagedreven Besluitvorming”.

3.2.2 Suppliers

The model was developed in-house, meaning no external suppliers were involved in creating MASHA. Regular, generic IT components, including cloud-based systems, are utilized within the acceptance workflow.

3.2.3 Data Use

Medical data processed by MASHA is subject to the highest levels of security and privacy standards. These processes follow standard IT guidelines and are regularly audited. Standard procedures, such as *Data Protection Impact Assessments* (DPIAs) and *Business Impact Analyses* (BIAs), have been followed. During model training, customer personal information, such as names and addresses, are excluded. Even case numbers are pseudonymized. The model undergoes *periodic validation* by medical specialists and Achmea’s Model Management team.

3.2.4 Quality Control

Medical evaluations conducted by both specialists and MASHA, undergo quality checks through *random sampling*. These checks ensure compliance with legal and regulatory requirements, internal policies, guidelines, work instructions, and agreements.

3.2.5 Bias Mitigation Strategies Implemented by Achmea

- *Ethical Frameworks*: Collaborated with HLEG Trustworthy AI and adopted the "Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making" to address bias risks.
- *Human Oversight*: Prevents negative decisions by the algorithm alone.
- *Data Validation*: Uses pseudonymized and regularly audited data, with ongoing assessments for fairness and inclusivity.
- *Continuous Monitoring*: Periodic evaluations and random quality checks help ensure compliance with ethical and regulatory standards.

3.2.6 Key Takeaways

- **Human-in-the-Loop Approach**: AI automates only positive decisions while human validation is required for negative outcomes.
- **Addressing compliance requirements**: MASHA follows data protection and General Data Protection Regulation GDPR compliance with strict security and privacy protocols by excluding PII and pseudonymized case numbers from model training and validation process.
- **Bias Mitigation Strategies**: Includes continuous fairness testing, impact assessments, and external ethical evaluations.
- **MASHA demonstrates how AI can balance automation with ethical and human-centered oversight**, serving as a model for other organizations in highly regulated industries.

AI GOVERNANCE IMPLEMENTATION AT ACHMEA

Achmea’s vision for AI started with AI should be legally compliant, ethically responsible, and technically robust. Through proactive measures, Achmea aims to ensure AI serves customers, aligns with societal values, and adheres to high standards of accountability and transparency. To apply AI in a safe, controlled and ethical way Achmea followed a human centric approach with AI as an “co-pilot” rather than an “auto pilot”. Furthermore, legal framework was considered as a minimum for business operations with an ambition to be at the forefront of the ethical application of AI. At Achmea, EEC and UNESCO global AI principles have been incorporated into the ethical framework for Data-Driven working which already applies to their

existing models. The framework includes measures like the "Ethical Wheel," which ensures customer interests are safeguarded by weighing how Achmea utilizes available technological possibilities. This framework, developed by the Dutch Association of Insurers, applies to all financial and non-financial models and will integrate requirements from the upcoming AI Act (2026).

4.1 Key AI Principles Adapted by Achmea

Achmea incorporates UNESCO principles “Human Rights to AI” and EEC principles ‘Responsible AI’ to its ethical and trustworthy AI framework with the following principles:

1. **Societal and environmental Well-Being:** Ensuring sustainability and minimizing negative impacts.
2. **Human agency and Oversight:** Systems should support human autonomy and decision-making.
3. **Privacy & Data Governance:** Protecting sensitive information with strict safeguards.
4. **Technical Robustness & Safety:** Models must be reliable, secure, and validated against attacks.
5. **Awareness & Literacy:** To ensure public awareness of AI and data should be promoted through open & accessible education.
6. **Accountability:** Ensuring accountability including involved technology partners by defining ownership and liability rules.
7. **Diversity, Non-Discrimination & Fairness:** Avoiding biases and ensuring fair treatment.
8. **Transparency & Explainability:** Models must clearly explain outputs and decisions.

4.2 Accountability & Oversight Measures

In the operational level, it was observed that the Governance mechanisms and the AI implementation has been driven by the adhered AI principles. The preproduction checklist is developed using the principles as the top-level categories, under which several compliance questions were mapped.

Achmea has developed multiple work packets for its AI implementation framework. These work packets are derived from the AI principles. Following are the identified work packets which are integrated with business and IT operations.

- *Legal frameworks* and internal policies are reconciled, with necessary updates implemented for all production models.
- By 2026, when the *EU AI Act* takes effect, Achmea must adhere full compliance.
- Developing and implementing *AI policies* and procedures.
- Establishing *AI governance framework* and management tools.
- Setting up and validating *model registration*.
- *Data preparation* and defining the role of the data steward.
- Designing AI workflow and *model management processes*.
- Establishing regular *AI risk assessments* and *red-teaming* practices.
- Service development and *management tooling* for the AI platform.
- Monitoring AI models for deviations and conducting stress-tests to *ensure robustness*.
- Third-party awareness initiatives.
- Employee *training and awareness* programs.

4.2.1 AI Risk management at Achmea

Achmea's AI governance and policies are formulated in compliance with ethical and regulatory requirements. To address accountability as one of their key principles, Achmea integrated its AI governance roadmap with NIST AI Risk Management Framework, ensuring a structured approach to risk assessment and compliance. The "NIST Risk Management Framework for Responsible AI" provides structured recommendations for AI risk assessment and ethics and regulatory compliance. These recommendations are plotted on previously defined measures to test completeness.

At the time of the research twenty-three recommendations were planned, but have not yet started, forty-four recommendations are being discussed in various project groups.

Notes: NIST Risk Framework for Responsible AI consists of seventy-two recommendations, divided into four categories:

- **Govern:** AI policy, governance structures, and third-party awareness.
- **Map:** Identification and documentation of AI risks and bias sources.
- **Measure:** Continuous AI model testing and fairness evaluations.
- **Manage:** Ongoing AI lifecycle management and risk mitigation.

Effectiveness: Ensures proactive risk assessment and comprehensive AI monitoring. Achmea has successfully incorporated the risk management framework into its policies, processes, and technical mechanisms to oversee AI systems.

4.3 AI Governance Structures

Achmea's approach to AI governance involves integrating oversight within existing policies and processes rather than creating a wholly separate structure. This means no additional procedures, but rather minimal new tollgates within established workflows. The design is currently work in progress, aiming to re-use Achmea's standard governance wherever possible. Key elements include:

- **AI Steering Committee and Senior Managers Committee:** Overseeing AI initiatives at both central and decentralized levels, with a specific "Responsible AI" project group among others.

- **Using already established Governance Components for AI Governance:**

- **Project Committee Achmea & Decentralized Project Committees** (per Division): Decide on central and local AI investments.
- **Existing IT-Incident and Monitoring Processes:** Currently managed by central IT team which is under review. A new central IT team for addressing red-teaming is in progress.
- **Data Platform User Groups** (operational and senior management): Set priorities and manage central deliveries or enablers.
- **Group Risk Committee:** Led by an *Executive Board Member* plus business unit Chief Executive Officer (*CEO*s), setting guardrails for *Responsible AI*.
- **Regular Risk Control Boards:** Key risks and controls managed by central and decentralized Risk Boards, potentially automated.

- **Data Governance Board/Privacy Board:** At the central level addressing data quality, compliance, and Business Intelligence/Artificial Intelligence (BI/AI) guardrails.
- **Ethics Complaint Committees & AI Ombudsman** – Oversee policy development and compliance and provide dispute resolution pathways.
- **Regulatory Compliance Team** – Ensure AI governance aligns with the EU AI Act, GDPR, and internal ethical guidelines and other required compliance obligations.
- **Audit and monitoring team** – Regularly performs audits to check for compliance to defined policy and ethical guidelines. Third-Party AI Ethics Audits conducted to ensure regulatory compliance.
- **Data Governance Team:** Monitoring and ensuring compliance with data-related regulations, quality and standards.

By embedding AI governance and risk management into these existing structures and refining a *decision tree* for risk assessments, Achmea seeks to ensure cohesive, efficient oversight while upholding privacy, ethical standards, and regulatory compliance without burdening the organization with redundant processes and additional team structures specific to AI implementation. The only additional Governance team added to this process is the **AI Bias Auditing Team** that conducts periodic fairness assessments and red-teaming exercises.

One major aspect of the AI governance stands out is stakeholder engagement. It is perceived as an essential activity for integration of the ethical framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making, incorporating EEC, European, and UNESCO AI principles.

4.4 Policy-Driven AI Governance Processes

Achmea recognizes that innovative technologies, including AI, introduce new risks and therefore new responsibilities. Rather than developing entirely separate frameworks, Achmea has incorporated additional controls into existing management processes, ensuring privacy, ethics, model management, and EU AI Act alignment are all addressed. These distinct risk classifications which are currently organized by a decision tree will help streamline or eliminate any redundant or overlapping measures.

4.4.1 Established Policies

Achmea's suite of policies covers the full spectrum of AI governance needs:

- **AI Policy Formulation**
 - Aligns with EEC and UNESCO AI principles
 - Codifies standards for ethical AI use
 - Provides standardized best practices for the entire AI lifecycle
- **Privacy Policy & PIA**
 - Conducts Privacy Impact Assessments
 - Generates low/medium/high risk classifications
- **Ethical Framework & Assessments**
 - Emphasizes fairness and non-discrimination
 - Produces low/medium/high risk classifications
- **Model Management & Validation Policy**
 - Applies its own risk assessment standards
 - Ensures models undergo robust validation
- **EU AI Act Policy**
 - Categorizes AI risk as forbidden, minimum, transparency, or high risk
 - Mandates strict documentation and risk controls

- **Data Governance and Stewardship**
 - Ensures ‘AI-Ready’ data via Achmea’s “DataFirst” approach
 - Guarantees reliable, responsibly consumed data for models
 - Implements the “Daily Close Principles” and fosters data maturity, collaborative data use, and business-oriented data organization
- **Pre-Production Checklist**
 - Validates legal requirements, bias mitigation, transparency, privacy and AI risk assessment for model deployment
 - Blocks launch until compliance is demonstrated by ensuring each project meets minimal compliance and ethical standards prior to launch
- **Employee Training & Awareness**
 - Equips staff with knowledge on responsible AI use and emerging ethical issues. Achmea has established training programs and e-learning facilities for wider adoption & awareness as governance measure.

4.4.2 Policy-Driven Governance Processes

Achmea has implemented the following policy driven governance measures those are essential to its ethical AI framework.

- **Model Registration & Validation**
 - Catalogues AI models for clear traceability
 - Conducts regular validation to confirm performance and compliance
- **Service Development & AI Platform Management**
 - Centralizes AI lifecycle oversight
 - Maintains consistent workflows for deployment and maintenance
- **Plan–Do–Check–Act (PDCA) Cycle**
 - Embeds continuous improvement in monitoring and accountability
 - Facilitates iterative risk management
- **Continuous Monitoring**
 - Monitors AI models for unexpected behaviour and addresses it according to severity
- **Red Teaming**
 - Purposefully probes AI models for undesirable behaviours, enhancing model robustness
 - Simulates adversarial attacks to identify vulnerabilities, strengthens AI’s resilience against misuse or bias

Effectiveness: Ensures policy-driven oversight of AI governance, structured AI implementation and risk assessment. These established policies and measures cover both *build* and *use* phase of the AI implementation as per OECD AI lifecycle definition further enhances their effectiveness.

Improvement Gap: The current approach focuses on very high-level questions; however, incorporating bias targeted questions for addressing specific bias types will strengthen Achmea’s ability to detect and mitigate nuanced biases.

Resolution: In response, Achmea has developed a new decision tree to refine existing processes, thereby reducing redundancy and capturing more granular bias-related risks moving forward.

4.4.3 Technical Mechanisms and Governance Practices

Achmea employs a comprehensive ethical framework to evaluate each AI implementation, including MASHA. Central to this approach is a template containing thirty practical test cases derived from the *Achmea Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making*. This template covers several high-level categories:

- **Ethical Frameworks**
 - Built on collaboration with HLEG Trustworthy AI and the “Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making,” ensuring consistent bias mitigation efforts.
- **Human Oversight**
 - Guarantees that negative or high-risk decisions never depend solely on algorithmic outputs.
- **Data Validation**
 - Pseudonymized and regularly audited data, with continuous monitoring for fairness and inclusivity.
- **Continuous Monitoring**
 - Uses periodic evaluations and random quality checks to verify compliance with ethical and regulatory standards.
- **Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) & Business Impact Analyses (BIAs)**
 - Incorporates formal procedures to evaluate privacy, security, and business implications before deployment.
- **Model Training Safeguards**
 - Omits customer-identifying details (e.g., names, addresses), with even case numbers pseudonymized.
 - Undergoes periodic validation by medical specialists and Achmea’s Model Management team.
 - Relies on random sampling to confirm medical evaluations performed by MASHA.
 - Applies threshold recalibration and fairness testing to maintain equitable decision thresholds.
- **Transparency & Explainability**
 - Ensures stakeholders can understand how MASHA’s decisions are generated, especially in high-stakes contexts.
- **Fairness Audits**
 - Conducted during model training to address potential biases early and uphold inclusive outcomes.

4.4.4 Key Testing Categories

Each AI project at Achmea must pass an extensive testing cycle covering:

- Cybersecurity
- Fallback and general security
- Data quality and integrity
- Respect for privacy and data protection
- Human oversight
- Preventing unfair bias
- Accessibility and inclusive design
- Auditability and risk minimization
- Social and democratic impacts

4.4.5 Monitoring and Compliance Measures

Achmea adopts real-time monitoring and red teaming for AI systems. Most monitoring tools are developed internally, supporting both machine learning and traditional scripted AI. Although currently manual, the organization plans to automate these processes before August 2026 by implementing Microsoft (MS) AI Foundry (AI-studio).

Effectiveness This policy-driven oversight enforces a structured approach to AI implementation and risk assessment, reinforcing accountability at every stage of AI's lifecycle.

Challenges: Scaling these measures across diverse AI applications requires further investments in automation, tool integration, and ongoing staff training. Nonetheless, Achmea's roadmap reflects a commitment to refining these governance practices to meet evolving ethical and regulatory standards.

4.5 Current Governance challenges and further need of improvement:

Current governance practices are in silos and implemented as verticals (Data governance, Privacy GDPR, EU AI Act, regulatory compliance etc.). These leads to inefficiency with redundant requirements and associated duplicate governance controls. AI needs horizontal governance approach as it depends and has impact over various internal organizations. May be a governance framework with the concept of Trias Politica along with its cross functional collaboration is an answer to such challenges. However, this study is not focusing on addressing this identified issue and it may need further research.

DATA GOVERNANCE PRACTICE AT ACHMEA ENSURES AI READY DATA

Achmea is actively enhancing the safety and reliability of data through robust data management and data governance practices. While IT ensures structured data in systems is reliable and secure, users are responsible for safeguarding unstructured data in their work environments. However, leveraging data effectively for AI requires additional steps.

Achmea is actively developing the building block "Expertise in Data & Digital" which is perceived as a strategic purpose enabler for Achmea. The reporting processes are being fully automated ensuring data processing complies with new regulations. There is an active data community, and an *online Data Hub*.

Achmea increasingly *collaborates with other service providers* to serve the same customers. Data exchange with partners supports this collaboration with a common "language." as per Open Finance regulations, which now has been delayed at EU level.

Data governance rules are automated as much as possible, streamlining compliance and ensuring seamless integration of data products. This is a 2028 strategic goal for Achmea.

Achmea claims its data is of high quality and, therefore, reliable. They protect their data and ensure it is used only for its intended purposes. They report to regulators on this (to maintain their "*license to operate*"). This reporting is also as automated as possible. As of end of quarter two this year, Achmea will implement this under a roadmap automating data governance measures within the boundaries of Microsoft.

The *DataFirst* approach has been in implementation since 2021. The S&T Data Governance Advisory Team supports the business in the transformation to the new data landscape, the implementation of the daily close principles, and growth to data maturity level 4. The Analytics platform is capable of processing confidential data since 2024. Business and IT collaborate to

enable data sharing through the *Senior User Data Council*. All unstructured data will be stored in M365 by 2025.

The Achmea DataFirst approach simplifies the data landscape reducing (unnecessary) duplicate data, and the required data is quickly available to everyone who needs it. It enables to share data securely and reliably. The Achmea DataFirst approach is built on six pillars:

1. **Daily Close Principles:** Ensuring that data is directly, reliably, and online available for the business processes.
2. **Unified Data Platform:** Using one data platform (Microsoft’s Azure cloud) to analyse and share data, enabling the use of each other’s data products under automated “rules of engagement.”
3. **Growth in Data Maturity:** Empowering everyone to provide and use data independently yet responsibly.
4. **Collaborative Use of Data:** All business units collaborate on data usage and sharing to further digitize Achmea.
5. **Business-Oriented Data Organization:** Structuring data as close as possible to the business based on data products within business data domains, following the industry standard “Data Mesh.”
6. **Responsible AI Integration:** IT ensures that AI understands the given data and uses it responsibly. IT services protect the data, ensure its use is purpose-driven, and enable ethical application through “security, privacy, and ethics by design.”

This comprehensive approach ensures a secure, efficient, and innovative use of data to support Achmea’s business goals. Achmea primarily uses two data planes. The ‘operational plane’ supporting primarily insurance and service processes of Achmea and the ‘analytical plane’ supporting decision making, model development, reporting and dashboards.

Achmea is increasingly applying the “Daily Close Principles” which have already been implemented in its operational reporting processes for frameworks such as Solvency II, International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), and Customer Due Diligence (CDD) processes. Achmea is currently implementing the *EU AI Act* and Open Finance Regulation, as well as applying these principles to the model management landscape.

5.1 Understanding “Daily Close Principles”

1. **Day-Current Data Supply and Processing:** Data is supplied and processed in IT chains daily, eliminating queues and backlogs in business processes.
2. **Fit-for-Purpose Data Quality:** Data must be of sufficient quality for its intended use. *Data quality is continuously measured, and if issues arise, they are corrected at the source immediately.* This ensures data can be processed digitally without delays (“First Time Right”).
3. **Fully Digital Processing:** Data is processed digitally without manual intervention, minimizing time *loss and errors*. This enables *Straight Through Processing*, where data is instantly available for use.

4. **Single Source of Truth:** Data is retrieved directly from its original source—the point where it first enters Achmea’s systems. This ensures a single, reliable version of the truth.
5. **Unique, Reusable Data Products:** The source publishes data as a unique, reusable data product. The *data catalogue* serves as a utility to provide the most up-to-date version. Unnecessary copies are avoided unless technically necessary.
6. **Automated Compliance:** Compliance with legal and policy frameworks (e.g., CDD, GDPR, Solvency II, IFRS, CSRD, OFR, EU AI Act) is enforced as much as possible through automation, ensuring data can flow securely through the organization (*Continuous Automated Controls*).
7. **Decentralized Where Possible, Centralized Where Necessary:** Data delivery and use occur within the departments working with the data unless centralization is required. This balances complexity and self-sufficiency.

By implementing the Daily Close Principles, Achmea ensures efficient, high-quality, and compliant data handling that supports both operational excellence and strategic goals.

5.2 Key Aspects of Growing in Data Maturity

Between 2021 and 2022, Achmea achieved data maturity level 3. By the end of 2024, both Business and IT aim to meet the requirements for level 4 maturity (the “Digital Insurer” level), preparing Achmea for the trusted use of AI.

On September 1, 2023, Achmea took the first step toward becoming a Data Mesh organization. In this model:

- **Source system owners** “harvest the raw carrots” (make raw data available on APA).
- **Data delivery teams** “wash and chop the carrots” and place them on the supermarket shelf (sanitizes and labels data, Purview Data Map).
- **Domain data teams** in the business create “a delicious salad” and put it on the menu (Purview Data Catalogue).

1. Empowering Users with Trusted and Controlled Data Consumption

- As Achmea grows in maturity, users gain the ability to independently share and use data within established rules.
- There is a transition from a defensive approach (overprotecting data, restricting its flow) to a controlled offensive approach, where data is actively used to create value.

2. Collaborative Effort Between Business and IT

- Business and IT collaborate to ensure data reliability and responsible usage.
- Both progresses simultaneously in improving data maturity, ensuring alignment across processes and systems.

3. Business-Led Data Quality Assurance

- The business takes responsibility for measuring and improving data quality at the source.

- This objective is achieved through a *data quality assurance cycle reusing IFRS/SII best practices*, which monitors and addresses data quality, making it increasingly reliable.

4. **IT-Driven Enablement:** IT ensures that every IT service provides functionality to:

- Manage data (quality, privacy, security, and ethics).
- Facilitate data sharing and data exchange.
- Enable improvements in data quality.
- For example, IT provides data quality dashboards to support ongoing improvements.

5. **Measuring Data Maturity**

- Maturity is assessed using a **maturity model**, one for IT's ability to deliver data and another for the business's ability to apply data.
- The model outlines specific practices required for IT service owners and business process owners to achieve the next maturity level.

6. **Investing in AI on Level 4 Capabilities**

- AI applications are only developed on *IT capabilities that meet level 4 requirements*.
- This ensures scalability and alignment with Achmea's broader digitalization goals.

Implications of Level 4 Maturity

Achieving level 4 data maturity means:

- Process data in an automated way, without manual interference with fully digitized processes.
- Users can work more autonomously and effectively with data.
- Data becomes a driver for innovation, value creation, and improved decision-making.
- Both IT and business processes are prepared to support AI responsibly and sustainably.

By focusing on these goals, Achmea ensures its data maturity growth supports its vision of becoming a trusted and digitally empowered organization.

ALIGNING LITERATURE REVIEW RESULTS WITH GOVERNANCE PRACTICES AT ACHMEA

6.1 Role of Governance from Literature review

Governance is integral to mitigating bias, bridging technical and process-level interventions with policy enforcement. It establishes frameworks for accountability, ensures compliance with fairness standards, and fosters transparency across the AI lifecycle. Key governance actions include:

- **Data Governance:** Enforcing diversity, updating datasets, and regulating third-party data sources.
- **Algorithmic Oversight:** Mandating fairness constraints and auditing optimization processes.

- **Deployment and Monitoring:** Instituting mechanisms for regular audits, interaction monitoring, and dynamic system adjustments.

Bias mitigation in AI requires coordinated efforts across technical, process, and policy domains. Governance serves as a centrepiece, ensuring the ethical design, deployment, and operation of AI systems. Aligning with OECD definition these phases are broadly classified into build phase and use phase. Governance mitigates AI biases through enforceable policies, ethical oversight, and continuous monitoring. It ensures accountability at every stage of the AI lifecycle, aligning technical and operational practices with fairness and inclusivity standards. By integrating governance into data collection, model development, and deployment, biases are systematically identified and addressed, fostering trustworthy AI systems. Insights from UNESCO, NIST, and related studies highlight governance as not just a supporting factor but a critical enabler of bias mitigation in AI systems.

A synthesis of the analysed documents from our literature review reveals a comprehensive governance framework for addressing bias in AI systems through *policy-based governance*, *process driven approach* and *technical mitigation techniques*. The literature review also emphasises that AI governance does not function in isolation; it is interwoven into the organization’s overall governance ecosystem, thereby fostering consistency in policy enforcement and accountability structures.

6.2 Mapping insights from literature review with Operational practices at Achmea

During our research we have observed various governance practices have been practiced at Achmea following its trustworthy and ethical AI implementation principles. We found evidence of strong data governance practices to ensure AI ready data, algorithmic oversight to ensure model robustness and adequate deployment and monitoring techniques to ensure risk free and efficient AI operation. The table 11 below provides a comprehensive list of governance policies, processes and technical mitigation techniques being practiced at Achmea to mitigate AI and bias related risks.

Relevant Mitigation Factors of Governance Framework	Key Elements	Description	Observed at Achmea?	Remarks
Policy based governance	Establishing governance standards	Formal governance structures that promote ethical AI practices including mandatory transparency and accountability policies	Yes	Collaborated with HLEG Trustworthy AI Framework
	Ethical principles	Recommendations include embedding fairness, non-discrimination, and ethical use guidelines into AI governance frameworks	Yes	EEC and UNESCO Principles and Ethical Framework for Data-Driven Decision-Making. The framework includes measures like the "Ethical Wheel," which ensures customer interests are safeguarded by weighing how Achmea utilizes available technological possibilities.
	Inclusive stakeholder engagement	Incorporating diverse perspectives in decision-making processes helps	Yes	Stakeholder engagement is an essential activity for integration of the ethical framework for

		address societal and institutional biases		Data-Driven Decision-Making at Achmea. Apart from applying the ethical wheel as a part of the 'Ethisch kader datagedreven besluitvorming', Achmea has a holistic, multi-disciplinary approach regarding Responsible AI. Especially applying 'daily close principles' to operational plane application of reporting processes. Multiple stakeholders are involved.
	Public accountability	Mandatory public disclosure of AI deployment and third-party audits ensure continuous oversight and public trust	Not explicit disclosure of AI models	Achmea had performed <i>external evaluation results</i> . Achmea will not reach as far in publishing AI models, the customer is submitted to. However, Achmea publishes GDPR policy statements. Third party audits to AI are part of regular audit system.
Process driven approach	Lifecycle risk management	Embedding bias mitigation as a continuous process across pre-design, design, deployment, and evaluation stages	Yes	Integrated risk management and compliance framework. Also adapting to NIST risk management framework. Achmea addressed this by conducting <i>bias impact assessments</i> and actively working to identify and mitigate hidden biases during development. It also conducts <i>fairness audits</i> during model training.
	Participatory and human centred design	Involving stakeholders from diverse backgrounds to incorporate social and cultural contexts during AI development	Yes	The model undergoes periodic validation by medical specialists and Achmea's Model Management team. Medical evaluations (conducted by both specialists and MASHA) are quality-checked through random sampling. In addition, Achmea has the ambition of continuously monitoring AI-model performance automatically, subjected to the availability of their preferred MSFT toolkit AI foundry.
	Incident reporting mechanism	Establishing feedback loops for tracking, documenting, and addressing bias-related incidents	No noticeable observation	Human Oversight; review critical decisions made by MASHA. Currently IT incident tracking is on use.
	Iterative testing and evaluation	Continuous validation of models for fairness, accuracy, and transparency ensures responsiveness to emergent biases	Yes	Performance Steering and Measurement Mechanisms for classical models like MASHA are already in place.
	Technical mitigation techniques	Bias detection and mitigation tools	Leveraging statistical techniques, rebalancing methods, and causal models to identify and reduce biases in data and algorithms	Yes

				they observed lack of Commercial Off The Shelf tools available in the market at this stage)
	Explainability and traceability	Developing tools for model interpretability and transparent documentation of datasets and algorithmic decision-making processes	The MDD was not shared with us due to confidentiality . However, Achmea confirmed this practice.	The Model Design Documentation (document MDD 3.1) has detailed explanation of operational details of MASHA. This document explains, among other things, the technical functioning of the model, the structure of the IT chain, data processing methods, model training, human supervision, testing procedures, and how explainability is ensured.
	Data quality controls	Ensuring high-quality, representative datasets and addressing gaps through robust data governance strategies	Yes	Data governance ensuring AI ready data. Using Microsoft AI and data governance software with the promises that it will integrate with Microsoft defender.
	Proactive testing	Employing advanced methods, such as adversarial testing, to identify potential bias risks in models before deployment.	Yes	Preproduction checklist with quality gates Random sample testing.

Table 11: Analysing Practical Implementation at Achmea with Literature Review findings

6.3 AI Bias related Risks in MASHA and related mitigation mechanisms

Despite its safeguards, MASHA is susceptible to AI bias risks related to data processing, decision thresholds, and interpretability. Table 12 below highlights potential bias related risks and current mitigation strategy by Achmea.

Bias related Risk in MASHA	Description	Mitigation Strategy Implemented by Achmea
Hidden bias in training data	If historical medical data contains biases (e.g. socioeconomic or demographic disparities), these can influence MASHA's scoring, leading to discriminatory outcomes.	Achmea addressed this by conducting <i>bias impact assessments</i> and actively working to identify and mitigate hidden biases during development. It also conducts <i>fairness audits</i> during model training.
Bias amplification	AI models can reinforce pre-existing biases through repeated use	<i>Human oversight</i> for negative outcomes and <i>periodic bias evaluations</i> .
Under representation in data	Rare medical conditions and historically excluded groups may have insufficient data representation	Ensuring diverse training datasets and <i>fairness evaluation metrics</i> . <i>It is a Requirement for third party data provider)</i>
Threshold sensitivity	The decision threshold determines automatic acceptance, but if poorly calibrated it may favour or disadvantage certain applicants.	Continuous <i>threshold recalibration</i> and <i>fairness testing</i> .
Interpretability challenges	AI decisions must be explainable and understandable to stakeholders	Transparency measures and compliance with <i>explainability requirements</i>

Table 12: Bias related risks associated with MASHA and related mitigation strategy

MAPPING ACHMEA’S AI GOVERNANCE PRACTICES TO TRIAS POLITICA CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The following table 13 tries to capture the insights from the study of AI implementation and related governance practices at Achmea. The conceptual model tries to map the captured insights into the Trias Politica based governance model. In practice, the teams, roles and responsibility may not be distinct as depicted, and, in some cases, the same team may be handling multiple roles. From the captured information, we have created a logical separation of roles and responsibilities by following the Trias Politica principles of separation of power.

	Legislative Branch	Executive Branch	Judiciary Branch
Teams /Departments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulatory Compliance Team Risk Management Team AI Governance team Data Governance Team UX Teams (for user centric policies) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Executive Leadership Product Owners/Business Leads AI Operations Teams IT & Infrastructure Team AI development team Senior User data Council 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Audit and Monitoring team AI Ethics Committee Appeals and Grievance Team Red-Teaming and Adversarial Testing Team
Roles	<p>Define the overarching legal and ethical frameworks for AI governance.</p> <p>(Governance policy creation, regulatory compliance, and ethical oversight.)</p>	<p>Enforce and operationalize the policies defined by the legislative branch.</p> <p>(Strategic leadership, operational efficiency, and ensuring AI aligns with business objectives.)</p>	<p>Ensures that AI regulations are interpreted and enforced in alignment with defined policies and principles.(Accountability, Audits, and dispute Resolution)</p>
<p>Primary Responsibilities</p> <p>Comprises of Mitigation factors of the Governance framework</p> <p>Policy based governance</p> <p>Process driven approach</p> <p>Technical mitigation techniques</p>	<p>- Drafting AI Policy, setting up AI governance principles, ethical guidelines, and compliance requirements aligned with GDPR, AI Act, and internal ethical standards</p> <p>- Designing process for Model management, defining lifecycle management rules for AI models, including validation, updates, and decommissioning.</p> <p>- Designing way of working, creating frameworks for collaboration between AI teams, risk management, and compliance processes.</p>	<p>- Implementing AI governance by enforcing AI policies through operational procedures</p> <p>- Deploying and maintaining tools for AI lifecycle management, including monitoring and auditing</p> <p>- Conduct Preproduction AI Quality Gate Checking</p> <p>- Data preparation and execute data steward activity to ensure high quality data for AI decision making</p> <p>- Setting up management organization and management tooling for AI platform</p>	<p>- Audit AI systems for fairness, transparency, ethical breaches and compliance.</p> <p>- Resolve disputes or grievances related to AI decisions.</p> <p>- Conduct red-teaming, adversarial testing, and stress testing for bias or vulnerabilities.</p> <p>- Liaise with external regulators for feedback and audits.</p> <p>- Human Oversight: Ensures that no negative decisions are made solely by the algorithm</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generate third party awareness by establishing guidelines for assessing AI risks from third-party vendors and external AI services - Defining AI risk management framework - Setting up Data Governance policies, procedures and principles - Preparation Preproduction AI Quality Gate Checklist 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducting employee training & awareness with AI ethics training, compliance awareness programs, and continuous learning initiatives - Maintain a Single Source of Truth and ensure quality in data pipelines. - Model registration and validation to ensure AI models are properly documented and evaluated - Ensuring diverse training datasets and <i>fairness evaluation metrics</i> - Setting up Human-in-the-Loop approach and feedback - Human oversight for negative outcomes and periodic bias evaluations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous <i>threshold recalibration</i> and <i>fairness testing</i> - Continuous Monitoring: Periodic evaluations and random quality checks help ensure compliance with ethical and regulatory standards. - <i>Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs)</i> and <i>Business Impact Analyses (BIAs)</i> - Conducting <i>fairness audits</i> during model training. - Statistical Metrics for Bias Detection (Red teaming, continuous monitoring) - PDCA cycle for monitoring and accountability with continuous improvement and risk management.
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Table 13: Trias AI Politica Governance Structure

ALIGNMENT WITH EU AI ACT

As part of our research and bringing in the EU AI Act context, we wanted to classify MASHA as per the defined risk categories based on the Sector and function approach. As per our findings, MASHA is a *high-risk* AI system. According to EU AI Act article 6 point 2, systems in Annex III are also considered high risk.

MASHA is involved in providing access to and enjoyment of essential private services and essential public services and benefits and is more specially used for risk assessment and pricing in relation to natural persons in the case of life and health insurance.

Therefore, Achmea provider of MASHA, is responsible to ensure fully compliancy with all applicable requirements enlisted in article 8, “Compliance with the requirements”.

Here is a list of high-level compliance requirements

- Article 9 Risk management system
- Article 10 Data and data governance
- Article 11 Technical documentation
- Article 12 Record-keeping
- Article 13 Transparency and provision of information to deployers
- Article 14 Human oversight
- Article 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity
- Achmea, as a provider of the high-risk AI system MASHA, must fulfil obligations of article 16, “Obligations of providers of high-risk AI systems.

Based on the governance practices currently implemented at Achmea, we have attempted to map them against the compliance obligations outlined in the EU AI Act. However, this mapping does not serve as a confirmation of full compliance, as the specific implementation details were beyond the scope of our study. The list in the table 14 serves only as an indicative overview of existing practices at Achmea that could potentially be extended or adapted to meet the requirements of the EU AI Act.

EU AI Act Provision	Achmea’s Implementation
Article 9 – Risk Management System	NIST AI RMF adoption (Govern–Map–Measure–Manage)
Article 10 – Data and Data Governance	“DataFirst” strategy & Daily Close Principles
Article 11 – Technical Documentation	Model Design Docs (MDD 3.1, not shared but confirmed present)
Article 12 – Record Keeping	Audit logs, model validation tracking
Article 13 – Transparency and provision of information to deployers	Explainability, user communication mechanisms
Article 14 – Human Oversight	No negative decision made solely by AI
Article 15 – Accuracy, Robustness, Security	Preproduction testing, red teaming, automated compliance
Article 16 – Provider Obligations	Model registration, DPIAs, BIAs, bias mitigation protocols

Table 14: EU AI Act compliance requirements and Mapping implementation

During our study, we have observed most of the compliance requirements already in place in some way. However, this study doesn't include any compliance check or validation of these measure as per the definition of the EU AI Act. Secondly, classifying MASHA as a high-risk system is based on our judgement and understanding of the AI Act and understood features of MASHA. As the Act is subjected to legal interpretations, the actual risk classification of the said system may vary.

CONCLUSION

This case study offers a comprehensive examination of Achmea's AI governance framework, using MASHA, an internally developed AI decision-support system for medical acceptance in term life insurance as the focal point. Analysing the implemented governance mechanism in the context of the Trias Politica governance model and EU AI Act reveals key insights on relevant factors for designing effective governance structures aimed at mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.

9.1 Summary of Findings

9.1.1 MASHA as an Ethical and Technically Robust AI System

MASHA demonstrates a high level of maturity in ethical AI deployment. It limits algorithmic decisions to only positive outcomes and uses human oversight for complex or negative cases avoiding direct algorithmic discrimination. Privacy-by-design practices, pseudonymization, and rigorous data handling protocols ensure GDPR alignment and reinforce trustworthiness.

9.1.2 Adoption of a Strong Ethical Framework

Achmea has incorporated trusted ethical frameworks such as the HLEG Trustworthy AI and the Dutch insurance sector's "Ethisch Kader Datagedreven Besluitvorming." These frameworks embed human rights, fairness, explainability, and accountability as foundational elements in AI development and use.

9.1.3 Operationalization of Standard AI Principles

Achmea is operationalizing AI ethics through measurable practices, preproduction quality gates, DPIAs, fairness audits, continuous threshold calibration, and explainability testing, effectively translating abstract AI principles into concrete business and technological workflows. While substantial progress has been made, Achmea is still in the process of implementing these tools and measures, with full deployment expected before the end of 2025.

9.1.4 Governance Processes and Best Practices

AI governance is implemented through a layered structure involving:

- Ethical oversight committees and compliance teams,
- Integrated model risk management workflows,
- Lifecycle-based quality assurance tools and custom-built monitoring platforms.
- Specific implementation of governance controls and technical measures during the *build* and *use* phase as defined by the OECD AI definition.

Furthermore, Achmea's DataFirst and Daily Close Principles contribute to a resilient data governance foundation, enhancing readiness for AI-driven processes.

9.1.5 Alignment with our Literature Review Findings

The case study reinforces the relevance of theoretical governance models by demonstrating how Achmea effectively embeds AI oversight within its existing Corporate, IT, and Data governance frameworks. This approach closely aligns with the literature review findings. In particular, Achmea's use of policy-based governance, lifecycle monitoring, and technical bias mitigation tools (such as red teaming and fairness metrics) reflects best practices recommended in academic research.

This alignment highlights the broader research consensus that integrating AI governance into established organizational structures, combined with proactive bias mitigation, is key to building trustworthy and compliant AI systems. While challenges such as public transparency and incident reporting are acknowledged elsewhere in this study, Achmea's current governance model nonetheless offers a strong foundation for ethical and responsible AI adoption.

9.1.6 Trias Politica Governance Model in Practice

The Trias Politica conceptual model emphasizing separation of powers was used to categorize governance functions at Achmea:

- **Legislative:** AI policy design, ethical standards, and regulatory alignment,
- **Executive:** Day-to-day AI implementation, data workflows, and training,
- **Judiciary:** Independent oversight, audits, grievance handling, and bias testing.

This separation creates clarity of roles, improves checks and balances, and enhances overall accountability. While the current operational responsibilities may practically overlap, the applied best practices offer sufficient assurance that a clear separation of roles and responsibilities can be effectively established in a greenfield AI implementation.

9.1.7 Alignment with the EU AI Act

MASHA has been identified as a **high-risk AI system** under the EU AI Act, particularly in the context of insurance risk assessment involving natural persons. The case study demonstrates that Achmea has proactively addressed nearly all key requirements of the Act including those outlined in Articles 9 to 16.

However, the study refrains from making legal determinations and recommends formal compliance audits. MASHA thus serves as a blueprint for responsible AI aligned with the EU's legislative vision.

9.1.8 Areas of Concern and Potential Improvements

As the pursuit of truly responsible AI continues at Achmea, key areas such as public transparency, structured feedback mechanisms, and integrated governance frameworks remain critical opportunities for enhancement. Notably, the lack of a dedicated incident reporting mechanism and limited external disclosures may undermine long-term stakeholder confidence and increase vulnerability to regulatory scrutiny. While Achmea's roadmap includes plans for automation and demonstrates a willingness to evolve, accelerating these initiatives will be vital as compliance requirements under frameworks like the EU AI Act become more stringent.

Currently, AI governance at Achmea operates within vertical silos, which is leading to duplicated efforts and inefficiencies in meeting compliance demands. A shift toward a more horizontally integrated governance model that follows central coordination but implemented across business functions could address these challenges more effectively. Reinforcing the Trias Politica structure through cross-functional working groups may offer a practical and scalable approach to achieving this integration.

9.2 Final Reflection

The MASHA case study underlines how a well-structured AI system, supported by robust governance and ethical oversight, can operate effectively even in high-stakes environments such as life insurance. Achmea's approach illustrates that integrating AI oversight into existing corporate frameworks strengthens accountability and operational cohesion. The cooperative model of "human plus machine" decision-making further exemplifies how an organization can innovate responsibly. Looking ahead, Achmea's ongoing refinements, particularly the planned improvements to bias detection, public transparency, and compliance monitoring, reinforce the practical relevance of this case study for organizations seeking to balance innovation with risk mitigation. It certainly helped us successfully aligning its governance model with both the *Trias Politica* framework and the evolving requirements of the *EU AI Act*. The implementation of MASHA, offers valuable validation for our research, highlighting the practical feasibility of clearly demarking governance functions (legislative, executive, and judicial) within an enterprise context.

For academic researchers, MASHA offers a tangible illustration of how governance theories such as Trias Politica and regulatory mandates (e.g., EU AI Act) can be operationalized within everyday corporate practice. The insights drawn from MASHA serve as both a proof of concept and a scalable model for other organizations seeking to navigate the complex ethical, legal, and technical challenges of AI adoption.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS:

Internal documents from Achmea considered for this case study.

- Werkpakketten AI volgens AMM-capabilities v3.3.xlsx
- Masha introductie.pdf
- AI in control 2024 _Def_Ext.pptx
- quant sheets.pptx
- AI beheersing 2024 versie def.pdf
- ethisch kader toetsing STV.pdf

Appendix – H

The Role of Ethical AI Principles in Governance and Bias Mitigation

Relevance Criteria

1. **High Relevance:** Directly addresses or mitigates bias in AI, focusing on fairness, inclusivity, accountability, and transparency (i.e. Fairness, Non-Discrimination, Transparency, Diversity).
2. **Indirect/Partial Relevance:** Influences bias through broader structural or secondary means but does not directly target bias elimination (i.e. Sustainability, Awareness, Environmental Concerns).
3. **No Relevance:** Minimal or no impact on bias, focusing on unrelated areas like technical aspects, ecological systems without social overlap, or purely operational goals (i.e. Examples: Only applicable if completely unrelated to bias).

	UNESCO AI Principles	Description	Relevance to Bias Issues
1	Proportionality and Do No Harm	Ensures that AI systems do not cause harm and that their impacts are proportional to their intended benefits.	High Relevance: Prevents harm to marginalised or vulnerable groups caused by biased systems.
2	Fairness and Non-Discrimination	Mandates equitable access to AI benefits and ensures the elimination of biased or discriminatory AI applications and outcomes.	High Relevance: Core principle addressing bias and promoting equitable outcomes.
3	Transparency and Explainability	Advocates for making AI systems understandable and their decision-making processes clear to ensure accountability and trust.	High Relevance: Facilitates bias detection and ensures accountability.
4	Responsibility and Accountability	Establishes ethical and legal responsibility for AI actions, ensuring systems and their creators can be held accountable for their decisions and impacts.	High Relevance: Ensures accountability for outcomes and rectifies bias-related harms.
5	Sustainability	Calls for the integration of sustainability goals, ensuring that AI supports social, cultural, and economic sustainability alongside environmental concerns.	Indirect/Partial Relevance: Encourages fairness in resource distribution, indirectly addressing structural biases.
6	Right to Privacy and Data Protection	Protects individuals' data rights, ensuring AI systems handle personal data ethically and securely.	High Relevance: Addresses biases arising from flawed or misused datasets.
7	Safety and Security	Advocates for the prevention of harms and vulnerabilities in AI systems to ensure their safe and secure operation.	Indirect/Partial Relevance: Protects against safety issues linked to biased systems but not primarily focused on bias mitigation.
8	Awareness and Literacy	Promotes public understanding and education about AI technologies and their societal impacts to empower informed decision-making.	Indirect/Partial Relevance: Enhances public capacity to identify and address biases through education.
9	Human Oversight and Determination	Mandates that humans retain ultimate control and accountability over AI decision-making processes.	High Relevance: Ensures human intervention to prevent or address biases in critical decisions.
10	Multi-stakeholder and adaptive Governance and collaboration	Encourages inclusive, multidisciplinary collaboration in AI governance to address ethical challenges comprehensively.	High Relevance: Inclusive approaches to AI governance, participation of different stakeholders through the AI

		system life cycle is essential to bias mitigation.
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Table 15: UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI. AI principles (UNESCO, 2023)

According to our study, seven out of the ten ethical AI principles defined by UNESCO are highly relevant to addressing bias-related issues, while three are either partially or indirectly relevant. Notably, none of the principles were identified as having no relevance. Table 15 on previous page provides a detailed analysis of the UNESCO principles and their relevance to bias-related concerns.

	OECD AI Principles	Description	Relevance to Bias Issues
1	People and Planet	Inclusive growth, sustainable development and well-being. Encourages the inclusion of underrepresented populations and reduction of inequalities while fostering creativity and well-being.	High Relevance: Directly promotes fairness, inclusion, and equity, addressing biases in data and societal impacts.
2	Human rights, privacy, fairness	Respect for the rule of law, human rights and democratic values, including fairness and privacy. Advocates for fairness, non-discrimination, diversity, and privacy throughout the AI lifecycle.	High Relevance: Explicitly targets bias elimination by upholding fairness and non-discrimination as core principles.
3	Transparency and explainability	Requires AI actors to disclose meaningful information about AI systems, including their limitations, processes, and decisions.	High Relevance: Ensures transparency to identify and address biases, making AI systems more accountable and understandable.
4	Robustness, security and safety	Emphasises reliable functioning of AI systems under adverse conditions with safeguards against harm.	Indirect/Partial Relevance: While not directly targeting bias, robust systems can prevent amplification of existing biases through unintentional errors.
5	Accountability	AI actors must ensure traceability, risk management, and responsible conduct across the AI lifecycle.	High Relevance: Directly addresses bias management by requiring traceability and accountability for harmful biases.

Table 16: OECD principles of trustworthy AI and their relevance to bias related to issues (OECD, 2022)

Similarly, four out of the five OECD principles of trustworthy AI are highly relevant to mitigating bias, with only one, “Robustness, Security, and Safety,” being categorised as indirectly or partially relevant. Table 16 presents a detailed breakdown of the OECD principles and their connection to bias-related issues.

TRIAS AI POLITICA CONCEPTUAL MODEL FOR BIAS-RESILIENT AI GOVERNANCE

Based on the synthesis of insights from bias literature and governance mechanisms and subsequent identification of key factors for a governance framework grounded in the principles of Trias Politica, we have prepared this conceptual model or framework proposal.

The ramifications of AI both in the build and use phases as defined by OECD extend beyond purely IT and data governance. Consequently, confining AI governance to IT and data alone is not viewed as a best practice; instead, it should be integrated into the broader corporate governance framework. The risks associated with AI, particularly high-risk models, can escalate exponentially, as indicated by the literature. Therefore, we explored how AI governance can be cohesively embedded into Enterprise Governance, IT Governance, and Data Governance.

To start with a conceptual model, we investigated the COBIT19 governance mechanism and relevant key components of a governance system. Based on the insights from the literature study we mapped in figure 17 below three key relevant components of the COBIT19 governance system “*Organisational Structure*”, “*Processes*” and “*Principles, Policies, Procedures*” (ISACA, 2018). To create a conceptual model for AI governance that aligns effectively with enterprise governance practices, we adopted the EGIT framework (De Haes, S. et al, 2020) and combined insights from the literature. We then mapped the EGIT structures, processes, and relational mechanisms to the Trias Politica principle of the separation of powers. In doing so, we leveraged governance controls identified in the literature to mitigate biases arising during both the development (“build”) and operational (“use”) phases of AI. Importantly, the relational mechanism highlights collaboration among the three structural bodies, ensuring checks and balances.

Figure 17: Identifying key COBIT19 Governance Components relevant to the RQ with reference to Literature Review Findings

Accordingly, we recommend placing the Trias Politica principle into the *structures, policies, processes, and technical mechanisms* under governance mechanisms, while positioning *collaboration and internal communication* within the relational mechanism. These adjustments should be reflected in the accompanying Figure 18 below to illustrate clearly how legislative, executive, and judiciary roles intersect with EGIT components.

A robust governance model for AI adaptation within organisations must be grounded in the Trias Politica principle of the separation of powers, which divides authority among legislative, executive, and judiciary branches to ensure balanced and accountable governance. This approach helps prevent the concentration of power and facilitates checks and balances, making it particularly suitable for complex, transformative technologies like AI. Leveraging the Enterprise Governance of IT (EGIT) framework provides a practical foundation for this conceptual model: EGIT integrates accountability, control, and stakeholder collaboration through processes, structures, and relational mechanisms to align operational and strategic goals (De Haes, S. et al, 2020).

In the context of AI governance, such a model aligns with global frameworks like UNESCO's *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence* (UNESCO, 2023) and the NIST AI RMF (NIST, 2023), which advocate embedding ethical guidelines, transparency, and fairness into governance systems. By incorporating structured oversight from legislative, executive, and judiciary branches, this model addresses systemic, computational, and human biases while offering a dynamic, lifecycle-based approach to risk management and compliance. It thus ensures that AI systems are both aligned with business objectives and reflective of societal values, fostering trust, accountability, and ethical responsibility at all levels of AI deployment (NIST, 2023); (UNESCO, 2023).

Building on the EGIT principle where structures, processes, and relational mechanisms are paramount, this mental model for AI governance is anchored in Trias Politica's checks and balances. Its aim is to provide a comprehensive framework that can be practically applied within organisations to enhance accountability, transparency, and risk management throughout the AI lifecycle.

Figure 18: Trias AI Política Conceptual Governance Model with reference to the EGIT model

Trias AI Política governance structure: The governance structure is envisaged with three branches of the Trias Política framework to ensure balanced oversight and decision making.

1. Legislative branch: Establishes the rules through ethical, legal and technical guidelines.
 - This branch is defined for policy making plays a role of defining and identifying legal and ethical frameworks for AI governance with the following responsibilities.
 - Develop policies mandating fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI systems.
 - Set compliance standards for data governance, algorithmic explainability, and risk assessment.
 - Engage multi stakeholder collaborations for inclusive policy development.
2. Executive branch: Executes the rules through audits, enforcement and capacity building.
 - The role of this branch is to enforce and operationalise the policies defined by the legislative branch with the following responsibilities
 - Establish regulatory bodies to monitor compliance and enforce penalty for non-compliance
 - Oversee the lifecycle of AI systems, including audits and certifications for bias mitigation and prevention.
 - Facilitate capacity building for organisational readiness in AI adoption and risk management
3. Judiciary branch: Perceived as a reactive body not so active in direct governance.
 - The role of this branch is to ensure the AI regulations are interpreted and enforced in alignment with defined policies. Following are the responsibilities for this role
 - Resolve disputes arising from AI deployments such claims of bias, discrimination, privacy violations, or algorithmic harm.

- Mandates remedies, compensations, or changes to AI systems that cause harm, ensuring accountability.

	Legislative Branch	Executive Branch	Judiciary Branch
Teams / Departments	Compliance Team Risk Management Team Data Governance Team UX Teams (for user centric policies)	Executive Leadership, Product Owners/Business Leads, Operations Teams, IT & Infrastructure Team	Audit and Monitoring team AI Ethics Committee Appeals and Grievance Redressal Team Red-Teaming and Adversarial Testing Team
Roles	Define the overarching legal and ethical frameworks for AI governance.	Enforce and operationalise the policies defined by the legislative branch.	Ensures that AI regulations are interpreted and enforced in alignment with defined policies and principles.
Primary Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop laws mandating fairness, transparency, and accountability in AI systems. • Set compliance standards for data governance, algorithmic explainability, and risk assessments. • Engage multi-stakeholder councils for inclusive policy development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish regulatory bodies to monitor compliance and enforce penalties for non-compliance. • Oversee the lifecycle of AI systems, including audits and certifications for bias mitigation. • Facilitate capacity building for organisational readiness in AI adoption and risk management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The judiciary branch can remain a reactive body, without being part of the direct governance structure. • Adjudicating disputes • Ensuring rights are protected

Table 17: Capturing a conceptual Trias AI Politica governance structure

In the conceptual model in above table 17, the independence of the judiciary branch is playing a *dormant role* in direct governance ensures unbiased oversight free from policy adaption and operational pressures faced by legislative and executive branches. Thus, the Judicial branch can serve as reviewing critical checks and balances of potential overreach or misapplication of AI regulations by other branches. While the legislative and executive branches are central to the AI governance structure and processes, the judiciary ensures that the output of these structures and processes are fair, lawful, and compliant to policies. This reactive role compliments the proactive measures of other branches, closing the loop on governance by providing corrective mechanisms when necessary.

Trias AI Politica governance processes: The AI governance processes focus on implementing the policies, processes and technical mechanisms with all the identified oversight mechanisms effectively. Some of the key processes includes lifecycle risk-management, which ensures continuous monitoring and mitigation of risks, from the design and development stages to deployment and post deployment evaluations (Schwartz, R. et al , 2022). This iterative approach allows organisations to address emergent biases and adapt to changing societal regulatory expectations (NIST, 2023). Additionally, participatory design emphasises involving diverse stakeholders throughout the AI development process to address systematic and representational biases, aligning AI systems with societal values (UNESCO, 2023). Processes such as incident reporting and feedback loops enable the identification and resolution of bias-related issues, fostering organisational accountability and trust (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023).

Dynamic adaptability in governance processes ensures that policies and practices are regularly reviewed and updated in response to technological advancements and evolving risks (NIST, 2024). Together these processes form a robust foundation for ethical and responsible governance framework.

Trias AI Politica governance relational mechanisms: Inspired by relational mechanisms proposed by EGIT framework which focuses on the Business and IT alignment, the AI governance practices focus on actionable mechanisms that operationalise ethical principles and regulatory compliance within organisation. Practices like establishing AI ethics committee are essential for evaluating the societal and ethical implications of AI deployments, ensuring alignment with organisational and societal values (UNESCO, 2023). AI impact assessments provide a structured approach to accessing the potential risks and benefits of AI systems before deployment, addressing issues of fairness, bias and transparency (NIST, 2023). Collaborative stakeholder forums create spaces for ongoing dialogues among regulators, developers, and affected communities to inform decision-making and refine governance strategies (Prud'homme, B. et al , 2023). Use of public disclosure portals can enhance transparency where organisations are required to share critical information about AI systems, such as training data origins and risk management measures, promoting accountability and trust (Schwartz, R. et al , 2022). These governance practices can enable organisations to implement ethical AI systems effectively while building stakeholder confidence.

This governance framework combines *policy, process* and *technical measures* as three important factors to address biases in AI systems comprehensively. It targets biases at the *systemic, computational, and human* levels, emphasizing transparency, inclusivity, and accountability to foster trust and fairness in AI applications. This multi-dimensional approach equips stakeholders with actionable strategies for developing ethical equitable AI systems.

1. Policy based governance
 - a. Establishing governance standards: All the above-mentioned documents emphasise on creating formal governance structures that promote ethical AI practices, including mandatory transparency and accountability policies.
 - b. Ethical principles: Recommendations include embedding fairness, non-discrimination, and ethical use guidelines into AI governance frameworks
 - c. Inclusive stakeholder engagement: Incorporating diverse perspectives in decision-making processes helps address societal and institutional biases
 - d. Public accountability: Mandatory public disclosure of AI deployment and third-party audits ensure continuous oversight and public trust
2. Process driven approach
 - a. Lifecycle risk management: Embedding bias mitigation as a continuous process across pre-design, design, deployment, and evaluation stages.
 - b. Participatory and human centred design: Involving stakeholders from diverse backgrounds to incorporate social and cultural contexts during AI development.
 - c. Incident reporting mechanism: Establishing feedback loops for tracking, documenting, and addressing bias-related incidents.
 - d. Iterative testing and evaluation: Continuous validation of models for fairness, accuracy, and transparency ensures responsiveness to emergent biases
3. Technical mitigation techniques
 - a. Bias detection and mitigation tools: Leveraging statistical techniques, rebalancing methods, and causal models to identify and reduce biases in data and algorithms

- b. Explainability and traceability: Developing tools for model interpretability and transparent documentation of datasets and algorithmic decision-making processes
- c. Data quality controls: Ensuring high-quality, representative datasets and addressing gaps through robust data governance strategies.
- d. Proactive testing: Employing advanced methods, such as counterfactual prompts and adversarial testing, to identify potential bias risks in models before deployment.

Under the Trias Politica conceptual governance model, the legislative, executive, and judiciary branches play distinct yet interconnected roles in regulating AI adaption within organisations. The legislative branch establishes the foundation by creating legal and ethical frameworks that embedded fairness, transparency, and accountability into AI governance. The executive branch operationalises these policies by implementing robust oversight mechanisms, enforcing compliance, and fostering capacity building for stakeholders to manage AI risks effectively. Meanwhile, the judiciary branch provides essential oversight by interpreting laws, adjudicating disputes, and protecting fundamental rights in the context of AI systems. Together, these branches ensure that AI governance balances proactive policymaking, rigorous implementation, and independent adjudication, fostering ethical and accountable AI adaption within organisations.

Appendix – J

ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIAAIC	AI, Algorithmic and Automation Incidents and Controversies
AIM	AI Incident Monitor
APO	Align, Plan and Organise
BAO	Buitenlands Zaken Analyse Omgeving
BIA	Business Impact Analyses
BI/AI	Business Intelligence/Artificial Intelligence
CDD	Customer Due Diligence
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
COBIT	Control Objectives for Information Technologies
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
DL	Deep Learning
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessments
DUO	Dienst Uitvoering Onderwijs
EEC	European Economic Community
EGIT	Enterprise Governance of Information Technology
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenAI	Generative AI
GMM	Grey Matter Matters
GSS	Group Support System
GPAI	Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
IFRS	International Financial Reporting Standards
ISD	Information Supported Decision
IT	Information Technology
MASHA	Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MDD	Model Design Docs
ML	Machine Learning
MS	Microsoft
M365	Microsoft 365
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NVIS	New Visa Information System
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PDCA	Plan Do Check Act
PIA	Privacy Impact Assessments

PII	Personal Identifiable Information
RBI	Remote Biometric Identification
RMF	Risk Management Framework
RQ	Research Question
RSQ	Research Sub Question
SSV	Short Stay Visa
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
US	United States
2FA	Two Factor Authentication

Appendix – K

FIRST EXPERT VALIDATION SESSION REPORT

The following link opens with UAntwerp account.

[Verification workshop with experts on AI-Trias-Politica.pdf](#)

Date: 2024-09-12

Author: Bhuba and Davy

Verification workshop with experts on AI-Trias-Politica

Participants

1. BH
2. Davy
3. Michel Mulders
4. Yuri Bobbert
5. Jeroen simons
6. Dion Kotteleman
7. Hans Mulder

1. Introduction Bhuba & Davy

Dear Experts, Researchers, and Professors,

I hope this message finds you well. My name is Bhuban Hota, and together with my classmate Davy Meukens, we are currently pursuing our master's thesis at AMS on the topic of Governing AI with the Trias Politica under the supervision of our promotors, Prof. Dr. Hans Mulder and Prof. Dr. Bart Van Gils. Based on the recommendations of Prof. Mulder, we are excited to invite you to participate in a focused group discussion.

This session aims to gather experts to explore the feasibility of an AI governance framework. We will focus on applying the Trias Politica model to reduce bias in AI systems, using the Information Supported Decision/Short Stay Visa process (IOB/KVV process) implemented by the Dutch Ministry of Foreign affairs as a case study.

Objective

The discussion will focus on identifying key elements of an AI governance framework inspired by the Trias Politica model. We aim to explore how this model can be adapted to address bias-related risks during the adoption of AI systems, particularly within the context of the EU AI Act.

Date and Time

12th September 2024

Please select one of the following time slots: (We will choose one option when most of us can join)

- Option 1: 1:00 PM - 2:30 PM CET
- Option 2: 8:00 PM - 9:30 PM CET

[Location/Online Platform]: MS team invitation to follow based on the chosen time option.

Agenda

- Participant Introductions
- Presentation: Workshop Objectives and Scope
- Expert Insights: Adapting the Trias Politica Model for AI Governance
- Roundtable Discussion: Mitigating Bias-Related Risks in AI Adoption
- Participant Consensus Voting on the discussed topics

For your reference, please find attached the document outlining the topics and questions we will discuss during the session.

Your collective expertise will play a crucial role in shaping the AI governance framework. The diverse perspectives from professionals, academics, and researchers like yourself will provide a deeper understanding of the challenges and solutions in this field.

Please confirm your availability for one of the proposed time slots by 10th September. Should you have any questions or require further information, feel free to contact Davy or me by email.

We are looking forward to your participation in what promises to be a stimulating and productive discussion.

Best regards,
Bhuban Hota
Davy Meukens

1. Introduction Bhuba & Davy
2. Participant Introductions
3. Presentation: Workshop Objectives and Scope
4. Exercise
5. Exercise
6. Exercise
7. Roundtable Discussion: Mitigating Bias-Related Risks in AI Adoption
8. Participant Consensus Voting on the discussed topics
9. To What Degree Do You Agree with the Following Proposition?
10. Session 1: Understanding Case Study - NVIS System
11. Session 2: Trias Politica based AI Governance model in context of EU AI Act.
12. Session 3: Evaluating Trias Politica Model with Learnings from NVIS Case Study
13. Session 4: Gauge participants' opinions

2. Participant Consensus Voting on the discussed topics

To what degree do you agree with the following propositions

- 4 = completely agree
- 3 = agree
- 2 = disagree
- 1 = completely disagree

1. Existing governance frameworks in most organizations are inadequate for addressing the challenges posed by bias in AI.
2. Current AI governance practices are insufficient to address the evolving landscape of AI technology.
3. The principles of the Trias Politica are essential for designing effective AI governance frameworks.
4. A lack of a standardized AI governance approach directly contributes to the occurrence of bias in AI systems.
5. The EU AI Act provides a sufficient foundation for mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.
6. The EU AI Act needs to introduce further governance enhancements for mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.
7. Cross-industry collaboration is necessary to develop AI governance frameworks that comply with the EU AI Act.
8. Implementing a Trias Politica-based governance structure would have prevented the bias issue (acceptable threshold) in systems like the NVIS system.
9. The separation of powers within a Trias Politica-based governance structure is crucial for ensuring accountability and fairness in AI governance.
10. The judicial branch (in-company or outside role) of a Trias Politica-based governance structure should have the power to enforce bias mitigation (prevention) in AI systems.
11. A Trias Politica-based governance model can be effectively implemented across different organizational settings.

3. To What Degree Do You Agree with the Following Proposition?

To what degree do you agree with the following propositions

- 4 = completely agree
- 3 = agree
- 2 = disagree
- 1 = completely disagree

Evaluation method: Rate from 1 to N | Votes: 7

Table view

Item	Rating	A	Variability
1. Implementing a Trias Politica-based governance structure would have prevented the bias issue (acceptable threshold) in systems like the NVIS system.	2.9	0	74%
2. The judicial branch (in-company or outside role) of a Trias Politica-based governance structure should have the power to enforce bias mitigation (prevention) in AI systems.	3.6	0	69%
3. Current AI governance practices are insufficient to address the evolving landscape of AI technology.	3.1	0	65%

Item	Rating	A	Variability
4. A Trias Politica-based governance model can be effectively implemented across different organizational settings.	2.9	0	55%
5. The separation of powers within a Trias Politica-based governance structure is crucial for ensuring accountability and fairness in AI governance.	3.6	0	48%
6. The EU AI Act provides a sufficient foundation for mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.	2.3	0	46%
7. The EU AI Act needs to introduce further governance enhancements for mitigating bias-related risks in AI systems.	3.3	0	46%
8. The principles of the Trias Politica are essential for designing effective AI governance frameworks.	2.9	0	42%
9. Cross-industry collaboration is necessary to develop AI governance frameworks that comply with the EU AI Act.	3.1	0	42%
10. Existing governance frameworks in most organizations are inadequate for addressing the challenges posed by bias in AI.	3.7	0	30%
11. A lack of a standardized AI governance approach directly contributes to the occurrence of bias in AI systems.	3.9	0	23%

Comments

3. Current AI governance practices are insufficient to address the evolving landscape of AI technology.

- There is nothing

9. Cross-industry collaboration is necessary to develop AI governance frameworks that comply with the EU AI Act.

- Like OECD but this needs more the "how", so there your research can help.

10. Existing governance frameworks in most organizations are inadequate for addressing the challenges posed by bias in AI.

- AI has many perspectives, including legal, IT, operations, risk, and security, which requires a very broad approach. Many governance frameworks are insufficient, and many organisations have no framework at all.

Appendix – L

FOCUS GROUP REPORT

The following link opens with UAntwerp account.

[Validating Trias AI politica conceptual model with Implementation of MASHA at Achmea \(1\).pdf](#)

Date: 2025-01-09

Author: Bhuban Hota

Validating Trias AI politica conceptual model with Implementation of MASHA at Achmea

Participants

1. Davy
2. Bhubanananda Hota
3. Arjan
4. Carolijn Loonen
5. Duncan Prins
6. Yuri Bobbert
7. Rutger
8. Henri
9. Magali Kouwen
10. Henriëtte
11. Willeke
12. Arjan1

1. Introduction and agenda

Agenda

1. Introduction meeting agenda and short Introduction of audience
2. Short Presentation focusing on objective of workshop
3. Workshop structure with 3 sections involving voting, Q&A and brainstorm
4. Wrap-up

Objective

To gather insights on identifying key factors of an AI governance framework based on the Trias Politica model, to mitigate bias-related risks during the adoption of AI in organisations like Achmea.

Scope: Implementation of MASHA (Medical Acceptability Scoring Heuristic Algorithm) System at Achmea

1. Introduction and agenda
2. Short Presentation focusing on objective of workshop
3. Section 1: To What degree do you agree with the following statement:
4. 1. What degree do you agree with the use of the Trias Politica model as a conceptual framework for governing AI systems like MASHA?
5. Section 2: Q&A: Please answer to the following questions:
6. What monitoring mechanisms?
7. How does the executive branch enforce policies?
8. What processes or tools?
9. Section 3 - Brainstorm with Open discussion
10. Section 4 - Wrap-up

2. Short Presentation focusing on objective of workshop

There will be a presentation Highlighting the Purpose and Objective of the research. An overview of the already finished literature study and the conceptual Trias AI politica model.

3. Section 1: To What degree do you agree with the following statement:

Note: "What degree do you agree" questions will be in a scale of 1 to 4. Where the scale indicates as follows.

- 1 = Strongly disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Agree
- 4 = Strongly agree

Please provide comments for the questions.

1. What degree do you agree with the use of the Trias Politica model as a conceptual framework for governing AI systems like MASHA?
2. What degree do you agree that separating powers between executive, legislative, and judiciary branches helps mitigate bias-related risks in AI governance?
3. What degree do you agree that the separation of powers in the Trias Politica framework be practically implemented in an organization like Achmea for AI governance to ensure fairness and accountability?
4. What degree do you agree with the proposed conceptual roles and responsibilities of the executive branch, including strategy, resource allocation, and risk response?
5. What degree do you agree that the executive branch should be responsible for ensuring AI systems like MASHA align with Achmea's strategic objectives and ethical values?
6. What degree do you agree that the legislative branch should take the lead in creating policies that enforce data quality, algorithmic fairness, and bias mitigation?
7. What degree do you agree with the role of compliance teams in collaborating with external regulators to align with regulations like the EU AI Act?
8. What degree do you agree that the judiciary branch should focus on auditing AI systems for fairness, transparency, and compliance with governance policies?
9. What degree do you agree that the judiciary branch should oversee dispute resolution for AI decisions, such as grievances related to rejected insurance claims?
10. To What degree do you agree with the following statement: "Defining an acceptable threshold for bias measurement is a good approach to keeping bias under control in AI systems like MASHA."

4. 1. What degree do you agree with the use of the Trias Politica model as a conceptual framework for governing AI systems like MASHA?

Note: "What degree do you agree" questions will be in a scale of 1 to 4. Where the scale indicates as follows.

- 1 = Strongly disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Agree
- 4 = Strongly agree

Please provide comments for the questions.

Evaluation method: Rate from 1 to N | Votes: 9

Table view

Item	Rating	A	Variability
1. 10. To What degree do you agree with the following statement: "Defining an acceptable threshold for bias measurement is a good approach to keeping bias under control in AI systems like MASHA.	3.8	0	41%
2. 1. What degree do you agree with the use of the Trias Politica model as a conceptual framework for governing AI systems like MASHA?	3.6	0	33%

Item	Rating	A	Variability
3. 2. What degree do you agree that separating powers between executive, legislative, and judiciary branches helps mitigate bias-related risks in AI governance?	3.6	0	33%
4. 6. What degree do you agree that the legislative branch should take the lead in creating policies that enforce data quality, algorithmic fairness, and bias mitigation?	3.6	0	45%
5. 7. What degree do you agree with the role of compliance teams in collaborating with external regulators to align with regulations like the EU AI Act?	3.4	0	33%
6. 8. What degree do you agree that the judiciary branch should focus on auditing AI systems for fairness, transparency, and compliance with governance policies?	3.3	0	44%
7. 3. What degree do you agree that the separation of powers in the Trias Politica framework be practically implemented in an organization like Achmea for AI governance to ensure fairness and accountability?	3.2	0	27%
8. 5. What degree do you agree that the executive branch should be responsible for ensuring AI systems like MASHA align with Achmea's strategic objectives and ethical values?	3.2	0	52%
9. 4. What degree do you agree with the proposed conceptual roles and responsibilities of the executive branch, including strategy, resource allocation, and risk response?	3	0	44%
10. 9. What degree do you agree that the judiciary branch should oversee dispute resolution for AI decisions, such as grievances related to rejected insurance claims?	2.9	0	66%

Comments

1. 10. To What degree do you agree with the following statement: "Defining an acceptable

threshold for bias measurement is a good approach to keeping bias under control in AI systems like MASHA.

- We can't make an AI system 100% bias free. Hence a good idea.

2. 1. What degree do you agree with the use of the Trias Politica model as a conceptual framework for governing AI systems like MASHA?

- As MASHA is identified as a High Risk AI system.
- It can be another way to look at the AI governance. Although within Achmea we have an strong Governance model, and it is a big organization, so changing this view would be challenging

3. 2. What degree do you agree that separating powers between executive, legislative, and judiciary branches helps mitigate bias-related risks in AI governance?

- You can have a clear separation of powers, but an exchange of bias-related risks should be done to mitigate.
- By distributing these responsibilities, the risk of bias and misuse of AI can be reduced, as each branch can hold the others accountable.

4. 6. What degree do you agree that the legislative branch should take the lead in creating policies that enforce data quality, algorithmic fairness, and bias mitigation?

- They may not define all policies, some policies can be inherited from best practices. So they can play a role to select policies to the best interest of the organization and society as a whole.
- Also federation? You probably can't foresee everything...

5. 7. What degree do you agree with the role of compliance teams in collaborating with external regulators to align with regulations like the EU AI Act?

- It's a good idea, but how much support they get from the Regulators is unknown.

7. 3. What degree do you agree that the separation of powers in the Trias Politica framework be practically implemented in an organization like Achmea for AI governance to ensure fairness and accountability?

- Existing organizations it may be difficult. Some roles may be played by one person that has responsibility assigned to multiple branches.
- Maybe should be implemented but would be quite hard to do it company-wide
- I think mainly a lot of roles are implemented. Maybe some alignment is missing. But I don't have an inside on this.

- There is already a kind of such separation
- 3

8. 5. What degree do you agree that the executive branch should be responsible for ensuring AI systems like MASHA align with Achmea's strategic objectives and ethical values?

- This should be a responsibility of all branches?

5. Section 2: Q&A: Please answer to the following questions:

Please argument your decision

11. What monitoring mechanisms does the executive branch use to ensure MASHA delivers intended outcomes while avoiding bias or errors and how does the executive leadership handle risks flagged by legislative or judiciary branches during MASHA's operation?
12. How does the executive branch enforce policies during the AI lifecycle to ensure MASHA adheres to ethical and regulatory standards and what additional measures could the legislative branch implement to improve enforcement of AI governance policies and mitigate bias effectively?
13. What processes or tools (e.g., red-teaming or stress testing) does the judiciary branch use to identify and address potential bias or vulnerabilities in MASHA?

6. What monitoring mechanisms?

11. What monitoring mechanisms does the executive branch use to ensure MASHA delivers intended outcomes while avoiding bias or errors and how does the executive leadership handle risks flagged by legislative or judiciary branches during MASHA's operation?

1. Human Oversight; review critical decisions made by MASHA
2. Analytics Maturity Model?
3. Risk Management and Compliance
4. 2) our own model management tooling
5. 1) Performance Steering and Measurement Mechanisms:
6. 1) Using Microsoft AI en Data governance software with the promises that it will integrate with microsoft defender.
7. I don't know specifics of Masha. But looking at functionality of Microsoft to monitor.

7. How does the executive branch enforce policies?

12. How does the executive branch enforce policies during the AI lifecycle to ensure MASHA adheres to ethical and regulatory standards and what additional measures could the legislative branch implement to improve enforcement of AI governance policies and mitigate bias effectively?

1. Setting up Human-in-the-Loop Approache and feedback
2. softskill like training
3. Data ready and data quality
4. Preproduction checklist with quality gates
5. Statistical Metrics for Bias Detection (Red teaming, continious monitoring)

8. What processes or tools?

13. What processes or tools (e.g., red-teaming or stress testing) does the judiciary branch use to identify and address potential bias or vulnerabilities in MASHA?

1. Sentinel, MS defender
2. The elements in Foundry are embedded Purview functionalities.
3. Python homebrew stuff
4. Pureview, Foundry from MS

9. Section 3 - Brainstorm with Open discussion

What communication or collaboration mechanisms could be introduced to ensure seamless interaction between the executive, legislative, and judiciary branches in Achmea's AI governance?

1. What communication or collaboration mechanisms could be introduced to ensure seamless interaction between the executive, legislative, and judiciary branches in Achmea's AI governance?

10. Section 4 - Wrap-up

Appendix – M

FINAL EXPERT VALIDATION REPORT

The following link opens with UAntwerp account.

Trias AI politica Relevance Factors - Final Expert Validation Session.pdf

Date: 2025-05-06

Author: Bhuban Hota

Trias AI politica Relevance Factors - Final Expert Validation Session

Participants

1. Davy
2. Linda Terlouw
3. YuriBobbert
4. Stefanie
5. Jean-Hugues Migeon
6. Jelle de Boer
7. Johan
8. Hans
9. Bas van Gils
10. Bhubanananda Hota

1. Introduction and agenda

Agenda

1. Introduction meeting agenda and short Introduction of audience
2. Short Presentation focusing on objective of workshop and Research Findings
3. Workshop structure with 2 sections involving voting, and a brainstorm session
4. Wrap-up with closing remarks and Appreciation

Objective

Gather expert confidence ratings on relevance and completeness.

Brainstorm any Observations, Suggestions, Future directions and Implications of this research.

Purpose

Present research findings on AI governance factors for bias mitigation.

Seeking expert validation and feedback on The research findings to refine the research outcome.

1. Introduction and agenda
2. Short Presentation focusing workshop Objectives and Research Findings
3. Section 1: To What extent do you agree with the following statement:
4. What extent do you agree with the following statement:
5. Section 4 - Open Discussion on the Topic for any Final inputs
6. Closing Remarks & Appreciation

2. Short Presentation focusing workshop Objectives and Research Findings

The session will include a presentation detailing its purpose and objectives, as well as an overview of the findings and critical factors for developing a Trias AI Politica governance model to address bias-related risks in organizational AI implementations.

3. Section 1: To What extent do you agree with the following statement:

Note: "What extent do you agree" questions are in a scale of 1 to 4. The scale indicates as follows.

Likert Scale (1-4)

1 = Strongly disagree

2 = Disagree

3 = Agree

4 = Strongly agree

Please provide comments for the questions.

1. Trias Politica Separation of Powers (Structure): To what extent do you agree that applying the Trias Politica model (Legislative, Executive, Judiciary branches) in governance structure is effective in balancing decision-making to mitigate AI bias risks?
2. Integration into Corporate Governance: To what extent do you agree that embedding AI governance within broader enterprise governance structures enhances accountability and bias mitigation effectiveness?
3. Stakeholder Engagement of Shadow Powers: To what extent do you agree that explicitly considering informal stakeholder influences (e.g., advocacy groups, media) strengthens AI governance robustness against biases?
4. Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC): To what extent do you agree that integrating ethical and trustworthy AI principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC standards) substantially enhances fairness and reliability in AI governance?
5. Categorization of Bias Types: To what extent do you agree that identifying types of bias and their underlying root causes in AI implementations facilitates more targeted and effective bias management?
6. AI Governance Components (Policy, Process, Technical Controls): To what extent do you agree that clearly defined policy, process, and technical control mechanisms are effective in practically reducing AI-related biases?
7. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Build Phase): To what extent do you agree that initiating bias mitigation during the AI build phase (design, data collection, training, testing) is critical to proactively prevent biases?
8. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Use Phase): To what extent do you agree that continuous bias monitoring and adjustments during the AI use phase (Field trial, post-deployment, feedback loop) are necessary for effective bias risk management?
9. EU AI Act Compliance Requirements: To what extent do you agree that compliance with EU AI Act's mandatory transparency, risk management, data governance, and human

oversight requirements significantly reduces bias-related risks?

10. Overall Completeness: To what extent do you agree that the identified relevant factors comprehensively address governance requirements to mitigate AI bias-related risks under the EU AI Act?

4. What extent do you agree with the following statement:

Note: "What degree do you agree" questions are in a scale of 1 to 4. The scale indicates as follows.

- 1 = Strongly disagree
- 2 = Disagree
- 3 = Agree
- 4 = Strongly agree

Please provide comments for the questions.

Evaluation method: Rate from 1 to N | Votes: 7

Table view

Item	Rating	A	Variability
1. 3. Stakeholder Engagement of Shadow Powers: To what extent do you agree that explicitly considering informal stakeholder influences (e.g., advocacy groups, media) strengthens AI governance robustness against biases?	3.3	0	58%
2. 5. Categorization of Bias Types: To what extent do you agree that identifying types of bias and their underlying root causes in AI implementations facilitates more targeted and effective bias management?	3.4	0	48%

Item	Rating	A	Variability
3. 8. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Use Phase): To what extent do you agree that continuous bias monitoring and adjustments during the AI use phase (Field trial, post-deployment, feedback loop) are necessary for effective bias risk management?	3.4	0	48%
4. 10. Overall Completeness: To what extent do you agree that the identified relevant factors comprehensively address governance requirements to mitigate AI bias-related risks under the EU AI Act?	3	0	35%
5. 2. Integration into Corporate Governance: To what extent do you agree that embedding AI governance within broader enterprise governance structures enhances accountability and bias mitigation effectiveness?	3.6	0	32%
6. 4. Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC): To what extent do you agree that integrating ethical and trustworthy AI principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC standards) substantially enhances fairness and reliability in AI governance?	3.4	0	32%
7. 6. AI Governance Components (Policy, Process, Technical Controls): To what extent do you agree that clearly defined policy, process, and technical control mechanisms are effective in practically reducing AI-related biases?	3.4	0	32%
8. 1. Trias Politica Separation of Powers (Structure): To what extent do you agree that applying the Trias Politica model (Legislative, Executive, Judiciary branches) in governance structure is effective in balancing decision-making to mitigate AI bias risks?	3.3	0	30%
9. 7. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Build Phase): To what extent do you agree that initiating bias mitigation during the AI build phase (design, data collection, training, testing) is critical to proactively prevent biases?	3.7	0	30%

Item	Rating	A	Variability
10. 9. EU AI Act Compliance Requirements: To what extent do you agree that compliance with EU AI Act's mandatory transparency, risk management, data governance, and human oversight requirements significantly reduces bias-related risks?	3.1	0	23%

Comments

1. 3. Stakeholder Engagement of Shadow Powers: To what extent do you agree that explicitly considering informal stakeholder influences (e.g., advocacy groups, media) strengthens AI governance robustness against biases?

- Always important to factor informal stakeholders, but try to relate it to formal powers
- Incorporating informal stakeholders—especially the press, advocacy groups, and civil society—into the governance of AI is not just a democratic virtue but a practical necessity. These actors enhance system responsiveness, reveal hidden harms, and push for ethical reflection, making AI governance more resilient, adaptive, and inclusive. Recognizing their influence explicitly is therefore a strategically sound approach to mitigate bias and strengthen public trust.
- Very important, whilst lobbying may negatively influence, it also gives perspective. Involving all types of actors will help.
- Although I agree that considering information stakeholder influences is important for any governance, I don't agree that it is particularly effective for AI governance or protection against bias in particular.
- All stakeholders play a role in procuring, implementing, running and decommissioning AI

2. 5. Categorization of Bias Types: To what extent do you agree that identifying types of bias and their underlying root causes in AI implementations facilitates more targeted and effective bias management?

- Integrating ethical and trustworthy AI principles from globally respected institutions into governance structures is a substantive step toward ensuring AI fairness and reliability. These frameworks not only elevate normative standards but also provide practical mechanisms to anticipate and mitigate harm, build public trust, and embed human-centric values in AI design and implementation. Their integration is, therefore, a crucial enabler of responsible AI governance.
- In essence, it helps but is not sufficient per se as a measure as Bias categorization

brings itself bias again based on the type of datasets selected on the type of bias that will be treated. Culturally speaking the bias or the weight given to counter a certain bias will differ (e.g. racial discrimination in the US is way more a concern than in East Asia).

- You have to. The whole idea of AI is to detect patterns, but you have to find out which patterns are not desirable in your results.
- I agree strongly. I feel like making the lists of potential biases longer, trying to make the list seem more 'complete' is actually counterproductive. Every potential bias you list needs to be concretely distinct from all the other biases on the list, otherwise the structure of the list should be changed to accommodate this.
- Vital to do opportunity and risk assessment and develop proper treatment plans. Categories help to understand, create awareness, feed discussions and qualified decision making

3. 8. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Use Phase): To what extent do you agree that continuous bias monitoring and adjustments during the AI use phase (Field trial, post-deployment, feedback loop) are necessary for effective bias risk management?

- Bias in AI systems is not a one-time fix; it is a persistent and evolving challenge. Continuous monitoring and adaptive mitigation during the use phase are therefore indispensable for effective bias risk management. This approach ensures AI systems remain fair, reliable, and aligned with societal values throughout their operational lifecycle.
- Continuous bias monitoring is extremely important as bias but more pre-production. This is even more important in production; whilst monitoring also the effect of users on the AI learning curve; (e.g. the case of Godwin point for all AI models until now : if users feedback are integrated, then systematically any AI turns to a Nazi AI...)
- You have to acknowledge the concept of data drift, the statistical properties of data in a certain domain may vary over time.
- I feel like probably most bias mitigation needs to happen in the build phase. On the other hand, continuous monitoring is necessary and surely obligated to continually be able to show that no bias has been introduced.

4. 10. Overall Completeness: To what extent do you agree that the identified relevant factors comprehensively address governance requirements to mitigate AI bias-related risks under the EU AI Act?

- All important factors, but don't forget about the unintended side effects
- I seem to be missing the concept of norms. The European Commission made a standardization request to CEN/CENELEC (European standardization organizations) to

make norms for the AI Act. These norms will not be mandatory, but they will give a presumption of compliance. So when you apply these norms, it is presumed you also comply with the law.

- This I am sort of unsure of. I feel like different 'typologies' are being mixed (what-when-how-why-etc vs structure-process-people vs AI-act-principles-policy-law). The result is that I am not confident that this is a 'closed' or 'complete' set of factors that fully addresses all possible perspectives on the matter.

5. 2. Integration into Corporate Governance: To what extent do you agree that embedding AI governance within broader enterprise governance structures enhances accountability and bias mitigation effectiveness?

- It is necessary
- Embedding AI governance within the enterprise's existing governance architecture does more than improve compliance—it embeds ethical accountability into the DNA of the organization. This approach increases both the capability and credibility of efforts to detect, mitigate, and prevent bias in AI systems. As such, it is a strategically effective and institutionally sustainable path to responsible AI governance.
- I believe it's necessary, it's not really possible (or at least not desirable) to do it otherwise (which implies keeping it separate).
- This is a central precondition since Corporations nowadays rely on Technology, which in the near future will be built upon AI technology in all their processes. Thus, they need to have integrated governance SPRM. It's also critical to create a countervailing power to avoid bias, drifting, and hallucinations on all levels of AI.

6. 4. Ethical and Trustworthy AI Principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC): To what extent do you agree that integrating ethical and trustworthy AI principles (OECD, UNESCO, EEC standards) substantially enhances fairness and reliability in AI governance?

- I agree with this, although I sometimes feel overwhelmed with the wide variety of different sets of principles you can subscribe to, made by various official bodies.
- Models help with structure, but applying models (e.g. frameworks, risk assessments etc) is crucial. All companies suffer from a quick and good start but lack in discipline and rigour hygiene to run this.

7. 6. AI Governance Components (Policy, Process, Technical Controls): To what extent do you agree that clearly defined policy, process, and technical control mechanisms are effective in practically reducing AI-related biases?

- Somewhat, the point is that too many processes, policy etc may lead to worse results in

AI. Data scientists also need the opportunity to experiment and to learn (for success as well as failure).

- Although I am not 100% sure about this typology. In the GDPR for example we commonly see organisational versus technical measures that need to be taken (a two-way split rather than three-way). I'm not convinced either one is perfect, but it's something think about.
- Vital to adhere to standards to accept, transfer, mitigate and treat risks and opportunities. Without boundaries, corporations create anarchy

8. 1. Trias Politica Separation of Powers (Structure): To what extent do you agree that applying the Trias Politica model (Legislative, Executive, Judiciary branches) in governance structure is effective in balancing decision-making to mitigate AI bias risks?

- The structure works quite well in my opinion, so I agree, but there are structures that are intended for this kind of purpose (like 3LM), which probably makes more sense.
- By distributing responsibilities and enforcing mutual oversight, the Trias Politica model introduces a systemic balance that is well-suited for governing AI in a way that limits the risk of bias, ensures accountability, and upholds democratic values. Thus, applying this model is not only effective but essential in the face of increasingly complex algorithmic decision-making.
- The concept of trias politica is of course initially created to counter the absolute power of the king. It deals with the relationship between public authority and civilians. In a company the board is in the lead and is accountable to stake holders. How comparable are a society and a company? Can you really use this principle in the same way?
- I feel fairly confident this could work, but so far I haven't exactly been convinced of it yet, by the work I've seen. I saw no result that concretely answers this question.
- This is a central precondition since you want to create a countervailing power to avoid bias, drifting, and hallucinating on all levels of the AI

9. 7. Timing of Mitigation Measures (Build Phase): To what extent do you agree that initiating bias mitigation during the AI build phase (design, data collection, training, testing) is critical to proactively prevent biases?

- Continuous bias monitoring is extremely important as bias may evolve and feedback loop is the only way for an AI to improve in all matters.
- I feel like with AI in particular it's extremely difficult to retroactively remove or mitigate bias, because of the black-box nature of many AI applications.

10. 9. EU AI Act Compliance Requirements: To what extent do you agree that compliance

with EU AI Act's mandatory transparency, risk management, data governance, and human oversight requirements significantly reduces bias-related risks?

- It is a start, it helps, but it is not enough by itself
- The EU AI Act does more than articulate ethical ideals—it enforces concrete measures that compel organizations to identify, document, and mitigate bias risks across the AI value chain. By institutionalizing transparency, accountability, and data integrity, the Act offers a legally backed framework that significantly reduces the likelihood and impact of algorithmic discrimination. Compliance is therefore not only a legal obligation but also a pragmatic strategy for bias risk management.
- It is not sufficient in itself, EU AI Act has already flaws such as only differentiating based on the role of the company providing the AI or the applications of an AI system but does not consider the structure and the stage from which a company uses an AI (e.g. Consumer app, Enterprise AI, fine-tuned model, pre-trained, from scratch).
- I do believe in the concepts of transparency, risk management etc help in reducing bias. However, the auditor should work very closely with the data scientists to understand what's actually going on. Just 'ticking boxes' on audit forms will not help to actually reduce bias.
- It does, although I am not 100% convinced that it fully solves the problem. Then again, no list of measures could make me 100% convinced.
- Vital since US BigTech is using our (personal) data as currency

5. Section 4 - Open Discussion on the Topic for any Final inputs

1. I would be interested to see a stronger mapping/stronger focus on trying to understand the governance that you found in the case study as related to the trias politica. I think doing so would lead to one of the most interesting aspects related to trias politica that I always found: what happens on the edge-cases, or where are exceptions made to the trias politica (like our cabinet members also having legislative powers). Another possible avenue: trias politica always implies a possible fourth power (media?) or even fifth (power of the civic servant?).
2. Is the Trias politica more helpful than other risk mitigating frameworks, like 3LM?
3. How do you see the role of research/academia in the trias politica model?
4. I miss the role of norms made by standardization organizations (CEN/CENELEC). Made a comment about this in the last question.
5. Would the effectiveness of Trias Politica differ based on the type organization that it applied in (Decentralized vs. Centralized organizations).
6. Would the Trias Politica be applicable to all concept/approach to AI ? (e.g. AI in East Asia does not have the same impact and implications than in Europe or than in North America or in Africa).

WORKS CITED

- Aswani, R. (2020, July 28). *Conceptualizing AI as a General Purpose Technology*. Retrieved from nasscom community: <https://community.nasscom.in/communities/emerging-tech/ai/conceptualizing-ai-as-a-general-purpose-technology.html>
- Australian Government. (2024). *White Paper on AI Governance*. Retrieved from Governance Institute of Australia: <https://www.governanceinstitute.com.au/app/uploads/2024/09/GovInst-AI-Whitepaper.pdf>
- Batool, A. et al. (2025, January 14). *AI governance: a systematic literature review*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-024-00653-w>
- Berente, N. e. (2021, September). *Managing Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352400557_Managing_Artificial_Intelligence
- Birkstedt, T. et al. (2023, June 27). *AI governance: themes, knowledge gaps and future agendas*. Retrieved from emerald insight: <https://doi.org/10.1108/INTR-01-2022-0042>
- Bobbert, Y., & van Dijk, V. (2023, Oct 1). *An Exploration of AI Risk & Collaborative Assessment Methodology*. Retrieved from ISACA: <https://isaca.nl/an-exploration-of-ai-risk-collaborative-assessment-methodology/>
- Chen, Y. et al. (2023, November 27). *Novel research and future prospects of artificial intelligence in cancer diagnosis and treatment*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13045-023-01514-5>
- Chiappetta, A. (2023, December 5). *Navigating the AI frontier: European parliamentary insights on bias and regulation, preceding the AI Act*. Retrieved from Internet Policy Review: <https://doi.org/10.14763/2023.4.1733>
- CIRIS. (2024). Retrieved from Learning Center: <https://www.ciris.info/learningcenter/triapolitica/>
- Contreras, B. (2024, February 8). *Tougher AI Policies Could Protect Taylor Swift—And Everyone Else—From Deepfakes*. Retrieved from Scientific American: <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/tougher-ai-policies-could-protect-taylor-swift-and-everyone-else-from-deepfakes/>
- Dartmouth. (2024). *Artificial Intelligence Coined at Dartmouth*. Retrieved from Dartmouth: <https://home.dartmouth.edu/about/artificial-intelligence-ai-coined-dartmouth>
- De Haes, S. et al. (2020). *Enterprise governance of information technology : achieving alignment and value in digital organisations*. Antwerp: Springer.
- EC/OECD. (2021). *National AI policies & strategies*. Retrieved from OECD.AI: <https://oecd.ai/en/dashboards/overview>
- EU. (2024, July 12). *European Union*. Retrieved from EUR-lex: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1689>
- EU. (2024, June 13). *REGULATION (EU) 2024/1689 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL*. Retrieved from EUR-Lex: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>
- EU FRA. (2022). *Bias in Algorithms – Artificial Intelligence and Discrimination*. Vienna: Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2021, April 21). *Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence 2021 Review*. Retrieved from European Commission Shaping Europe's digital future: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/coordinated-plan-artificial-intelligence-2021-review>

- European Commission. (2024). *AI Act*. Retrieved from European Commission: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>
- European Commission Press corner. (2024, August 1). Retrieved from European Commission: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_24_4123
- European Parliament. (2023, June 20). *What is artificial intelligence and how is it used?* Retrieved from Topics European Parliament: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20200827STO85804/what-is-artificial-intelligence-and-how-is-it-used>
- Favier, M. et al. (2023, September 20). *How to be fair? A study of label and selection bias*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-023-06401-1>
- Ferrara, E. (2024, December 26). *Fairness and Bias in Artificial Intelligence: A Brief Survey of Sources, Impacts, and Mitigation Strategies*. Retrieved from MDPI Open Access Journals: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sci6010003>
- Gichoya, J. W. et al. (2023, September 23). *AI pitfalls and what not to do: mitigating bias in AI*. Retrieved from Oxford Academic: <https://doi.org/10.1259/bjr.20230023>
- Government UK. (2023, November 29). *Ethics, Transparency and Accountability Framework for Automated Decision-Making*. Retrieved from GOV.UK: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/ethics-transparency-and-accountability-framework-for-automated-decision-making/ethics-transparency-and-accountability-framework-for-automated-decision-making>
- Heikkila, M. (2022, March 29). *Dutch scandal serves as a warning for Europe over risks of using algorithms*. Retrieved from Politico: <https://www.politico.eu/article/dutch-scandal-serves-as-a-warning-for-europe-over-risks-of-using-algorithms/>
- Hoogervorst, J. (2017). *Foundations of Enterprise Governance and Enterprise Engineering*. Springer.
- Iowa State University. (2024). *History*. Retrieved from Iowa State University: <https://www.cs.iastate.edu/history>
- ISACA. (2018, November 14). *COBIT 2019 Framework: Governance and Management Objectives*. ISACA.
- ISACA. (2025, 1 31). *Leveraging COBIT for Effective AI System Governance*. Retrieved from www.isaca.org: <https://www.isaca.org/resources/white-papers/2025/leveraging-cobit-for-effective-ai-system-governance>
- ISED. (2022, June 16). *The Artificial Intelligence and Data Act (AIDA) – Companion document*. Retrieved from Government of Canada: <https://ised-isde.canada.ca/site/innovation-better-canada/en/artificial-intelligence-and-data-act-aida-companion-document>
- Mallinson, D. J. (2023, May 15). *Catching up with AI: Pushing toward a cohesive governance framework*. Retrieved from Wiley: <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/polp.12529>
- Mäntyrnäki, M. et al. (2022, February 24). *Defining organisational AI governance*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-022-00143-x>
- Mayank, G. (2025, January 27). Retrieved from www.appliedaicourse.com: <https://www.appliedaicourse.com/blog/ai-vs-ml-vs-dl/>
- NIST. (2022, MAR). *Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from NIST: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/NIST.SP.1270.pdf>
- NIST. (2023, January). *Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework*. Retrieved from NIST: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.AI.100-1>

- NIST. (2024, July 26). *Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework: Generative Artificial Intelligence Profile*. Retrieved from NIST: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.AI.600-1>
- OECD. (2022, February 22). *OECD Framework for the Classification of AI systems*. Retrieved from OECD/Publications: <https://doi.org/10.1787/cb6d9eca-en>
- OECD. (2023, November 29). *Unsupervised bias detection tool*. Retrieved from OECD.AI: <https://oecd.ai/en/catalogue/tools/unsupervised-bias-detection-tool>
- OECD. (2025). *AI incidents and hazards monitor*. Retrieved from OECD AI: https://oecd.ai/en/incidents?search_terms=%5B%5D&and_condition=false&from_date=2014-01-01&to_date=2025-05-09&properties_config=%7B%22principles%22:%5B%5D,%22industries%22:%5B%5D,%22harm_types%22:%5B%5D,%22harm_levels%22:%5B%5D,%22harmed_entities%22:%5B%5D
- OECD.AI. (2025). *About OECD.AI*. Retrieved from OECD.AI: <https://oecd.ai/en/about/about-gpai>
- OECD.AI. (2025). *About OECD.AI*. Retrieved from OECD.AI: <https://oecd.ai/en/>
- Olavsrud, T. (2024, October 2). *Amazon AI-enabled recruitment tool only recommended men*. Retrieved from 12 famous AI disasters: <https://www.cio.com/article/190888/5-famous-analytics-and-ai-disasters.html?amp=1>
- Papagiannidis, E. et al. (2022, April 20). *Toward AI Governance: Identifying Best Practices and Potential Barriers and Outcomes*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-022-10251-y>
- Parnas, D. L. (2017, September 25). *Communication of the ACM > The real risks of artificial intelligence*. Retrieved from ACM digital library: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3132724>
- Perset, K. et al. (2024, March 5). *Explanatory memorandum on the updated OECD definition of an AI system*. Retrieved from OECD Artificial Intelligence Papers: <https://doi.org/10.1787/623da898-en>
- Prud'homme, B. et al. (2023, April 18). *Missing links in AI governance*. Retrieved from UNESCO Publication: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/missing-links-ai-governance>
- Ritchie, J. et al. (2013). *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. London: Sage Publications.
- Rivas, P., & Das Jui, T. (2024, January 31). *Fairness issues, current approaches, and challenges in machine learning models*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13042-023-02083-2>
- Roser, M. (2022, December 6). *The brief history of artificial intelligence: the world has changed fast — what might be next?* Retrieved from Our World in Data: <https://ourworldindata.org/brief-history-of-ai>
- Schmidhuber, J. (2019, October 4). *Deep Learning Miraculous year 1990-91*. Retrieved from <https://people.idsia.ch/~juergen/deep-learning-miraculous-year-1990-1991.html>
- Schneider, M., & Steimers, A. (2022, March 18). *Sources of risks of AI systems*. Retrieved from MDPI: doi: 10.3390/ijerph19063641
- Schwartz, R. et al. (2022, March 15). *Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from NIST: <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1270>
- Shah, M., & Sureja, N. (2024, May 8). *A Comprehensive Review of Bias in Deep Learning Models: Methods, Impacts, and Future Directions*. Retrieved from Springer Nature Link: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11831-024-10134-2>
- Shaping Europe's digital future*. (2019, April 8). Retrieved from Library: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

- Shaping Europe's digital future*. (2018, June 14). Retrieved from News & Views: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/commission-appoints-expert-group-ai-and-launches-european-ai-alliance>
- Shaping Europe's digital future*. (2025, February 18). Retrieved from AI ACT: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/regulatory-framework-ai>
- Stanford University. (2023). *The AI Index 2023 Annual Report*. Stanford: The Stanford Institute for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence (HAI). Retrieved from www.hai.stanford.edu: https://hai-production.s3.amazonaws.com/files/hai_ai-index-report_2023.pdf
- Stanford University. (2024). *The AI Index 2024 Annual Report*. Stanford: The Stanford Institute for Human-Centered Artificial Intelligence (HAI).
- Stankovich, M. et al. (2023). *Global toolkit on AI and the rule of law for the judiciary*. Retrieved from UNESCO UNESDOC Digital Library: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000387331>
- Strycker, C., & Kavlakoglu, E. (2024, Augustus 9). *What is artificial intelligence (AI)?* Retrieved from www.ibm.com: <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/artificial-intelligence>
- Stryker, C., & Scapicchio, M. (2024, March 22). *What is generative AI?* Retrieved from www.ibm.com: <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/generative-ai>
- The University of Tokyo. (2023, September 15). *Towards Responsible AI Deployment Policy Recommendations for the Hiroshima AI Process*. Retrieved from Institute for Future Initiatives The University of Tokyo: https://ifi.u-tokyo.ac.jp/en/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/policy_recommendation_tg_20230915e.pdf
- Tweede Kamer. (2024, April 29). *Antwoord op vragen het lid Dekker-Abdulaziz over het bericht over het visumbeleid door het ministerie van Buitenlandse Zaken*. Retrieved from Tweede Kamer: <https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/kamervragen/detail?id=2023Z17966&did=2024D17775>
- UNESCO. (2023, May 16). *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*. Retrieved from UNESCO Publication: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/recommendation-ethics-artificial-intelligence>
- van Gils, B. (2023). *Data in Context*. Springer.
- van Gils, B., & Mulder, J. B. (2023). *Governing AI with Trias Politica*. Antwerp Management School (AMS).
- Vickers, C. (2024, July 4). *How AI risks creating a 'black box' at the heart of US legal system*. Retrieved from THE HILL: <https://thehill.com/business/personal-finance/4571982-ai-black-box-legal-system/>
- Vroom, R. W., & Horvath, I. (2014, January). *Editorial: How are product development and engineering processes enhanced by involving research?* Retrieved from ResearchGate: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261215955_Editorial_How_are_product_development_and_engineering_processes_enhanced_by_involving_research
- Wheeler, T. (2023, June 15). *Commentary The three challenges of AI regulation*. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/the-three-challenges-of-ai-regulation/>
- Whicher, D. et al. (2022). *Avoiding Racial Bias in Child Welfare Agencies' Use of Predictive Risk Modeling*. Washington: U.S. DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES.

- Woollacott, E. (2023, August 17). *ChatGPT Has Liberal Bias, Say Researchers*. Retrieved from Forbes: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/emmawoollacott/2023/08/17/chatgpt-has-liberal-bias-say-researchers/>
- Young, S. D. (2024, March 28). Retrieved from www.whitehouse.gov: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/M-24-10-Advancing-Governance-Innovation-and-Risk-Management-for-Agency-Use-of-Artificial-Intelligence.pdf>
- Zhou, N. et al. (2022). Bias, Fairness and Accountability with Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Algorithms. *International Statistical Review*.